

ACTAS | PROCEEDINGS

STAR Global Conference 2023: Transformative Education for an Interconnected and Equitable World

Cátedra UNESCO:
*Educación transformadora:
ciencia, comunicación e sociedade*

Universidade de Vigo

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STAR Global Conference 2023:
Transformative Education for an
Interconnected and Equitable World

Edited by:

Elena de Prada Creo

Bo Zhang

Alba Quintairos Soliño

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PRÓLOGO | PREFACE

Introduction: A Journey Through Transformative Education

In undertaking the ambitious task of encapsulating the essence of the STAR Global Conference 2023, I am humbled by the vast expanse of knowledge and perspectives shared under the theme of "Transformative Education for an Interconnected and Equitable World." I am particularly struck by the thoughtfulness of the editors of this volume, Dr. Elena de Prada Creo, Dr. Bo Zhang, and Dr. Alba Quintairos-Soliño. My gratefulness also extends to the members of the scientific committee. Hosted in partnership with the University of Vigo and UNESCO Chairs, this conference became a melting pot of innovative ideas, where the brightest minds in academia converged to redefine the paradigms of higher education. This preface, while a modest attempt to capture the spirit of our discussions, is a tribute to the collective wisdom that emanated from this significant global gathering.

Ethical Frontiers in Modern Academia

The conference prominently featured discussions around the ethical challenges in contemporary academic pursuits. Highlighted by Manuel Curado's insightful keynote, this theme was echoed in papers like "Digital Bill: An Approach to Minimize Illicit Activities and Other Drawbacks of Crypto Currency" by Romel Sharif and "Evaluación de la eficacia de las plataformas educativas en la universidad" by Amparo Rodriguez Damian. The ethical quandary in research and education is further exemplified by the UNESCO's report on "Futures of Education," which calls for a renewed ethical framework to guide scientific inquiry and educational practices. This theme underscores the necessity of an ethical compass in guiding our advancements, ensuring that our progress is aligned with the values of integrity, responsibility, and sustainability.

Embracing the Digital Revolution

Digital technology's transformative impact on education was a recurring theme, with keynotes like that of Paz Prendes-Espinosa setting the stage for a broader discussion. Papers such as "Zooming from Palestine and Ohio: Lessons from Facilitating a Virtual Intercultural Dialogue" by Roger Anderson and Ms. Shahd As'ad, and "Engineering Virtual Labs for E-learning" by Míriam Timiraos et al.,

showcased the potential of digital tools in enhancing educational access and quality. The World Bank's "World Development Report 2021" highlights that digital advancements can play a pivotal role in achieving inclusive and equitable quality education, as outlined in the Sustainable Development Goal 4. These discussions at the conference emphasized the importance of harnessing digital technologies to create more inclusive, adaptive, and innovative educational environments.

Fostering Global Connections and Mutual Learning

The conference's focus on internationalization and global engagement was exemplified in numerous presentations, building upon the insights of keynotes like Pilar Mendoza. Papers such as "International students' gains in mobility programmes" by Adriana Pérez-Encinas et al., and "Educational collaboration and internationalization in China" by Marcia Sun, highlighted the importance of global connections in enriching the educational experience. According to the OECD's "Education at a Glance 2020" report, international education plays a crucial role in fostering mutual understanding and global competencies. These discussions underlined the significance of developing sustainable international partnerships that go beyond mere academic exchanges to cultivate a sense of global citizenship and shared responsibility.

Cultivating Creativity and Innovation

Creativity and innovation in education, themes central to keynotes like that of Mark A. Runco, were also echoed across various sessions. Papers such as "Unlocking the potential: fostering creativity and innovation in teachers for professional development" by Yadu Prasad Gyawali and "The Roadmap for Developing an Introductory Artificial Intelligence Course in Teacher Education" by Valerie Riggs & Sharif Uddin, demonstrated the diverse approaches to embedding creativity and innovation in educational practices. The European Commission's report on "Innovation in Education" underscores the need for education systems to adapt and encourage creative thinking to meet the challenges of the 21st century. These presentations at the conference highlighted the vital role of creativity and innovative thinking in shaping sustainable and responsive educational systems.

Building a Sustainable and Inclusive Future

Sustainability and inclusivity were overarching themes, with presentations exploring how these principles can be effectively integrated into educational

practices. From "Promoting international cooperation in Online Postgraduate Programs to Higher Educational Institutions in disadvantaged countries" by Ranwa Khorsheed to "School leadership under covid-19 pandemic: a critique of the South African school context" by Mmalefikana Sylvia Sepeng, the range of topics underscored the multifaceted nature of sustainability in education. The United Nations' "The Sustainable Development Goals Report 2020" highlights the critical role of education in achieving sustainable development. These discussions at the conference emphasized the need for educational practices and policies to be environmentally sustainable and socially inclusive, ensuring equitable access to quality education for all.

Concluding Reflections: Charting a Path Forward

As we reflect on the STAR Global Conference 2023, it becomes clear that the path to a more sustainable and equitable future in higher education is complex yet attainable. The insights and discussions presented throughout the conference not only advanced the discourse on sustainable practices but also highlighted our collective responsibility to embrace and implement these practices. This gathering, inspired by the intellectual legacy of Professor Noam Chomsky and exemplified by the recipients of the A. Noam Chomsky Global Connections Award, serves as a powerful reminder of our duty to foster an academic environment that is intellectually robust, ethically sound, and aligned with the principles of sustainability.

These proceedings stand as a beacon of hope and a call to action, urging all stakeholders in education – from academics to policymakers, administrators, and students – to engage actively in the pursuit of a more sustainable, inclusive, and innovative educational landscape. As we forge ahead, let us carry the insights and inspirations from this conference, committed to transforming higher education into a force for positive change in our global community. Let this preface and the proceedings it introduces serve as a guide and a source of inspiration, illuminating the path toward a future where education is not just a tool for personal advancement but a catalyst for global sustainability and equity.

UTTAM GAULEE
STAR Scholars President

I

KEYNOTES

DIGITAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP FOR UNIVERSITIES: A FRAMEWORK OF COMPETENCES FOR STUDENTS, TEACHERS AND INSTITUTIONS

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

To accept a merely business vision of entrepreneurship is to have a very limited vision in which there are many aspects that escape. Digital entrepreneurship can be analyzed from a business and economic perspective, more linked to the creation of new businesses, or in a clearly different line it can be studied from a training perspective. In the latter case, we understand digital entrepreneurship as the knowledge, skills and attitudes that enable people to tackle innovative initiatives linked in one way or another to the digital world. This relationship between entrepreneurship and digitalization can come either from the use of digital technologies to launch a project or because the innovative initiative itself is linked to the world of digital technologies, having as its goal a digital innovation in itself or taking place in the virtual world.

Thus, entrepreneurship is a construct closely linked to civic responsibility and citizenship, as well as to the progress of our environment. The European Commission (2006, p. 8) defines entrepreneurship competence as the ability “to transform ideas into action” involving creativity, innovation, the attitude of risk-taking and other abilities to manage projects, to manage people or to solve problems. And all this knowledge must be supported by ethical values in our social context.

From this more global and holistic perspective (European Commission, 2014), we approach digital entrepreneurship as a core competence for all universities that influences: 1) on the one hand, university students, who must acquire digital entrepreneurship competences; 2) teachers, who must train their students in this area; 3) the curriculum and institutions, as digital entrepreneurship as a cross-cutting core competence has to mark - together with other competences - instructional design and institutions have to organise services and initiatives to support young digital entrepreneurs.

In our research work (EmDigital Project funded by the Seneca Foundation and MAEDU Project funded by the Ministry of Science and Universities) we propose a model that comprehensively addresses all these axes in relation to digital entrepreneurship. Our main pillar is the model EmDigital (Prendes et al., 2021; Prendes, 2022) focused on university students and the areas of competence to be promoted in our higher education system.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Digital Entrepreneurship, University, Competences, Training, Digital Technologies

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THE HIGH PRICE OF A GOOD THING: A REFLECTION ON THE COSTS OF ETHICAL EVALUATION OF SCIENCE

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

This communication is organized around the following argument: as there is no education without science and there cannot be science without ethics, it follows that the process of ethical evaluation of scientific projects must be thought about in depth, contributing to the dissemination of the notion of an ethically responsible science. There is, therefore, a need to educate the population regarding the ethical evaluation protocols of scientific research projects, mitigating the secrecy and elitism that usually characterize this evaluation. Starting by explaining how science ethics committees work, it is shown that the ethical review of projects has many internal problems of which neither its members nor society in general are aware. Some of these problems are inventoried and explained: (i.) ethics committees operate according to rules that are different from the normal way of life; (ii.) despite being called “ethics committees”, there are in fact no broad ethical debates at their meetings, and, often, the review of projects submitted to the committees is limited to checking possible legal problems; (iii.) each evaluation deals with specific projects, making it impossible to reflect on the social context of the projects, which means that societies that invest in science ethics accept other social processes that harm ethics; (iv.) no scientific advance was actually prevented by ethics committees, which, in the most serious cases, only postponed its achievement; (v.) ethics committees do not have superior guidelines to clearly separate scientific investigations from social and political activism, as many projects mix science and activism in the theoretical foundation they offer to committee members; (vi.) some international organizations, when promoting ethical debates on certain subjects, contribute more to the promotion of these subjects than to ethical

reflection on them; (vii.) the inability of ethics committees not to be influenced by tables of values that have been promoted in recent decades is denounced. As a result of this analysis, it is concluded that ethics committees, despite their number having grown, have been emptied of their most important functions, namely that of the sapiential guidance of society in areas in which techniques and scientific knowledge have very relevant consequences, sometimes even dramatic. Contrary to the purely symbolic relevance of the committees and the factual irrelevance in the ethical advice of societies with regard to the application of science, a review of the committees' operating protocols is advocated. The communication therefore ends with the demonstration that societies pay a very high price for the benefits of ethics committees.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Ethical Evaluation, Scientific Projects, Ethics Committees, Social Context, Costs

INTERNATIONALIZATION STRATEGIES BASED ON MUTUALITY

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

International partnerships are likely to result in scientific colonization, which privileges the academic norms, language (English), and publishing patterns of nations in the Global North, primarily the Anglo-Saxon powers. Neoliberal rewards system leads to what has been termed parachute research, in which scholars of the Global North partner with scholars in lower-income nations for short periods, deterring the possibility of building a sustainable, meaningful, and long-lasting relationship (George Mwangi & Yao, 2021). Many involved in international partnerships assume a savior mentality based on the problematic beliefs that lower-income countries should adopt the models of rich countries (Rhoades et al., 2019). In this presentation I elaborated on mutuality as a framework at reducing these power differentials through equity, autonomy, solidarity, and participation (George Mwangi, 2017) and showed a joint research center I co-direct with UNIMINUTO, an institution in Colombia that models mutuality, the International Research Center for the Development of Education (CIIDE) (Mendoza et al., 2020). I concluded with these recommendations for building transformational partnerships: The importance of mutuality as a guiding framework. Leverage the ties and competencies of international faculty, who are well-positioned to become champions of transformational partnerships due to their likely interest in working with compatriots on issues impacting their nations of origin. Incentivize champions of transformational partnerships by adjusting promotion policies to explicitly account for the long-term outcomes of sustained international work. Properly fund transformational partnerships so that both partners equally participate in the associated planning and the funding. Provide institutional resources to seek external funding for internationalization including specialized staff. Once a faculty champion has demonstrated that there is capacity for a long-lasting partnership, the institution should incentivize other

champions to join the effort. This way, the partnership does not depend on one individual faculty member.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

International Partnerships, Mutuality, Equity in International Initiatives

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TRANSFORMATIONAL CREATIVITY FOR EDUCATION

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

This presentation examines transformational education from the context of creativity research (and theory). Three observations are offered. First is that there is a need for educational reform, a need which has been recognized for decades but has recently become much more critical and vital. This chapter reviews how transformation is related to creativity, summarizes recent work on transformational creativity, connects this to benevolent creativity (and contrasts it with malevolent creativity), and outlines a theory for education. This theory suggests that students need opportunities and support for executing transformations, discretion, and intentions. This should be considered because, right now, it is the current transformational imperative.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Creativity, Transformational Creativity, Transformational Imperative, Personal Creativity, Discretion, Intentionality

II

INNOVATION AND TECHNOLOGICAL PROGRESS

EFFECTIVENESS OF GAMIFIED INTERVENTIONS AT SCHOOL: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The changes that originated in the last years demand the abandonment of the most traditional approaches in teaching and it is necessary to incorporate innovative training proposals to increase the motivation level of students. The use of gamification as a methodology is undoubtedly one of the innovation techniques with encouraging results for the improvement of academic performance. The aim of this study is to analyze the interventions in formal education through gamification by performing a systematic review. Among the main results we observed that the most worked topics are those related to the scientific field and that there is an improvement in all interventions in variables such as academic performance and motivation. It is concluded that the use of this type of innovative methodologies is more effective in increasing the motivation and involvement of students in the teaching-learning processes. It seems necessary to implement a more systematized form of gamification in formal education.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Gamification, Innovation, Educational Intervention

ZOOMING FROM PALESTINE AND OHIO (USA): LESSONS FROM FACILITATING A VIRTUAL INTERCULTURAL DIALOGUE

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Objectives: By the end of this (recorded) session, attendees will be able to 1. identify core tenets of this particular program's model of intercultural dialogue, 2. reflect on challenges that the co-facilitators faced during their Spring 2023 program, specifically how some cultural and national differences contribute to facilitate and/or impede the communication process, and 3. consider the five successes that resulted from this program.

Methodology: As a recorded session due to the challenges associated with international time zones, it will be less interactive with participants, but nonetheless highly informative for attendees interested in virtual exchange and cross-cultural dialogue. Speakers will be video-recorded speaking over PPT slides that provide images and relevant information.

Content: The two presenters will first introduce themselves and explain how they became involved in Soliya's intercultural dialogue facilitation.

Next, an overview of the particular program's core values and its practices will be discussed. It will be made clear what it is and is not, what it does and does not aspire to do.

These dimensions will then be discussed in the context of the four-week session in Spring 2023 that the presenters co-facilitated. The five biggest challenges they

encountered will be shared, followed by the five most successful aspects of the experience.

Finally, each presenter will offer their perspectives on the importance of this type of programming for students in their region/ country, followed by a personal reflection on the meaningfulness of this programming to them personally. This includes a reflection on language, the fact that English is the language used in Soliya programming, and its implications within the program.

The session will end with an invitation to attendees to compare/ contrast similar projects in which they are involved and share particular strengths with other attendees. *NB: presenters are not authorized speakers on behalf of the non-profit organization that administers this programming, which is intentionally not named. This positionality grants presenters the ability to think critically and speak openly about the types of learning afforded to participants through this organization's programming and their experiences as co-facilitators.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Virtual Exchange, Intercultural Dialogue, Middle East/ North Africa (MENA), Arab World, "the West"

CONFI-ARTE: THE DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL CITIZENSHIP SKILLS THROUGH AND BY THE ARTS

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The world in which we live is undergoing profound social transformation. This change is marked by the advent of a technological revolution, which will put some pressure on the education system and the competences traditionally taken as scholastic. We understand, in this sense, that creativity, innovation and critical thinking will be the skills to be promoted in this century. To ensure a sustainable future, it is imperative that we think about education at a global level, fighting injustices and creating an idea of planetary union. Thus, it will be imperative for an educational reconfiguration centred on more humanitarian values, which value the human role in an era that is announced as predominantly automated. Faced with growing robotisation and the development of artificial intelligence, human beings will have to coexist with the efficiency and precision of automated means. And this coexistence necessarily implies an educational commitment to human competences, such as emotional intelligence, critical citizenship, interculturality and creativity. Education must strengthen the fight against violence, discrimination and injustice, aiming at sustainable human development and education for peace. This educational reconfiguration implies a transformation in the ways of doing and thinking, as well as of the learning spaces and times, where arts become motivating and performing agents of a social, emotional and intercultural learning. In this context, we present the project "Confi-Arte |+ Arte-Cidadania", outlining the guidelines, methodologies and results of the project. Based on the implementation of 34 workshops, held in 16 different locations in Portugal and abroad, 47 Art-Citizenship projects were developed, involving 1557 participants of all age groups (six months to 96 years). In this communication, we will focus on the potential of the arts to, in an

interdisciplinary way, enhance not only the development of scientific skills, but also intercultural skills, inclusion and promotion of creative and innovative practices.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Educational Reconfiguration, Critical Citizenship, Arts, Creativity, Innovation

SUBISU CABLENET: ENHANCING EDUCATIONAL OPPORTUNITIES FOR CHILDREN AND FAMILIES IN NEPAL THROUGH INNOVATIVE PROGRAMS

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

In today's rapidly evolving world, accessible and engaging educational content is essential for the holistic development of children and their families. Nepal, a country with diverse cultural, linguistic, and socioeconomic backgrounds, presents unique challenges and opportunities in the realm of education. This presentation aims to explore Subisu Cablenet's innovative educational programs designed specifically for children and families in Nepal, and how these initiatives are promoting lifelong learning, bridging the digital divide, and fostering a sense of community. The presentation will cover the following aspects: (1) Overview of Subisu Cablenet: A brief introduction to Subisu Cablenet, its core values, mission, and the impact of its services on the lives of the Nepalese population. (2) Educational Programs and Content: A detailed analysis of the various educational programs and content curated by Subisu Cablenet, such as interactive lessons, cultural programs, and educational games that cater to different age groups and learning needs. (3) Collaboration with Local Stakeholders: How Subisu Cablenet partners with schools, community organizations, and government agencies to design and implement educational programs that are tailored to the local context. (4) Inclusivity and Accessibility: The strategies employed by Subisu Cablenet to ensure that its educational programs are inclusive and accessible to children and families from diverse backgrounds, including those in rural and remote areas. (5) Measuring Impact: A presentation of qualitative and quantitative data showcasing the effectiveness

of Subisu Cablenet's educational programs in improving learning outcomes, boosting digital literacy, and fostering a sense of community among the Nepalese population. Join us for an insightful discussion on how Subisu Cablenet is revolutionizing education in Nepal and the potential for further growth and expansion in the future.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Subisu Cablenet, Educational Opportunities, Innovative Programs, Inclusivity, Accessibility, Nepal

LA LINGÜÍSTICA Y LA INTELIGENCIA ARTIFICIAL

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Las últimas décadas han sido marcadas por el avance y el desarrollo de las nuevas tecnologías, un hecho que tuvo en nuestra sociedad, en general, un significativo impacto. La pandemia Covid-19 aceleró todavía más el desarrollo de la inteligencia artificial (IA), lo que llevó a la aparición del Chat GPT o de programas como FromaGE (Frozen Retrieval Over Multimodal data for Autoregressive Generation), que suscitan muchas discusiones y fomentan controversias

Modelos lingüísticos como Chat GPT, programas como DeepL han revolucionado también el mundo de la lingüística. Lo que nos proponemos en este workshop es discutir cómo funcionan estos modelos y programas y hasta qué punto son capaces de reproducir una lengua. Ofreceremos las ventajas de tal modelos y programas, de las nuevas oportunidades. Pero a la vez nos centraremos en las desventajas; esto se hará partiendo de ejemplos concretos.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Tecnologías, Inteligencia Artificial (IA), Discusiones, Lengua, Impacto

ACCESS, EQUITY AND INCLUSIVENESS IN INDIAN HIGHER EDUCATION THROUGH ONLINE LEARNING: THE ROAD AHEAD

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The sudden outbreak of the Covid 19 Pandemic and the consequent lockdown in various countries have further intensified many of the existing challenges slowing down the developmental processes in the entire world. This situation has forced all types and levels of educational institutions to operate at a distance and put certain emergent online teaching practices into place to mitigate the crisis. But, the fact is that the sudden closure of the educational institutions has further widened the learning inequalities following which the vulnerable children and youths are hard hit. In a developing country like India too, such problems are being perceived and efforts are being made to immediately sustain the education systems. At the time of the crisis, when people are undergoing trauma, stress and psychological pressure, we should perhaps ask ourselves—if we should focus on teaching educational contents online or on teaching how to share, collaborate and support each other with the motto of providing ‘therapy, empathy and care.’ But, unfortunately, in a country like India with specific challenges to meet at the current situation, the ‘one size fits all’ concept may not work. Before putting certain steps into practice, we must take into consideration the many variables, including the target group of learners, their social and economic background, their age range, their access to technological infrastructure and so on.

Thus, the social issues, pedagogical challenge in terms of using technology for teaching learning process, access and affordability of technology, psychological mind set and hurdles towards acceptability of online and blended learning for teaching purpose etc. has laid the ways for more discussion on these issues for ensuring sustainable quality learning opportunities for all in the coming days.

Objectives: The objectives of the chapter are mainly:

- To discuss how the Indian higher educational system is able to provide the equal quality learning opportunities to all
- To find out the prospects and challenges of online and blended learning programmes for transacting academic contents in India during and post Pandemic situation.

Methodology: For this study, a literature review method will be adopted to discuss how the various online and blended learning approaches have been used for academic transaction and also what types of resilient approaches have been adopted for providing education during the COVID 19 pandemic and post pandemic situation. Besides, a critical analysis of the present state of higher education in India will be done on the basis of the social inquiry model and inclusive theory.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Indian Higher Education, Equity, Access, Inclusiveness, Online and Blended Learning Programmes

EL CAMBIO CLIMÁTICO EN EL MUNDO: DESARROLLO DE COMPETENCIAS GLOBALES A PARTIR DE UN PROYECTO TRANSMEDIA

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

La presente ponencia resume los resultados de un estudio piloto que evalúa el desarrollo de competencias globales a partir de un proyecto transmedia sobre el cambio climático realizado en colaboración con una escuela rural de la India. Los 20 estudiantes involucrados tienen un nivel elemental e intermedio de inglés y toman clases en línea todos los días durante 40 minutos. El análisis cuantitativo de las percepciones de los estudiantes reveló que sus expectativas acerca del proyecto fueron cumplidas en el 90% de los casos. Además, los participantes otorgaron las puntuaciones máximas en relación con sus percepciones del desarrollo de la creatividad (5,8 en una escala Likert de 7 puntos). También el resto de los aspectos estudiados obtuvieron puntuaciones satisfactorias: desarrollo de la competencia global (5,2), desarrollo de las competencias lingüísticas (5,7), y desarrollo de las competencias digitales (5,6). Las respuestas cualitativas a los enunciados propuestos complementaron las percepciones y opiniones expresadas por los estudiantes de manera numérica. En particular, los participantes valoraron la oportunidad de trabajar en equipo y de aprender sobre diferentes culturas.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Cambio Climático, Transmedia, Competencias Globales, Inglés, Proyecto Telecolaborativo

TRANSMEDIA SKILLS FOR A GLOBAL WORLD

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

As technology continues to make it easier to connect on a global scale, the need for transmedia literacy – and to produce practical teaching kits and tools – seems even more urgent than ever. This workshop intends to raise awareness and spark debate on the importance of developing transmedia literacy in the formal EFL secondary school classroom. The presenter will explore the main skills identified by the Transliteracy Project (Scolari, 2018) and introduce innovative transmedia sequences developed by EFL preservice teachers at a local teacher training college in Buenos Aires to help students boost their creativity and critical thinking skills while tackling global issues and engaging in new forms of content production, sharing and reporting. To conclude the session, participants will be invited to reflect on the possibility of implementing these or similar sequences in their own teaching-learning contexts. To this end, they will be presented with a series of tips and ideas to adapt the activities to the needs of their students in different contexts and formats.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Transmedia Sequences, Global Issues, EFL, Secondary School.

UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL: FOSTERING CREATIVITY AND INNOVATION IN TEACHERS FOR PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Innovation and creativity have become essential skills in today's fast-paced and dynamic educational landscape. As such, teachers must develop these skills to meet the demands of modern education and ensure that students receive the best possible education. This presentation explores how fostering creativity and innovation in teachers can promote professional growth and unlock their potential. Similarly, this presentation focuses on discussing the benefits of fostering creativity and innovation in teachers for their professional growth, sharing successful initiatives from Nepal's higher education that promote creativity and innovation in teachers, and providing practical strategies to help teachers unlock their potential to foster creativity and innovation in their teaching practices. The methodology includes a comprehensive literature review on creativity and innovation in teaching, supported by case studies that illustrate how successful initiatives promote creativity and innovation in teachers in higher education in Nepal.

The expected results of the presentation are to provide educators with practical and actionable strategies that can help them foster creativity and innovation in their teaching practices. This can lead to improved job satisfaction, increased motivation, and better student outcomes. Collaboration, professional development, and technology use are crucial strategies that the presentation emphasizes for fostering creativity and innovation in teaching. However, the factors that limit creativity and innovation in teachers, such as external restrictions, lack of resources, and rigid curriculum are also discussed.

The ultimate goal of this presentation is to provide educators with practical strategies to unlock their potential and foster creativity and innovation in their

teaching practices. As a result, we can create a dynamic and effective educational system that serves the needs of students and society in the 21st century.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Innovation, Creativity, Teacher Development, Higher Education, Teaching Strategies

TIC-TAC-TEP: PROPUESTA PEDAGÓGICA PARA LA FORMACIÓN DE FORMADORES Y SU VALIDACIÓN EN DIVERSOS CONTEXTOS DE EDUCACIÓN SUPERIOR

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Las Tecnologías de Aprendizaje y Conocimiento (TAC) tratan de orientar el uso de las Tecnologías de la Información y Comunicación (TIC) hacia el uso más formativo que informativo, tanto para el estudiante como para el docente, a fin de aprender más y mejor. Las dificultades encontradas durante la pandemia han rebelado carencias en los docentes, como las deficiencias en el uso de herramientas virtuales, la inexperiencia en el planteamiento de actividades con apoyo virtual, o el temor ante las innovaciones tecnológicas. A la vez, han puesto de manifiesto las brechas digitales, especialmente en ambientes desfavorecidos de áreas rurales. La tecnología es un medio que ayuda a acercar el conocimiento a las personas. Sin embargo, si queremos salir del uso de sistemas clásicos transmisivos que conducen al consumo de conocimiento, tenemos que buscar sistemas transformativos que faciliten la producción de conocimiento, no su mera reproducción. En este sentido, este artículo presenta una propuesta de curso online (TIC-TAC) para formaciones superiores, que tiene el propósito de transformar el proceso de enseñanza aprendizaje, fomentar el pensamiento crítico y creativo en los estudiantes e incorporar también nuevas Tecnologías de Empoderamiento y la Participación (TEP). Finalmente, se valida la propuesta en una Maestría desarrollada por una universidad europea y en actividades de formación superior dirigidas a docentes en América Latina y África.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

TIC, TAC, TEP, Formación de formadores, Formación on line

FOMENTO DEL EMPRENDIMIENTO EN JÓVENES RURALES MEDIANTE LA FORMACIÓN EN ALTERNANCIA: EL CASO DE LOS CEFFA DE GUATEMALA

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Como parte de un proyecto internacional de investigación que pretende estudiar los impactos de la formación en alternancia de los Centros Educativos Familiares de Formación en Alternancia (CEFFA), este trabajo pretende mostrar los resultados sobre el empleo rural juvenil en Guatemala, que es uno de los 15 países que participan en dicho proyecto. En concreto, se analizan los aspectos del sistema de alternancia que han contribuido a que los egresados hayan sido capaces de encontrar empleo o de generar autoempleo desarrollando emprendimientos. Para ello, se valoran los 239 cuestionarios electrónicos que se pasaron a egresados de una muestra intencionada del total de CEFFA existentes en el país entre agosto de 2020 y marzo de 2021. El análisis realizado concluye que los egresados valoran la formación en alternancia recibida porque les permitió generar capacidades técnicas, académicas y humanas que favorecen la empleabilidad y el emprendimiento. Así mismo, destaca la valoración positiva de la formación personalizada y el acompañamiento que recibieron por parte de sus profesores, tanto en la escuela, como en el entorno socio-profesional. Cerca del 20% manifiesta haber puesto en marcha su propia empresa, lo cual es relevante para la sostenibilidad del desarrollo de los territorios rurales desfavorecidos en los que habitualmente se asientan estos jóvenes.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Formación en alternancia, Centros Educativos Familiares de Formación en Alternancia (CEFFA), Emprendimiento, Jóvenes Rurales, Guatemala

ADDRESSING INEFFECTIVE TEACHING AND LEARNING PRACTICES DURING COVID-19 IN NEPAL: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW OF TPACK AND UDL INTERVENTIONS

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The objective of this systematic literature review is to explore the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on English language teaching (ELT) in Nepal and identify sustainable ELT practices for the 21st century, using the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework and Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles. The PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) model was used to conduct a systematic literature search using ProQuest and Google Scholar for relevant studies published between 2020 and 2023. The keywords "Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge", "TPACK", "Universal Design for Learning", "UDL", "English language", "ESL", "EFL", and "English teachers" were used to obtain relevant data. The search yielded 30 studies, which used a range of methodologies, including mixed, quantitative, and qualitative. The findings suggest that both TPACK and UDL have been successfully applied in various teacher professional development initiatives in different countries in the world, resulting in positive outcomes such as increased teacher confidence and competence in using technology, and improved student learning outcomes. However, Nepal is where the gap was found. The TPACK and UDL philosophies are seldom ever used in Nepal's educational systems. UDL is a completely new concept for Nepalese education sectors compared to TPAK. Since the use of technology in classrooms was not taking place aligning with the learning principles, the online classes during COVID-19 were ineffective affecting students' outcomes at all levels. Based on the analysis, the researcher proposes several recommendations for ELT practitioners and policymakers, including the development of TPACK and UDL training programs for teachers, the adoption of open educational resources, and the promotion of collaborative and student-centered approaches. This

comprehensive overview of the literature emphasizes how crucial it is for ELT during difficult times like the COVID-19 epidemic to incorporate TPACK and UDL principles and suggests as the must incorporate ingredients while teaching online. It offers insights into the pandemic's effects on ELT and identifies sustainable teaching and learning methods for the twenty-first century. The results of this study have implications for ELT practitioners, policymakers, and teacher educators who are involved in creating and putting into place efficient professional development initiatives for teachers. The suggestions made in this study can aid in promoting efficient methods of instruction and enhancing student learning results in difficult times.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

TPACK, UDL, ELT, ESL, COVID-19

FACTORS AFFECTING LEARNERS' USE OF EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY IN MATHEMATICS: A LOW SOCIO-ECONOMIC PERSPECTIVE

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Current statistics show that mathematics learners in South African schools are still very low as compared to learners in the general stream subjects. Given this, there is a need for appropriate use of educational technology tools in order to have a positive influence in the teaching and learning of mathematics. There is not much research in South African low socio-economic schools on factors affecting learners' use of educational technology in mathematics and the influence of their use of these tools on their persistence of mathematics beyond grade 12. This study investigated two rural schools in Limpopo province, South Africa, which included 76 learners between grades 10 to 12 who filled out a questionnaire. In addition, two focus group interviews were also conducted. Key findings are that learners' uses of educational technology are consistent with teachers' use of these tools in the two schools. Learners' persistence in studying mathematics is also influenced by using technologies in teaching and learning mathematics. In conclusion, it is highly recommended that the use of technological resources in teaching mathematics is encouraged in low socio-economic schools.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Educational Technology, Low Socio-economic Schools, Learners, Mathematics Learning

HIRED BY ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: DIGITAL INCLUSION PRACTICES FOR PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Artificial intelligence (AI) is developing at a rapid pace and entering all spheres of the economy. It supports the development of multiple industries, including healthcare, finance, education, robotics, entertainment, commerce, and many others. One of the activities closely related to all industries is human resource management - affiliated with the lives of people in companies. The role of HR specialists is wide-ranging and aimed at helping employees feel good about the companies they work for, providing them with space for creativity, and offering them empathy in a work environment. AI is also found in HR activities, including recruitment, thereby speeding up the hiring process and reducing the workload of specialists engaged in this activity. AI-powered systems that support hiring processes need to be convenient not only for HR professionals, but also for candidates. However, a special user group is often neglected - people with disabilities, who often face barriers when using software in a digital environment.

In this regard, the aim of this paper is to investigate the digital inclusion practices for people with disabilities by applying artificial intelligence-driven HRM systems. The paper proposes a heuristic evaluation method for software accessibility assessment based on international standards.

The objectives of this study are:

- research on best practices for digital inclusion of people with disabilities in the workplace;
- study of international standards for software accessibility;
- research on AI-powered systems applied to employment and specifically inclusive practices for people with disabilities.

The expected results are related to deriving an assessment of the accessibility of AI systems for employment.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Heuristic Evaluation, Digital Inclusion, Accessibility, Human Resource Management, Artificial Intelligence

CHATGPT – CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES IN DEVELOPING CRITICAL THINKING

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The grand emergence of ChatGPT - a conversational artificial intelligence (AI) system, in late 2022, is changing the public's awareness of what is possible with AI. It is a simple web interface that follows the imperative model, where the user inputs a request, and the chatbot returns the results in a multilingual context. This article addresses the application of AI in education, with a focus on ChatGPT. It is a literature review aiming to answer the following research question: What are the challenges and opportunities presented by ChatGPT in developing critical thinking? The main objectives defined are to analyse the potentialities of ChatGPT, its limitations' in an educational context, assess concerns raised by the use of ChatGPT and explore possible solutions. ChatGPT is recognised as an AI tool that generates grammatically correct, contextually appropriate, and coherent responses. In addition to conversation, ChatGPT has various capabilities such as content creation, translation, summarisation, exercise generation, lesson planning, and case study creation. In an educational context, ChatGPT can provide personalised learning experiences by offering feedback and corrections to students. However, the limitations of ChatGPT are also acknowledged. It can generate responses with reasoning errors, contradictions, or inaccurate information. ChatGPT does not adequately respond to questions related to problem-solving in science learning and does not generate truly innovative solutions to real problems. Therefore, ChatGPT requires students to further develop critical thinking skills, asking questions to obtain better results. It is also important to note that ChatGPT does not offer emotional support to students or any sort of empathy and, therefore, cannot replace teachers. In an attempt to assess the concerns raised and explore possible solutions, we conclude that concerns regarding errors and imprecision in ChatGPT's responses are not relevant, given the current development stage and considering future versions of GPT. Users can benefit from ChatGPT's context awareness to perform fact-checking tests and verify the accuracy and validity of the information.

Furthermore, it is pivotal for users to critically evaluate the information quality provided by AI, considering the context and relevance to their specific question. Regarding the risk of plagiarism, using self-assessment demonstrates critical reflection on the work produced is suggested. Moreover, a change in the education system is necessary to address the outsourcing of writing and the pursuit of easy searching mechanisms, while valuing skills such as innovation and critical thinking. Hence, it is essential to redesign the teaching-learning process and ethically integrate AI, while focusing on the skills mentioned above. Teachers and students should be empowered to use ChatGPT appropriately, aligning its use with the curriculum and learning objectives. Universities can explore alternatives such as ChatGPT support in simulations and the creation of AI-based learning tasks to solve real-world problems. Concerning assessment, a shift in traditional formats is expected, emphasising that neither creativity nor critical thinking can be replaced by AI. A continuous, authentic, and adaptable approach is recommended, employing diverse methods, including group projects, hands-on activities, and oral presentations. ChatGPT can assist in evaluating and reporting students' performance, providing personalised learning support. In response to the research question, it is possible to conclude that, given ChatGPT's inability to adequately answer to problem-solving issues and keeping in mind that interacting with ChatGPT requires students to engage in more critical thinking and develop better questioning skills, we believe that this weakness should be turned into an opportunity. This means defining objectives, activities, and assessment formats centred around the development of students' critical thinking, leveraging ChatGPT's writing potentialities and the fact that it does not require extensive technical or Information and Communication Technology (ICT) skills.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Artificial Intelligence, ChatGPT, Critical Thinking, Creativity, Real-World Problem Solving

DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR SOCIAL TRANSFORMATION: A CASE OF NEPAL

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Digital technologies are computer-mediated media that allow people to create, share, or exchange information, ideas, and experiences among themselves. It has interconnected the world into a village. Nepal is a culturally, linguistically, religiously, and ethnically diverse country where about 129 languages are spoken and 125 ethnic groups live. All people, wherever and whenever they are found of using digital technology for different purposes. In this diverse context, digital technology can be an agent to bring them into a single spare of development. Digital technology not only interconnects diversities but also challenges people's behaviours. It has brought a shift not only in the forms and contents of the message but also in the form of human efficiency and efficacy. In this rationale, I am trying to meet the following objectives:

- i. To find out the role of digital media in the cultural and linguistic identities of the people in Nepal
- ii. To investigate the influence of digital technology on human behaviour
- iii. To explore the role of digital technologies for social transformation

Methodology

An explanatory sequential mixed methods research design will be used to carry out this research. A set of Survey questionnaires from 100 convincingly selected informants from different cultural and ethnic groups in Nepal will be used for quantitative data, and for qualitative data, purposively selected 10 people form 10 different ethnic and linguistic backgrounds will be interviewed. Both sets of data will be analyzed first separately and integrated into the discussion.

Expected Results

Digital media may have severely affected their traditional cultural and linguistic identities and turned them into hybrids f.

The way of intercultural communication, interpersonal relationships, and their day-to-day behaviour may have changed and it may have challenged their originality.

Digital technologies may have changed the overall behaviour of Nepalese people.

Conclusion and Implications

Digital technology, which is the cry of the day to survive in the world, can be a boon in diverse contexts like Nepal if it is adequately used, otherwise, it may support linguistic and cultural loss. The findings of this study will be implacable for policymakers to make appropriate digital policies, and for curriculum developers to design the curricula appropriately to teach the students harmony between technologies and their backgrounds.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Social Transformation, Diversities, Digital Technology, Human Behaviour

INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS' GAINS IN MOBILITY PROGRAMMES: EVIDENCE WITHDRAWN FROM LITERATURE TO GROUP DISCUSSIONS

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Existing literature determines that it is crucial to support higher education students in their learning processes during mobility experiences abroad, so they can understand the learning outcomes they have gain. To this respect, this work, which is part of a European project called Erasmus Careers, explores which specific competences can be attributed to mobility abroad experiences. In so doing, we first carry out a systematic literature review on the topic, analyzing its evolution, theoretical and empirical approaches, etc. In a second stage, the results of this literature review are complemented and tested with the realization of focus groups carried out in four countries (Spain, Netherlands, Belgium, and Greece) with students and interns who have participated in an international mobility experience. Results from the systematic literature review has allowed us to propose a classification of the competences acquired during mobility experiences into four categories: academic gains, cultural gains, personal development gains and employability gains. Data revealed that the most predominant competences acquired or developed during mobility programmes are interactive learning and educational innovation (academic gains), intercultural sensitivity, cultural awareness, and language skills (cultural gains),

autonomy, independence and social skills (personal development gains), and finally work experience and networking (employability gains). In the case of students that went abroad to study, they have identified as the most important competences those related to personal development. On the other hand, for those who did internships abroad the employability gains were also very relevant. In line with these findings, this research has also identified a growing number of academic publications in the last years that focus on the competences related with self-awareness and personal development, two key important issues discussed by students in the focus groups.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Student Mobility, International Experience, Competences, Systematic Literature Review, Focus Groups

ESCENARIOS DE APRENDIZAJE. DISEÑO E INFLUENCIA EL ESPACIO ARQUITECTÓNICO UNIVERSITARIO EN EL PROCESO DE ENSEÑANZA-APRENDIZAJE MEDIANTE METODOLOGÍAS ACTIVAS

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

La educación es un tema de interés mundial, en todos sus ámbitos, incluyendo también los espacios donde se desarrolla. Se habla de un cambio en la educación, de nuevas metodologías activas, pero no se habla del espacio necesario para estas nuevas metodologías. Con el objetivo de poner en valor el diseño de los escenarios de aprendizaje y analizar su evolución histórica, así como su estado actual, se emplea la metodología lógico-empírica inductiva, que tomando como punto de partida elementos concretos y casos particulares sirve para extrapolar y obtener conocimientos generales. Bajo el paraguas del filósofo y pedagogo Dewey, siguiendo su máxima de aprender haciendo, analizaremos los escenarios de aprendizaje en el nivel universitario y los factores a tener en cuenta en su diseño, observaremos que existe la necesidad de un cambio en los escenarios de aprendizaje, pues estos no han cambiado en el último siglo, o no sustancialmente, y deben adaptarse a la metodología, actividades a desarrollar y sus usuarios. Además, observamos que hay una falta de referentes en la escala más pequeña, la del diseño interior y mobiliario. Dentro del cambio del aula escena al ambiente escenario, se refleja el paso de la formación dirigida del profesor experto hacia los estudiantes escuchantes al nuevo entorno, los nuevos dispositivos que lo conforman y las nuevas metodologías activas, que corresponden con la nueva sociedad y las nuevas necesidades. Deconstruimos el aula y sus principales elementos más característicos, no como simples objetos, sino como paradigmas que están en un proceso de cambio, mostrando la historia de estos y hacia donde vamos. Del pupitre mueble al prototipo móvil, engloba el paradigma pupitre y su evolución, dejando de ser el mueble tal y como lo conocemos, y dando paso a un dispositivo, que no necesariamente tiene que componerse de una mesa y una

silla, sino que será móvil y con formas diversas para ser más interactivo. De la pizarra y el estrado a la interface interactiva, estudia la historia de la pizarra y el estrado, para así poder analizar hacia donde se dirigen, siendo el estrado eliminado, y la pizarra sustituida por una interface que permita la colaboración y la interacción. De la puerta a la apertura, abarca la distribución de los elementos anteriores y el espacio donde se produce el aprendizaje, pasando del cubo del aula tradicional, espacio limitado al que se accede por una puerta, a un ambiente más distendido y abierto. Y finalmente se analizan tres casos de estudio que dan lugar a diversos paradigmas. Los escenarios de aprendizaje en la arquitectura nórdica, con el paradigma laboratorio y el lugar de encuentro; en la arquitectura mediterránea, con el paradigma reciclaje urbano y la reactivación de la ciudad; y en la arquitectura americana, con el paradigma garaje. En conclusión, no existe una fórmula exacta ni una solución única, es necesario aprender a usar el espacio y espacios que crezcan con nosotros, no sabemos las velocidades de transformación, estamos en un momento de expectación, hay un gran potencial, y queda mucho trabajo por hacer.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Escenarios de aprendizaje, Diseño de espacios educativos, Aprender Haciendo.

EXPLORING THE RELATIONSHIP OF UNDERREPRESENTED STUDENTS WITH MACHINE LEARNING AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

In 2019, the Council of Europe's Committee of Ministers adopted a recommendation on digital citizenship education in which a key focus was the application of Machine Learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) in educational contexts: AI, like any other tool, offers many opportunities but also carries with it many threats, which make it necessary to take human rights principles into account in the early design of its application. Educators must be aware of the strengths and weaknesses of AI in learning, so as to be empowered – not overpowered – by technology in their digital citizenship education practices, especially with minorities and/or underrepresented students, because it could increase the social and digital gap. This is not a simple review of the more than 40 years of academic research into the application of AI in education. Instead, it is a critical analysis of what is happening now, with AI tools developed by multi-million-dollar-funded commercial (various software or applications such as ChatGPT or Metaverse itself). I am focusing on the many complex challenges raised by the connections between AI and education, to provide a holistic view in order to ensure that future developments and practices are genuinely for the common good.

This paper seeks to advance knowledge of minority and underrepresented people in education. We must analyze whether errors, biases or overrepresentation occur with the use of these technologies; There is little research on why underrepresented minorities are less likely to specifically study Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence (ML/AI); I will find applications that can improve and reduce the learning difficulties of this type of student, taking into account that their application is growing and will be even greater in their professional future. While using AI to profile learners may have some benefits, for example to identify students at risk of dropping out, it can also be overly

intrusive, undermining a learner's rightful expectation of privacy. It may also have punitive effects on the family where attendance is tied to state welfare payments, such as in the Bolsa Familia programme in Brazil. Use of AI in this way raises many problems that need to be analyzed to prevent harmful effects. How is functioning the computational learner modeling employed by many AI tools that often uses profiles or stereotypes to predict academic performance and identify learners for early interventions?

A review has been started for its realization through the main bibliographic databases, documentation from public and private organizations, press releases and statistics. Inclusion and exclusion criteria were defined, as well as a set of variables to analyze the characteristics of the selected documentation. Based on this information, the descriptive work was carried out, deepening and reflecting on its current situation, the future and the importance of these tools in relation to the empowerment of minorities and/or underrepresented students, and fundamental rights.

I conclude with a discussion and needs analysis of open challenges, opportunities and implications of ML and AI in education. The USA has seen a proliferation of consulting firms offering predictive analytics to educational institutions for staff and student recruitment and retention, and AI is being used at the state level in India to address the perennial problem of retention rates beyond primary school, especially for girls. However, such uses of technology can be misleading – as measures of participation are not measures of quality or equity-. The computational learner modeling employed by many AI tools often uses profiles or stereotypes to predict academic performance and identify learners for early interventions. However, this approach can lead to discrimination in underrepresented populations. Inferring learner states from indicators or features such as gender, ethnic or cultural background and, even, socio-economic status, also introduces bias and further widens existing gaps. Finally, all too often, and almost always with the best of intentions, learners' learning and attendance data are being repurposed in ways for which the data was never designed – and usually without consent. In 2017, the UK's University of Buckingham began monitoring learners' social media posts as proxies for mental health risks: "An algorithm will scour their social media looking for key positive and negative words, which will then be used to determine their levels of happiness, engagement and fulfillment". The complex ethical issues that such a practice raises are self-evident. Cases such as those indicated will be explored to

analyze vulnerable aspects in the implementation of these technologies, if we want a more democratic and inclusive society.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Minorities, Education, Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence, Fundamental Rights

THE ROADMAP FOR DEVELOPING AN INTRODUCTORY ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE COURSE IN TEACHER EDUCATION

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

As artificial intelligence (AI) continues to shape the world, it is crucial to equip pre-service teachers with the skills and knowledge necessary to thrive in future classrooms that will become integrated with AI. Undergraduate teacher education programs should embrace new innovations and introduce their students to concepts such as AI to prepare them as the advanced technology spurs the evolution of new computing standards and curriculum for K-12 districts. The teacher education faculty at a historically black college/university (HBCU) in the Northeastern United States will share how they have developed a required “Introduction to AI for Elementary Education” course that prepares their students to teach the next generation. This presentation will provide a roadmap for creating an introductory AI class for elementary education undergraduate programs. The researchers have framed this work by utilizing foundational theories in AI that incorporate the 5 big ideas: Perception, Representation and Reasoning, Learning, Natural Interaction, and Societal Impact. The course work includes the usage of project-based methodologies and researchers will also share the process of using an alignment matrix to synthesize course development based on accreditation standards and district student learning standards. The researchers will share their method for the development of learning modules that focus on introducing basic AI concepts such as machine learning, natural language processing, and robotics in a cross-disciplinary way. Resources will be shared for simple programming platforms such as Scratch and Code.org as well as project-based assignments where students can employ critical thinking, benefits and consider the drawbacks of AI as they consider the

development of their own pedagogy and how they will integrate these innovations within their own classroom in helpful and meaningful ways. In addition, the researchers discuss the results of the development of this course and implications for the future which include challenges and opportunities for integrating AI into elementary education, including the need for teacher training, curriculum development, and appropriate classroom assessment methods.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Artificial Intelligence, Course Design, Elementary Education Program, Machine Learning

EVALUACIÓN DE LA EFICACIA DE LAS PLATAFORMAS EDUCATIVAS EN LA UNIVERSIDAD

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Con la evolución de la tecnología digital, la educación ha experimentado una transformación significativa en las últimas décadas. Esto ha dado lugar a la creación de varias plataformas educativas que han facilitado significativamente el proceso de aprendizaje, ya que ofrecen una amplia gama de recursos y herramientas que complementan y enriquecen la experiencia educativa. Se parte de la premisa de que las plataformas educativas en la educación superior pueden ayudar a mejorar la calidad de la enseñanza y tienen un impacto positivo en la tasa de éxito de los estudiantes.

Este estudio tiene como objetivos describir las opiniones del alumnado sobre su experiencia con las plataformas educativas de la universidad; así como su grado de satisfacción con las mismas y analizar la relación entre las herramientas seleccionadas por el profesorado en la plataforma con las metodologías y técnicas de evaluación más utilizadas.

Para alcanzar estos objetivos, en primer lugar, se realizará una exhaustiva revisión de las distintas plataformas educativas disponibles en el ámbito de la educación superior. En segundo lugar, se llevará a cabo un estudio de caso en una universidad en la que la utilización de una plataforma educativa es voluntaria. En dicho estudio, se realizará una revisión longitudinal de cómo se ha utilizado la plataforma en un periodo de tiempo concreto. Se examinarán detalladamente las herramientas proporcionadas por la plataforma y se clasificarán previamente en categorías de "activas" y "pasivas", según su capacidad para favorecer el aprendizaje activo de los estudiantes. La opinión de los usuarios, es decir, de los estudiantes y docentes que utilizan esta plataforma, se llevará a cabo utilizando una encuesta. Según los datos obtenidos, los usuarios de las plataformas educativas tienen una opinión positiva de la misma. Además, se ha constatado que las herramientas pasivas más utilizadas de la plataforma son documentos y enlaces (66%), anuncios (12%), y calificaciones (11%) y herramientas activas: ejercicios (48%), grupos (24%) y cuestionarios (17%). Las

metodologías más utilizadas son la lección magistral (91%), resolución de problemas (40%) y trabajo tutelado (38%). Las técnicas de evaluación más empleadas son resolución de problemas y/o ejercicios (38%), examen de preguntas de desarrollo (35%) y examen de preguntas objetivas (34%). Esto indica que la plataforma se adapta a las necesidades y prácticas pedagógicas de los docentes, lo cual promueve la alineación entre los recursos tecnológicos y los objetivos educativos. En opinión del alumnado la actividad que más promueve el profesorado es la consulta de material de la asignatura a través de la herramienta documentos y enlaces (38%), subir archivo de tareas a través de la herramienta ejercicios (25%), la publicación de notas a través de la herramienta calificaciones (22%), la realización de exámenes parciales a través de la herramienta cuestionarios y/o ejercicios (9%), las autoevaluaciones a través de la herramienta cuestionarios y/o Ejercicios (4%), y foros (2%), otras (1%).

Al realizar el análisis de sentimientos sobre la opinión de los usuarios de la plataforma, la coincidencia entre el profesorado y el alumnado es alta tanto en las en las valoraciones positivas como en las negativas.

Se puede concluir que el diseño curricular y las plataformas educativas pueden ayudar a mejorar el futuro de la educación universitaria, al proporcionar una forma eficaz y segura para los estudiantes de interactuar con el profesorado. De hecho, estas herramientas permiten al profesorado diseñar un currículo flexible y adaptado a las necesidades de los estudiantes, fomentar la adopción generalizada de plataformas educativas e integrarlas de manera efectiva en el diseño curricular es clave para aprovechar al máximo sus beneficios. Para lograrlo, sería necesario establecer un sistema de información que permita monitorizar y evaluar la efectividad de las plataformas educativas en relación con las metodologías y técnicas de evaluación utilizadas, así como identificar áreas de mejora y tomar decisiones fundamentadas. El sistema debe ser capaz de recopilar datos relevantes de manera automatizada y generar informes que sean accesibles para los docentes (para que pueda tomar decisiones durante y después de que se imparta la asignatura) y los responsables de la institución. Esto podría incluir la recopilación de datos sobre la frecuencia de uso, las actividades realizadas, el tiempo dedicado, las calificaciones y otros indicadores relevantes.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Plataformas Docentes, Instrumentos de Evaluación, Metodologías Docentes, Aprendizaje Activo

LA PARENTALIDAD POSITIVA EN LOS CENTROS EDUCATIVOS GALLEGOS

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

El trabajo que se presenta se focaliza en las escuelas de padres y madres y el abordaje de la Parentalidad Positiva. Se considera relevante el vínculo de los programas de parentalidad positiva con las escuelas de madres y padres como sistema de democratización de la formación parental. Todas las familias tienen derecho a la educación de sus hijos y, por tanto, cuentan con al menos un centro educativo en el que apoyarse ante posibles dificultades. En este estudio se analizan datos relativos al funcionamiento de las escuelas de madres y padres de Galicia. Se abordan temas relacionados con las temáticas tratadas, la figura del dinamizador/a, la participación y asistencia, la satisfacción personal de los progenitores asistentes, en antes y el después de la pandemia en el tipo de formación parental y sus necesidades. La muestra la componen los 1.325 centros escolares de Galicia que ofrecen escolaridad obligatoria, de titularidad tanto pública y privada concertada. Para la recogida de los datos se ha efectuado, en primer lugar llamadas telefónicas a todos los centros para poder establecer el total de centros de Galicia que contaban con escuela de madres y padres, a la vez que dar a conocer el objetivo del estudio y motivarlos a participar en el mismo. Posteriormente, a los centros que manifestaron tener alguna iniciativa de formación a familias, se les envió un cuestionario ad hoc. El análisis cuantitativo y cualitativo de los resultados permitió establecer los aspectos positivos de las iniciativas analizadas, a la vez que justificar la necesidad de formar a los profesionales implicados en parámetros positivos de parentalidad.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Parentalidad Positiva, Programas de Educación de padres, Familia, Escuela.

THE NEXUS BETWEEN RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT, HIGHER EDUCATION AND ECONOMIC GROWTH: A MAURITIAN PERSPECTIVE

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Economic growth remains an integral part of the development of many countries. In recent decades, this subject has captivated the unwavering attention of various stakeholders - from economists to policymakers - across the globe. The focus has been amplified worldwide following the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, which has triggered an unprecedented situation fraught with uncertainties. Thus, understanding the drivers of economic growth is of utmost importance for the delineating of suitable policies to foster sustainable development and ensure a resilient future. In the literature, the neoclassical growth model has shown that there are several factors (capital stock, labour, technological progress, investment, population growth, trade openness, and inflation rate among others) explaining the fluctuations in the economic growth of a country. On the other hand, the endogenous growth model postulates that human capital, investment in research and development (R&D), innovation, infrastructure and government policies play a role in promoting a country's economic growth. Despite the initiatives of the Mauritian government to position the country as a regional knowledge hub and a centre for higher learning, little attention has been given to the potential impacts of higher education (HE) and research and development (R&D) on the country's economic growth. In light of this, this study aims to include higher education and research and development (R&D) as regressors in the growth equation. This will be investigated using annual data spanning from 1990-2019 and a dynamic time series approach. The dynamic framework will also provide insights into both their short-term and long-term impacts. Furthermore, this study will also examine the interactive effects of R&D, higher education and capital. Before estimating the model, the stationary properties of the variables

will be assessed using appropriate unit root tests and the presence of co-integrating relationships will also be checked. The outcomes of this analysis will help to quantify the contributions of higher education and R&D expenditures in relation to other economic growth drivers. These findings have significant implications for policymakers and the government in terms of the allocation of funds for research and development. They will also provide an assessment of the effectiveness and productivity of investments made in higher education.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

R&D, Higher Education, Economic Growth, Mauritius

DIGITAL BILL: AN APPROACH TO MINIMIZE ILLICIT ACTIVITIES AND OTHER DRAWBACKS OF CRYPTO CURRENCY

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The objective of this paper is to propose a solution for addressing concerns about money laundering, illicit activities, and lack of acceptance in the mass adoption of cryptocurrency, through the development of a secure and reliable digital currency called Digital Bill (DB). The world of cryptocurrency has been plagued with concerns about money laundering, illicit activities, and lack of acceptance in the mass adoption of cryptocurrency. These issues have caused many potential investors to be hesitant in embracing blockchain technology. The proposed solution is a digital representation of a bill of exchange called "Digital Bill (DB)". The Digital Bill (DB) currency is designed to offer several features that address these concerns, including cyber security protection, inflation resistance, no mining requirements, private key regeneration, DEX hacking prevention, depository insurance, trust guarantees, and instant currency value adjustment. The features of DB present a foundation for an ecosystem based on the "Digital Bill (DB)" network that can serve as a secure and safer cryptocurrency. In general, a wallet contains the total amount of cryptocurrency a user possesses. However, in the proposed DB system, the client's wallet will hold the same total amount of DB, but denominated in divisible numbered units. This means that when the client executes a transaction, they will use specific numbered DB units, rather than the total amount. Furthermore, the client's wallet may hold a bundle of numbered DBs. The wallet is designed in a way that shows the total amount of DB, but automatically delivers the equivalent amount of numbered DB units at the time of spending. This is similar to physical wallets where we don't have to check the issuing number of banknotes while spending. It simplifies the transaction process and enhances the user experience. Besides, to ensure the security of the Digital Bill (DB) network, a volunteer committee will be established to manage and regulate the DB network. In the event of a cyber-attack or ransomware incident affecting a node of Digital Bill (DB), the node owner may request the volunteer committee to cancel or ban the specific numbered DBs associated with their node, and request the issuance of new DBs in their name.

The volunteer committee will carefully analyze the event and verify the latest transaction records on the blockchain before issuing the new DBs. This measure ensures that the integrity and security of the DB system are maintained at all times. Similarly, in the event of a cyber-attack on a crypto exchange or decentralized exchange (DEX), they can request the committee, who are the sole operators of the DB network, to reissue the DBs. After analyzing the previous data, the committee can then determine the appropriate amount to reissue. This process ensures that the exchange or DEX can continue to operate and that users do not suffer any losses due to the cyber-attack. In a blockchain, each block contains a set of data, along with metadata like timestamp, hash value, and previous block hash. In our proposed "Digital Bill (DB)" system, we suggest that each block should contain additional built-in features to enhance security and reliability. This includes approved CSS codes of well-known, reliable browsers, as well as restrictions on vulnerable browsers that are commonly used to access dark nets and VPNs. Moreover, in order to track illicit activities, important stampings like IP addresses, location, IMEI no., MAC addresses, etc. are needed to be included in the block. These stampings will help in identifying and tracking any malicious activities related to the transaction recorded in the block. The inclusion of these stampings can act as a deterrent to illicit activities, as it can help authorities to trace and identify the perpetrators behind any wrongdoing. Additionally, these stampings can also help in building a more transparent and accountable system, which can be crucial in building trust among users. In conclusion, the proposed Digital Bill (DB) system presents an innovative approach to addressing concerns about money laundering, illicit activities, and lack of acceptance in the mass adoption of cryptocurrency. By offering a range of advanced features, including cyber security protection, inflation resistance, private key regeneration, DEX hacking prevention, depository insurance, trust guarantees, and more, the DB system can provide users with a secure, reliable, and convenient alternative to traditional currency. While more development is needed to fully realize the potential of the DB system, the proposed approach offers a promising glimpse into the future of a safer and more secure cryptocurrency. It is hoped that the DB system will help to increase public trust in cryptocurrency and encourage greater adoption and implementation of blockchain technology in the years to come.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Block Chain, Crypto Currency, Minimizing Money Laundering Risks

ENGINEERING VIRTUAL LABS FOR E-LEARNING

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Because they revolutionize the way knowledge is taught and acquired in higher education, virtual laboratories are essential to the European Higher Education Area (EHEA). With the help of these technologies, students can enhance their learning experience by having unlimited access to experiments and practices, regardless of their location or schedule. This encourages individualized, independent, and active learning—all of which are in perfect harmony with the EHEA's pedagogical tenets. Virtual laboratories also help educational institutions save money and maximize resources without sacrificing instruction quality, which boosts the effectiveness and globalization of higher education in Europe.

This case study details the creation of virtual labs for remote instruction in industrial automation for the University of A Coruña's Master of Industrial Engineering program. The project engaged international students in creating a virtual package sorting conveyor based on weight using Factory I/O and Unity

Pro-XLS software. Throughout the experience, students were empowered to conduct research, theory and practice were integrated, knowledge was applied, and both hard and soft skills were developed. Furthermore, in educational environments, this didactic suggestion is in line with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Results from a comparison of student performance in traditional and virtual laboratories were quite positive.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Industrial Facilities, Engineering, Virtual Labs, E-learning, Students

III

SUSTAINABLE AND INCLUSIVE APPROACHES

VIRTUAL VISUAL ART INTEGRATION AND BIOLOGY: MORE FAVOR OR CHALLENGES FOR EMERGENT BI/MULTILINGUAL HIGH SCHOOLERS

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

As educators, we are becoming increasingly aware that delivering effective education will likely change after the coronavirus pandemic. As a result, we have an opportunity to frame teaching differently and bring innovation to the forefront. In doing so, educators explored online tools and creative ways to connect with students and found new ways to teach. Using an exploratory case study methodology and working within a theoretical symbolic interactionism (SI) framework, I investigated how virtual teaching visual arts integration and biology are more favorable or challenging for emergent bi/multilingual high schoolers. The lesson titled Using Depiction to Illustrate the Interdependent Functions of a Plant Cell was implemented. I implemented a series of visual arts integration activities with ten ninth-grade emergent bi/multilingual students at a mid-sized high school in the United States southeastern region. Research activities took place, via Zoom, in a communication skills class. The findings reveal that learning new content mediums and skills during visual arts integration activities enhances students' learning process. Moreover, emergent bi/multilingual students can benefit from face-to-face classes because they receive more practice speaking and benefit from their teacher's advice on their tasks. Nevertheless, more flexible class times and delivery methods may help students meet the many challenges created by the need to help provide for their families.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Emergent bi/Multilingual Learners, Communication Skills Class, STEAM, Symbolic Interactionism, Virtual Visual Arts Integration.

LIBRO-OBJETO Y DESARROLLO SOSTENIBLE: PERCEPCIONES DEL PROFESORADO EN FORMACIÓN

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Ante el propósito de encontrar soluciones a la crisis ambiental y humanitaria en la que estamos inmersos, surge la idea de desarrollo sostenible, que se sostiene en la idea de que el desarrollo del ser humano ha de ser compatible con los procesos ecológicos. El sistema educativo no puede ser ajeno a estas cuestiones, por lo que ha de promover un pensamiento crítico, ético y creativo, que propicie acciones capaces de mejorar el mundo. En este sentido, los elementos lingüísticos, visuales y materiales de los libros-objeto, así como su organización dinámica, ofrecen un marco adecuado para interpretar y actuar ante la actual crisis ambiental. Por ello, este trabajo tiene como objetivo principal conocer las percepciones del profesorado en formación en relación a las potencialidades de los libros-objeto para abordar las problemáticas ambientales. La inexistencia de instrumentos específicos ha motivado la realización de una escala ad hoc para evaluar dichos aspectos sobre una muestra compuesta por 88 estudiantes del grado de Educación Infantil. Los resultados, que fueron analizados mediante un método no experimental descriptivo, indican que el profesorado en formación no es un gran conocedor de las lecturas de carácter ecoalfabetizador bajo el formato del libro-objeto. Asimismo, no es totalmente consciente de las potencialidades que poseen los diferentes elementos configuradores de los libros-objeto (textos, ilustración, materialidad, dispositivos móviles...) en la creación de sentido y en el estímulo de una reflexión-acción necesaria para contribuir a la armonización entre el ser humano y el medio natural. Estamos, pues, ante un estudio exploratorio pertinente que supone un punto de partida para que el profesorado pueda incorporar a sus aulas prácticas lectoras, reflexivas, dialógicas y propositivas de carácter transformador, que también respondan a las demandas de la Agenda 2030 para el desarrollo sostenible.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Desarrollo Sostenible, Libro-objeto, Formación de docentes, Innovación

AFFIRMATIVE ACTION IN HIGHER EDUCATION ADMISSION

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The affirmative action policy in admission to higher education has been widely discussed before and after its endorsement by the court in 1978. Many states and universities are in a dilemma to advocate for considering affirmative action in admission. The objective of this paper is to uncover possible novel alternatives to affirmative action in admission. The study is primarily based on a systematic review of the literature and researchers' own experiences of affirmative action. After analysis of the pieces of literature, I have found that affirmative action was primarily initiated by several movements and the court decision in the US. Referencing the court decisions in the recent past, existing admission policies and practices in different states and universities, public opinions, and so on, it is purported that future policy initiatives require anticipating the notion of affirmative action on the basis of a need-based, race-neutrality, socioeconomic foundation, and academic performance of students. Therefore, affirmative action in admission needs to be amended with alternative policies and practices.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Affirmative action, Higher education, Race-neutral

CYBERPERFORMANCE AND TEACHING METHODOLOGIES WITHIN THE ARTS

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The two years of pandemic isolation increased the use of online platforms in the performing arts and related teaching at higher education level. However, this rapid change also presented challenges such as the need to guarantee the quality of online connection for all involved, accessibility to digital resources and the adaptation of methods to virtual environments. In this context, the research project CyPeT, hosted by the Center for Research in Arts and Communication (CIAC) – Algarve University, in partnership with the Open University and University of Maia, funded by the Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT), in Portugal, aims for developing a new pedagogical model for the inclusion of cyberperformance in higher education curricula.

In our proposal we will present investigation that respond to the following questions: How can we learn from the practice of cyberperformance, its practitioners and as part of the audience that informs its teaching? And how can the methods of teaching cyberperformance can be of use to inform new methodologies in the teaching of digital media-based practices?

We will look into examples that combine exploratory practices with teaching methods. These methods are sustained on online practices, such as cyberperformance, as holding potential to inform new ways of teaching and learning. Technology as tools for performing and integration of students and teachers as collaborators are some of the analysis parameters. In the Portuguese scenario, the University of Aveiro developed the "Performing Science" project, which consists of a digital performance laboratory that uses advanced technologies to create new ways of teaching and learning science. The project

"Teaching Art in Times of Crisis", developed by the University of Lisbon, also used cyberperformance to teach art to higher education students in pandemic times. Resulting from a collaboration between the composer and professor Jônatas Manzolli together with the professor Daniela Gattii, both from the Brazilian University UNICAMP, in collaboration with the University of Coimbra, developed, in a multidisciplinary broader context, "Jardim das Cartas". This project brought together students from dance and music to interpret excerpts of a musical score by using an interactive sound application. The performers created an installation that involves sound and movement. A similar growing interest is observed internationally such as "Cyber Performance Workshops" – a series of initiatives that offer workshops and courses on cyberperformance, including the exploration of existing communication technologies to create innovative and experimental performances is one of the examples for our analysis.

As a result, the research intends to present a contribution to a response to a real need to update teaching methodologies, in view of the use of digital technologies in the classroom. In this scenario, cyberperformance is, therefore, a possibility for potential inclusiveness in future education.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Cyberperformance, Performing Arts, Methodologies, Higher Education

ESTUDIO DE LA MOTIVACIÓN DOCENTE EN INFANTIL, PRIMARIA Y SECUNDARIA: UN ANÁLISIS POR CONSTRUCTOS MOTIVACIONALES

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

La motivación docente es posiblemente el factor más importante implicado en el rendimiento del discente, de ahí la importancia de medir esta variable de forma rigurosa y fiable, de tal manera que en función de los resultados se puedan aplicar programas adecuados para el aumento de la motivación en el colectivo de profesores. Basándonos en la teoría de la autodeterminación, el objetivo de este estudio es conocer qué tipo de motivación vivencian los maestros de los colegios de la ciudad Vigo, en las distintas tareas que ocupan su día a día en las aulas. La muestra está compuesta por 369 profesores de infantil, primaria y secundaria, los cuales trabajan en colegios concertados y públicos. Este estudio se enmarca dentro del enfoque interpretativo y de un diseño cuasi-experimental, dado que la finalidad última es conocer e interpretar qué tipo de motivación manifiesta el profesorado. Para el tratamiento de este trabajo se ha seleccionado una metodología de carácter cuantitativo utilizando una escala tipo Likert como instrumento de medida, concretamente The Work Task Motivation Scale for Teachers, traducida y validada al español. Esta escala mide la motivación del docente centrándose en cinco constructos motivacionales y seis tareas propias del maestro. Los resultados principales obtenidos muestran que la motivación docente varía significativamente según las tareas desempeñadas, siendo las tareas administrativas y de gestión del aula las que repercuten de forma importante en la disminución de la misma.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Motivación Docente, Teoría de la autodeterminación, WTSMT, Constructos Motivacionales

COMPETENCIAS BLANDAS Y AUTOCONCEPTO: EXPLORACIÓN DE SU VÍNCULO CON FACTORES EDUCATIVOS EN ESTUDIANTES DE ORQUESTAS UNIVERSITARIA

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Las orquestas universitarias, arraigadas en el seno de las instituciones académicas, promueven la práctica musical entre estudiantes de nivel superior, desempeñando un papel educativo esencial para la formación integral del alumnado. El propósito de esta investigación es examinar el nivel de autoconcepto y habilidades blandas en intérpretes de orquestas universitarias, así como su relación con variables educativas. Se cuenta con una muestra de 201 músicos provenientes de diversas orquestas universitarias en países europeos. Entre los hallazgos más destacados, se observa que el autoconcepto tiende a ser bajo y no presenta una asociación clara con las variables formativas. En cambio, se evidencia un sólido dominio de diversas competencias blandas que sí se vinculan estrechamente con los aspectos educativos. Como conclusión, se destaca que la participación en orquestas universitarias durante el periodo académico en instituciones de educación superior constituye un valioso complemento formativo para el crecimiento integral de los estudiantes universitarios.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Soft Skills, Autoestima, Orquestas Universitarias, Educación Superior, Educación Musical

LA DIVERSIDAD CULTURAL Y MUSICAL EN EL ALUMNADO DE EDUCACIÓN INFANTIL: UN ESTUDIO DE CASO GRUPAL

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

El eje central de la competencia en expresiones culturales y musicales desempeña un papel crucial al permitir que los estudiantes forjen una identidad única en su entorno. El propósito de esta investigación radica en evaluar el nivel de competencia en expresiones culturales a nivel local, global y musical entre los alumnos de educación infantil. Entre los resultados más destacados se evidencia que, a pesar de la atención curricular dedicada a la cultura local, los estudiantes muestran una competencia deficiente en este ámbito, mientras que demuestran mayor competencia en cultura musical. En última instancia, se subraya la importancia de la formación docente para incorporar de manera efectiva los descriptores operativos de la competencia cultural y artística en los procesos de enseñanza-aprendizaje, con el objetivo de elevar el nivel de competencia cultural y musical del alumnado.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Competencia cultural y artística, Educación musical, Educación infantil, Música, Cultura global

COMUNICANDO E INTERPRETANDO EL PATRIMONIO CULTURAL. CONOCER Y DISFRUTAR

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

El objetivo es demostrar el impacto positivo que las visitas guiadas tienen para una comunidad. La metodología consistió en realizar más de siete mil visitas guiadas a tres lugares patrimoniales distintos: a) una catedral, Ourense b) un municipio, Boborás c) una exposición internacional, In Tempore Sueborum. Todo ello ha sido acompañado de un plan de comunicación que le dio proyección tanto nacional como internacional. En los tres casos se han realizado visitas bien documentadas con una duración superior a la hora, en todos los casos no más de tres horas. El resultado ha sido satisfactorio por la repercusión y la reacción del público participante.

En la catedral hubo 20 visitas en diez años (2004-2014) con una duración máxima de tres horas. Pasaron por esta actividad todos los sectores sociales de la ciudad. En Boborás se hicieron cerca de mil visitas semanales, durante seis meses (junio-noviembre 2017) a cada uno de los 13 destinos diferentes que se establecieron: románico, pazos, naturaleza, minas, castillo, termas...Y la exposición internacional estuvo abierta seis meses (diciembre 2017-mayo 2018). La comunicación ha funcionado en los tres casos, sumando cerca de diez mil visitas en total. Hubo repercusión mediática, especialmente en la exposición internacional sobre el mundo suevo, que llegó a varios millones de personas en todo el mundo, como se mostrará en la ponencia. Los resultados de estas tres experiencias han revolucionado el panorama cultural de Ourense en este aspecto. Fue un reto propio, como comunicador, guía turístico, intérprete del patrimonio y doctor en Historia. Los datos finales demostrarán que, en la educación para toda la vida no reglada, podemos sostener que, si se hace con rigor, esta acción de visitas patrimoniales puede repercutir en el desarrollo de una comunidad, así como aportar orgullo a la misma.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Patrimonio, Interpretación del patrimonio, Visitas guiadas, Comunicación

PROFESIONALIZACIÓN DOCENTE Y ALTERNANCIA EN LAS ESCUELAS FAMILIARES AGRARIAS DE GALICIA

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Los Centros Educativos Familiares de Formación en Alternancia (CEFFA) vinculados a la AIMFR (Asociación Internacional de los Movimientos Familiares de Formación Rural), promueven acciones educativas y de desarrollo a través de asociaciones locales que implementan el sistema pedagógico de alternancia. Dicho sistema consiste, desde el punto de vista de la formación, en alternar períodos escolares en el entorno socioprofesional (empresa) y en el aula (escuela), de manera similar a como lo hace el sistema dual, tan de moda actualmente en España. En Galicia hay tres escuelas tipo CEFFA denominadas Escuelas Familiares Agrarias (EFA), en las provincias de Pontevedra y A Coruña, que están integradas en una Federación Regional y en una Unión Nacional española, y que están celebrando su cincuentenario. Este artículo está focalizado en el estudio de un factor clave del sistema de alternancia y de cualquier sistema educativo: el profesor. Su perfil multifuncional es complejo porque, más allá de la docencia, tiene un rol de liderazgo territorial y de acompañamiento de familias y otros actores locales. Por su posición nuclear dentro del sistema, tiene un impacto relevante en la estabilidad del proyecto asociativo. Su profesionalización es complicada por la ausencia de definición de sus competencias profesionales y de un estatuto propio que reconozca esa posición nuclear y ese perfil multifuncional. Este trabajo presenta, por un lado, los resultados cualitativos de entrevistas abiertas realizadas a los docentes de las EFA de Galicia entre abril y mayo de 2023 en lo que se refiere a sus necesidades y expectativas de formación

y profesionalización. Por otro, los resultados preliminares de las percepciones de esos profesores sobre los impactos de las EFA de Galicia, como respuesta a cuestionarios cerrados realizados en 2022. Estos resultados, se enmarcan en un proyecto de investigación internacional que involucra 5 universidades y 15 países donde hay CEFFA pertenecientes a la AIMFR. Como consecuencia de ambos abordajes, se señalan algunas pistas para una contribución a la consolidación de una formación específica que responda a esas necesidades y expectativas personales y profesionales.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Formación en alternancia, Formación de formadores, Profesionalización docente, Escuelas Familiares Agrarias (EFA), Galicia

IMPACTS OF FORMATION ON TERRITORIAL DEVELOPMENT: THE CASE OF FAMILY AGRICULTURAL SCHOOLS IN GALICIA

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Galicia's territorial cohesion and balance require strengthening the agroforestry sector to a greater extent than in other areas of Spain or Europe due to the high socioeconomic influence of the primary sector in the region. However, the lack of opportunities for people living in rural areas, the negative demographic evolution, and irrelevant educational programs, has generated several problems related to poorly diversified production models that do not generate employment -particularly youth employment- and are often environmentally unfriendly. This paper presents the experience of the Family Agricultural Schools (in Spanish, Escuelas Familiares Agrarias, EFA) in Galicia. The EFAs, supported by family-led local associations, use the alternating/dual pedagogical system where training periods in the socio-professional environment and in the classroom are combined. Thanks to this formation, which includes social, environmental, and territorial context into the curriculum, the schools contribute to the development of rural areas through the permanence of trained young people capable of implementing projects that generate employment or self-employment. After a brief conceptual description of alternating cycle education and its situation worldwide, some results are shown in Galicia of one international research that aims to study the impact generated by alternation/dual training in 15 countries on four continents. Finally, three case studies of graduates in Galicia are presented, one per school, which show how

relevant training oriented to employment helps improve people's quality of life and provides sustainability to the territories.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Rural Education, Territorial Development, Alternating Cycle Education, Escuelas Familiares Agrarias (EFA), Galicia

UNA MIRADA MULTIVARIANTE A LA GESTIÓN UNIVERSITARIA EN MATERIA DE SOSTENIBILIDAD

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

El papel de las Instituciones de Educación Superior en el desarrollo sostenible ha sido ampliamente reconocido por la literatura científica. Las misiones de la docencia y la investigación, así como las operaciones en el campus, convierte a las universidades en líderes proactivos en la mejora y la protección del medio ambiente. Por ello, la evaluación de su sostenibilidad está siendo objeto de gran atención y UI GreenMetric ha sido reconocido a nivel mundial como una de las principales herramientas para ayudar a las instituciones a alcanzar los cambios deseados en el desarrollo sostenible. Su impacto se muestra en el creciente número de participantes (1050 en la edición del 2022), que cubren diferentes regiones del mundo con condiciones económicas y sociales completamente distintas. El objetivo de esta investigación es analizar el comportamiento de las 127 universidades mejor clasificadas en UI-GreenMetric en las regiones de América del Norte, América del Sur, Europa, Asia, África y Oceanía, para estudiar sus características distintivas, así como las diferentes dimensiones del ranking y sus correlaciones. El análisis se realizó a través de la técnica multivariante HJ-Biplot (Galindo, 1986), en la que pueden superponerse universidades e indicadores en un mismo sistema de referencia con la máxima calidad de representación. Se trata de una potente herramienta de visualización que permite interpretar de manera intuitiva la relación entre variables (indicadores del ranking), entre individuos (universidades) o entre variables e individuos a través de la distancia entre dos puntos, la longitud de un vector, el ángulo entre dos vectores y la forma de ordenar puntos sobre un vector. Los resultados muestran que las universidades tienen diferentes comportamientos en función de la región en la que se encuentren insertas. Las instituciones europeas y asiáticas son las más activas en materia de sostenibilidad, mientras que las

africanas muestran valores más alejados. También se observan agrupaciones según su aproximación a una u otra dimensión. En cuanto a las variables del ranking, todas correlacionan de forma directa, excepto energía y cambio climático y entorno e infraestructura que no guardan relación entre ellas, siendo este último indicador el que muestra una mayor variabilidad. Esta covariación directa indica que las instituciones líderes están incorporando el desarrollo sostenible en todas sus misiones: educación, investigación y actividades de extensión. Existe un creciente reconocimiento del trabajo realizado por las universidades para incorporar el desarrollo sostenible en sus actividades diarias. La herramienta GreenMetric facilita el análisis de las instituciones más activas en esta área y puede ayudar a compartir buenas prácticas en materia de sostenibilidad.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Sostenibilidad, Desarrollo Sostenible, Universidad, Educación Superior, IU-GreenMetric

PROMOTING INTERNATIONAL COOPERATION IN ONLINE POSTGRADUATE PROGRAMS TO HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS IN DISADVANTAGED COUNTRIES

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Postgraduate studies have proven to be a necessity during the last decade in order to ensure the continuity and proliferation of an academic institution. Postgraduate studies also ensure that there will always be a new generation of scholars that will carry the torch and keep the light of knowledge flickering. However, there are some disadvantaged institutions that have been suffering from the effects of wars and international political disputes. This paper describes the economic and logistic efficiency of online joint PhD programs. Those programs would be established as a fulfillment of universities' need of a well-prepared academic staff due to shortage in qualified faculty members in different majors. The shortage is a result of different local conditions given in a country such as Syria. Those conditions have affected local universities and therefore many obstacles were hindering educational agreements that used to exist and offer scholarships for postgraduate studies. New graduates and potential candidates used to be offered scholarships to study abroad at well renowned universities in order to gain the required knowledge and expertise to become a qualified faculty member in specialties that could not be developed or catered to locally such as linguistics, cognitive linguistics, corpus linguistics as those specialties are not quite well established in such countries. Another reason might be the rarity of qualified staff to teach those specialties. The perfect case study could be applied to the conditions of postgraduate programs at the English Department at Damascus University. The department used to offer a master program sponsored by Warwick University. However, the local conditions have greatly affected and disturbed the previous agreement and hindered its development into a PhD program. A solution would be reached with the assistance of the Syrian virtual university to host such a joint online program that

could still be rich, credible, and qualifying to help limit staff shortages. In addition, it will eliminate many logistic issues, such as acquiring a visa, and will greatly reduce costs for both parties. Finally, it will reduce the time spent overseas in studying and will enable postgraduate students to become effective members of staff while pursuing their degrees and thus fill the need for faculty members.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

International Cooperation, Syria, Online Postgraduate Programs, Disadvantaged Countries, Staff Shortages

PROBLEMATIZING DOMINANT DEFINITIONS, DISCOURSES, AND PRACTICES OF SUSTAINABILITY IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Sustainable (development) is one of our most pressing global challenges. In 2015, member states of the United Nations adopted the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. As a result, many HEIs are integrating sustainability (and sustainable development) into their mandates, operations and curricula. However, even while sustainable development is quickly becoming a new legitimating discourse in higher education, this does not mean its definition, associated meanings, and practices are fixed. The concept itself remains abstract, complex, and multidimensional (Ceulemans et al., 2015; Waas et al., 2011). Moreover, most academic research on sustainability in higher education focuses on institutions in the Global North (Caeiro et al., 2020; Urbanski & Leal Filho, 2015; Yanez et al., 2019). This is despite the fact that lower- and middle-income countries in the Global South are disproportionately experiencing the effects of climate change and environmental degradation (Islam & Winkel, 2017). This paper responds to calls for HEIs to include pluralistic views of the world as well as diverse ways of knowing when framing sustainability efforts in higher education (Binagwaho et al., 2022). Our paper brings together findings from two projects in a multi-pronged research program addressing how HESD is enacted in diverse contexts.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Sustainability, Higher Education, Localization, New Approaches.

INVESTIGATING THE CAUSALITY BETWEEN TOURISM REVENUE AND GDP IN NEPAL: AN ARDL BOUNDS TESTING APPROACH

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Tourism has become an important economic factor for Nepal due to its unique cultural and natural heritage and various adventure travel activities that attract millions of tourists each year. The sector accounts for around 7.5% of Nepal's GDP and offers numerous employment opportunities. However, the relationship between tourism receipts and GDP in Nepal is not fully comprehended. The purpose of this study is to investigate the long-term and short-term causal relationship between tourism revenue and GDP in Nepal. This study has utilized the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) framework with Granger causality to investigate the existence of long-term relationships between two variables. This study examines the dynamic relationship between tourism receipts and GDP in Nepal using data from 1995 to 2020. The ARDL framework and ECM are used to explore long-term equilibrium relationships between two variables. The study also uses the Granger causality test to examine causal relationships between variables. Empirical estimates in this study strongly support a long-run cointegration between tourism receipts and GDP, indicating a significantly positive relationship. The Granger causality test examines whether one variable can be used to predict another variable in a time series dataset by estimating a regression model and testing for causality. The results show evidence of causality between LNTR and LNGDP, with past values of each variable providing predictive power for future values of the other variables. The results suggest a bidirectional causal relationship between the two variables. The study found a strong positive relationship between tourism receipts and GDP in Nepal. This is underpinned by the long-term co-integration and robustness of the ARDL model. Tourist arrivals are known to have a significant impact on GDP. Government

funding for tourism development and infrastructure is therefore recommended to boost the country's industry and overall GDP.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Tourism Revenue, Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Granger Causality, ARDL Bounds Testing Approach, CUSUM Test

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHERS' PROFESSIONAL JOURNEY AND CONSTRUCTION OF THEIR IDENTITY

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Given the widespread concentration on beliefs, values, emotions, critical incidents, and practices in exploring teachers' professional identities, this study presents the trajectories of identity construction of three English language teachers from Nepal, analyzing their storied lives from schoolteachers to university professors. For this purpose, the article considered the three-dimensional professional development model forwarded by Padwad and Dixit (2014) to explore the effective mediation by the state agencies, culture and the policies, appropriate support from the organizations, and the bottom-up initiatives taken by the teachers in their professional development. Besides, the professional development journey derived from the in-depth interview of the participants is analyzed by employing Wenger's (1999) communities of practice, particularly engagement, alignment, and imagination, as theoretical categories to discover their professional identities. The analysis revealed that passion for language, creativity, and motivation to learn English during childhood initially encouraged them to study English. In addition, inspiration from their teachers during their schooling and later a competitive working environment motivated them to experiment with innovative teaching approaches and establish themselves in the profession. Furthermore, diversification in university teaching according to university requirements and resultant divergence from the professional root ultimately transformed their identity beyond English teachers. Finally, university policy, customization of teachers as per the university requirement, and their survival strategy as English teachers in a university where technical subjects are given more priority has impacted their professional identities.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Teacher Professional Development, English Language Teaching, Professional Identity, Communities of Practice

EXPLORATORY RESEARCH: IS THERE A RELATION BETWEEN EMERGENCE OF POPULISMS IN THE POLITICAL SCENARIO AND DETERIORATION OF THE TOURISM DESTINATION IMAGE?

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The political class has always shown a great interest in the tourism sector of their territories, even being aware that tourists are not voters. The multiplier effect that comes with tourism development on wealth and employment or the big amount of tax revenues are already convincing arguments, and yet there is another powerful reason. The tourist image of the destination is the biggest support for the transverse image of the territory (Kim, Styliadis, & Oh, 2019). This research intends to perform an exploratory analysis about the potential cause-effect relationship between the emergence of populisms in public institutions and the deterioration of the tourism destination image (TDI), considering destinations at national level. On the one hand, the influence of the TDI on country competitiveness has already been demonstrated by the World Economic Forum (WEF). The WEF bi-annual Travel and Tourism Competitive index (TTCI, recently re-called Travel and Tourism Development index -TTDI-) includes indicators related to competitiveness. On the other hand, tourist perceptions should also be analyzed considering the meaning, structure, formation, and measurement regarding how the TDI is perceived (e.g., Gallarza, Saura, and Garcia 2002; Pike 2007). The main hypothesis for this exploratory work would be whether, in a *ceteris paribus* scenario, as populisms emerge, the TDI is negatively affected. Since these political waves have only recently haunted countries where tourism has a great economic impact, there is not much scientific literature addressing this thematic, hence its originality. This research uses a demonstrative methodology through the analysis of real cases at national level, where tourist competitiveness acts as an indicator of the evolution and positioning of the brand-destination. But also, since a cause-effect relationship

between the TDI and the volume of tourists has been proven (Viana, de Sousa Saldanha & Barreto, 2021), quantitative data analysis will be carried out, considering the tourism sources of the targeted countries. The main outcome of this study will result in the confirmation of the hypothesis (either with or without exceptions) regarding the penalizing aspect of populisms on the TDI, and in consequence, on the general image of a territory.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Populism, Politics, Country Brand, Tourist Destination Image

MOVIES FOR TEACHING BUSINESS MANAGEMENT TO GENERATION Z

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Teaching introductory courses on topics linked to business management to undergraduate students poses a challenge beyond capturing interest. Besides, the majority of first undergraduate students are millennials with different learning habits compared with their previous cohorts. Thus, teaching management concepts to them could be very challenging. In this paper, we present an experience about teaching business management with movies. A movie, as a tool for classroom learning, can be an effective teaching method to introduce experiential learning in the business management classroom. Using content analysis, we wrote a short summary and business issues depicted in seven movies. Additionally, questionnaires about student satisfaction and business management topics are carried out. Finally, a quantitative multiple regression analysis is carried out with the responses of both questionnaires. The results suggest the usefulness of movies as a learning tool in the subject of business management. Recommendations and research questions are provided in order to improve the use of movies for learning business management in future academic courses.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Movies, Centennials, Business Management, Teaching Tools, Higher Education

INVESTIGACIÓN-ACCIÓN PARTICIPATIVA EN EL ABORDAJE DE DISFUNCIONES DEL SUELO PÉLVICO EN MARISCADORAS: PROMOCIÓN DE SALUD EN EL MARCO DE LA AGENDA 2030

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

La Investigación-Acción-Participativa (IAP) es una metodología que facilita la intervención comunitaria para promover la salud del suelo pélvico de las mariscadoras a pie en Pontevedra. Su objetivo es identificar necesidades de salud, empoderar a las mariscadoras y generar cambios socio-laborales mediante la intersectorialidad y acuerdo político, alineándose con los principios de la Agenda 2030 y en particular con los Objetivos de Desarrollo Sostenible 3 (Salud) y 5 (Género). La IAP dentro del paradigma sociocrítico sigue un proceso cíclico, combinando investigación y acción. Con diseño descriptivo-interpretativo enmarcado en las fases 1, 2 y 3 de la Guía Acción Comunitaria para ganar Salud. Se promueve la participación activa y colaborativa creando un equipo motor y red de apoyo que involucra académicos, instituciones, profesionales y mariscadoras. Se emplearon técnicas cualitativas (observación, entrevistas, focus group) y cuantitativas (cuestionario). Los resultados del análisis descriptivo, del contenido y la revisión de objetivos de cada fase, indicaron que las mariscadoras reconocen necesidades de salud en relación con el suelo pélvico. Se obtuvieron acuerdos de participación y el interés del Servicio Gallego de Salud para la implementación y difusión mediática. Las fases iniciales de la IAP constituyen una metodología efectiva para analizar y priorizar las necesidades de salud para la acción comunitaria.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

IAP, Acción Comunitaria, Mariscadoras, Agenda 2030, Promoción de la Salud

ANÁLISIS DE LA COHERENCIA ENTRE METODOLOGÍAS Y TÉCNICAS DE EVALUACIÓN UTILIZADAS EN EDUCACIÓN SUPERIOR PARA EL DOMINIO DE COMPETENCIAS. UN ESTUDIO DE CASO

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Este estudio pretende analizar la coherencia entre las metodologías educativas y las técnicas de evaluación utilizadas en educación superior, así como su vinculación con los diferentes tipos de competencias a través del análisis de los diseños curriculares que figuran en la plataforma de tele docencia, con el fin de ofrecer un panorama de las diferentes opciones elegidas por el profesorado. Para ello se describirá las técnicas metodológicas utilizadas agrupándolas en activas y pasivas, así como los instrumentos de evaluación. En segundo lugar, estableceremos el número de competencias que se evalúan con cada instrumento elegido por el profesorado y cuál es su tipología, se comprobará el número técnicas de evaluación seleccionadas son adecuadas y coherentes con el tipo y número de competencias evaluadas y se verificará la coherencia de las metodologías educativas en relación con el nivel competencial y los instrumentos de evaluación utilizados para comprobarlo. Además, se describirán las técnicas metodológicas más comunes en relación con el ámbito de conocimiento. Se ha optado por un estudio de caso de corte exploratorio descriptivo mediante procedimientos cuantitativos. Entre los resultados se destaca que en las asignaturas de grado se emplearon 28 metodologías distintas con un promedio de 4 técnicas por asignatura. El 2 % del profesorado utiliza solamente una técnica durante su proceso educativo. El 91 % de las materias emplearon la lección

magistral. Las metodologías empleadas fomentan el aprendizaje activo (67 %) frente al pasivo (33 %). Si se tiene en cuenta las áreas de conocimiento, el área de ciencias es la que más metodologías activas utiliza (71 %), seguida de ingeniería y arquitectura (69 %), ciencias sociales y jurídicas (67 %), ciencias de la salud (62 %) y por último artes y humanidades con un (61 %). Se emplean 35 instrumentos de evaluación diferentes. En cada asignatura se utiliza un promedio de 3 instrumentos de evaluación para calificar las competencias del alumnado. Los instrumentos más utilizados son resolución de problemas y/o ejercicios (35 %) y examen de preguntas de desarrollo (34 %). Un instrumento de evaluación evalúa una media de 10 competencias, el número máximo evaluado es de 35 competencias, mínimo 3 competencias. En cada asignatura se evalúa una media de 14 competencias, entre básicas (2), genéricas (3), específicas (4) y transversales (5). Las técnicas metodológicas utilizadas se relacionan con el dominio de conocimientos (100 %), procedimientos (74 %) y actitudes (10 %), y no hay diferencias entre los distintos ámbitos de conocimiento. Mientras que los instrumentos de evaluación se clasificaron de acuerdo con el tipo de contenidos que miden y se observa que el 96 % mide conocimientos, el 53 % procedimientos y 21 % actitudes. Destacamos que el 36% utiliza como instrumento de evaluación técnica metodológica. Tampoco existen diferencias en función del área de conocimiento. Resultaría útil crear un software que ayude a mejorar la eficiencia y coherencia en el diseño de los diferentes elementos curriculares de los programas educativos.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Metodologías Docentes, Instrumentos de Evaluación, Aprendizaje Activo

LA INFLUENCIA DEL CONTEXTO PERSONAL Y SITUACIONAL EN LA MOTIVACIÓN POR EL APRENDIZAJE DE LENGUAS EXTRANJERAS

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

El aprendizaje de lenguas extranjeras tiene un papel esencial en la preparación de los estudiantes para enfrentarse con las nuevas perspectivas creadas por una sociedad en continuo cambio. Numerosos investigadores de la adquisición de lenguas (Hinkel, 2017; MacIntyre, 2017; Oxford, 2018) coinciden en afirmar que las diferencias en el aprendizaje y la variedad de niveles de competencia comunicativa entre estudiantes de una misma lengua extranjera se deben a distintos factores individuales que interactúan entre sí. De este modo, en el proceso de adquisición de otras lenguas, tanto en el propio país como en el extranjero, influyen diferentes variables que pueden favorecer o dificultar el aprendizaje y la asimilación de conocimientos lingüísticos, de conocimientos socioculturales y de conocimientos pragmáticos imprescindibles para el dominio eficaz de la lengua. En el proceso de adquisición de otras lenguas intervienen algunas variables individuales (Moronta Tremols, Rodríguez Fernández y Fernández-Lasarte, 2019) como la memoria (Sunderman y Kroll, 2009), el estilo de aprendizaje y las estrategias de aprendizaje, la personalidad, la motivación y la ansiedad (Alpaslan y Yalvac, 2017; Asif, 2017; Bhatti y Memon, 2016; Dogan y Tuncer, 2016; Ramos, 2017; Razak, Yassin, y Maasum, 2017; Santos, Gorter, y Cenoz, 2017), las creencias del estudiante (Corpas, 2015), el entorno y la edad (Llanes y Muñoz, 2012). En el contexto de aprendizaje de un idioma la actitud y

la motivación se va construyendo en función de las opiniones y creencias del individuo hacia un determinado referente (Rodríguez-Pérez, 2014). Ante situaciones de contacto lingüístico, el hecho de que un hablante escoja una u otra lengua para comunicarse responde, entre otros factores, a las actitudes y motivaciones lingüísticas. Con este estudio pretendemos averiguar el tipo o tipos de motivación de los informantes para aprender una lengua extranjera y el grado de correlación de las mismas. Trabajamos con una muestra compuesta por un total de 442 estudiantes, 149 hombres (33,7 %) y 293 mujeres (66,3 %), con edades comprendidas entre los 14 y los 73 años ($M=41,57$; $DT=3,31$). Se ha optado por un estudio de tipo descriptivo correlacional para establecer las posibles relaciones entre las variables estudiadas. Para medir estadísticamente las posibles correlaciones entre las variables estudiadas, se ha aplicado el Coeficiente de Correlación de Pearson (r). Se ha utilizado como herramienta la Escala de Motivación en Educación (EME) integrada por 28 ítems. Consta de tres factores: motivación intrínseca, motivación extrínseca y desmotivación. Para el análisis de la consistencia interna se utilizó el coeficiente alfa de Cronbach cuyo valor resulta aceptable y significativo desde un punto de vista estadístico ($\alpha =0,91$). Los resultados muestran diferencias significativas entre las variables objeto de estudio y ponen de manifiesto la existencia de claras y significativas diferencias en el afrontamiento de la motivación como variable dependiente. En concreto, se ha podido confirmar que los estudiantes varones presentan diferencias significativas en motivación intrínseca y en motivación extrínseca presentando una media inferior en ambos casos. Este patrón diferencial se repite en todas las variables objeto de estudio como edad, modalidad y situación laboral alcanzando niveles significativos.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Motivación, Desmotivación, Enseñanza-aprendizaje, Lengua Extranjera

AYUDANDO A LAS FAMILIAS A TRAVÉS DE LAS ESCUELAS DE FAMILIAS. HABILIDADES Y COMPETENCIAS

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Esta investigación surge a partir de la Recomendación Rec (2006)19 del Consejo de Europa sobre políticas de apoyo al ejercicio positivo de la parentalidad. La iniciativa europea incita a las autoridades estatales y locales a que adapten la disposición a sus características particulares y lo hagan con medidas estables y continuadas en el tiempo. Por ejemplo, a través del diseño y puesta en práctica de programas de parentalidad positiva. Para que esto sea posible es necesario, en primer lugar, la implicación de los investigadores sociales de las universidades y, en segundo lugar, un acuerdo con los agentes sociales, de forma que estas investigaciones puedan llevarse a la práctica. Este estudio aúna ambas necesidades y se focaliza en el estudio y autoevaluación de una Escuela de Familias de un Instituto de Educación Secundaria Obligatoria creada ad hoc para la investigación. La autoevaluación se desarrolló con las siguientes herramientas: la Guía de Competencias Interprofesionales en Parentalidad Positiva y la Guía de Buenas Prácticas en Parentalidad Positiva, publicadas en España y fruto del trabajo de un convenio entre Universidades españolas y la Federación Española de Municipios y Provincias; Una encuesta de satisfacción diseñada ex profeso para nuestra investigación y una adaptación del International Parental Survey. Los objetivos que se pretenden son los siguientes: Analizar si se realizan buenas prácticas y competencias interprofesionales en nuestra Escuela de familias; Comprobar si, tras la experiencia, las familias están satisfechas con el programa; Comprobar si hay diferencias en los parámetros de parentalidad positiva en el

hogar antes y después de realizar el programa de parentalidad positiva en la Escuela de familias. Se dedicó parte de la primera sesión de la Escuela de familias a cumplimentar la adaptación del International Parenting Survey por las familias. Este cuestionario se comparó con el realizado en la última sesión del programa. La persona encargada de dinamizar las sesiones de la Escuela de familias comprobó el cumplimiento de los diferentes indicadores de buenas prácticas y competencias interprofesionales. Al finalizar el programa se cumplimentó un cuestionario de satisfacción sobre algunos aspectos del programa, Lo que se pretende con este estudio es demostrar el buen funcionamiento de un programa de parentalidad positiva en lo que se refiere a las competencias y habilidades necesarias para llevarlo a cabo con éxito. De igual manera se pretende poner el valor la creación de Escuelas de Familias en centros de educación públicos para hacer llegar a todas las familias que así lo deseen, la ayuda que necesitan de manera sencilla, eficaz y gratuita. Los resultados de estudios como el que presentamos es enorme ya que benefician a la sociedad en su conjunto y en cualquier lugar del mundo. Por otra parte, ayuda a resolver una amplia gama de problemas reales directamente relacionados con el bienestar familiar y, por ende, con un adecuado desarrollo social.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Parentalidad Positiva, Programas de Educación de padres, Familia, Escuela

THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY ON THE INTELLECTUAL CAPITAL AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE RELATIONSHIP

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

In the knowledge-based economy, information and knowledge enables firms to develop a unique set of skills and competencies, which in turn contributes to organizational growth and enhanced financial performance (Ferraris et al., 2019). Intellectual Capital (IC) is often considered as one of the drivers of performance in that knowledge era (Jordao & Almeida, 2017). However, the dimensions of IC are evolving very fast and embrace new issues and challenges within today's business environment. The social implication of organizations is also becoming a significant concern for policy-makers and business managers. Companies that were conventionally seen as economic entities operating to enhance shareholder's value now have the mandate of being socially sustainable (Waddock and Graves, 1997). Over and above their traditional role of providing goods and services, nowadays society expects organizations to act in a socially responsible manner (Lee & Cho, 2019). Such accountability towards society is called "Corporate Social Responsibility, CSR". Although various empirical studies have been done to prove the contribution of CSR towards FP, relatively few ones have integrated IC as a construct even though such capital is often considered as part of CSR activities. IC is one of the CSR's components in the context of people. If the company is concerned about its employees, both its product quality and customer service will improve significantly. Thus, CSR activities have a proportional relationship with IC (Razafindrambinina & Kariodimedjo, 2011; Musibah & Sulaiman; 2013). This paper attempts to supplement the existing literature by examining how IC influences CSR which then acts as a mediator on the relationship between IC and FP. To achieve the objective of this paper of empirically testing CSR as a mediator in the IC-FP relationship, the Barron and Kenny's (1986) four-step approach will be used

together with the PVECM approach for the 40 listed companies in Mauritius over the period 2007 to 2022. The empirical results firstly show that IC and CSR independently have a positive and significant influence on FP. The findings also confirm that IC influences CSR and vice versa. Lastly, Barron and Kenny's results conclude that CSR has a partial mediating effect on the IC- FP relationship.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Intellectual Capital, Financial Performance, Corporate Social Responsibility, Mediating Effect

SCHOOL LEADERSHIP UNDER COVID-19 PANDEMIC: A CRITIQUE OF THE SOUTH AFRICAN SCHOOL CONTEXT

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The advent of COVID-19 exposed the lack of readiness for school leaders to cope with demands of leading during a pandemic. We argue that globally, school leaders were not trained to deal with a crisis of COVID-19 proportions. Leaders in the twenty-first century need to have the required skills like the twenty-first century leadership skills and Fourth Industrial Revolution skills. This study investigated how school leaders are handling the challenges of school leadership under the COVID-19 pandemic in the 4IR era. We did an analysis of local and international literature to identify gaps. The study revealed that school leaders and teachers have inadequate information and communication technology skills. Leadership preparation programmes are lagging behind in preparing school leaders to lead in a crisis. Furthermore, the study revealed that school leaders and teachers do not establish communities of learning to learn leadership skills from each other. The study has concluded that there is no alignment between the level of readiness for school leaders and leadership skills of the twenty-first century.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Educational Leadership, Leadership in a Crisis, Leadership Skills, School Leadership, 4IR (Fourth Industrial Revolution)

EQUITABLE HIGHER EDUCATION FUTURES: ADDRESSING ACCESS, PARTNERSHIPS AND SUSTAINABILITY

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The pandemic illuminated crucial gaps in the quality of education systems around the world. Students across all education levels faced challenges; however, learning was a greater challenge for vulnerable communities. The students from marginalised communities in Global South have been at a greater disadvantage as they suffer systemic inadequacies along with intersectional barriers like gender, class, colour, race, disability, religion. Ensuring Justice (a pre-requisite for sustainability) is pivotal in developing contexts by guaranteeing affordable access to quality-education for all citizens. Aspiring to enhance equity and justice, the Indian government has introduced the National Education Policy, 2020. Targetting 50%GER in higher education by 2035 and reinforcing SDG 4, partnerships are forged between the government and private-players as an efficient strategy to reduce state investment while ensuring deliverables. Taking the massification of the education agenda ahead, the post-secondary assessment has been reformed. Now, admissions to all courses are granted through standardised tests to ensure transparency, merit and greater participation in most public HEIs. Standardised testing requires specialised and exclusive preparation alongside good test-taking skills. Although the state seeks inclusion through free and subsidised tutoring, in practice it legitimises the informal education markets, reinforcing more privatisation. The rise of education-technology, partnership and mergers between shadow education and ed-tech companies, and privatisation of public educational spaces are tools used in comparative contexts to reduce state participation in ensuring education provisions. The new developments in the expanding Indian-education-markets that take ahead the

massification of higher education are discussed. This paper is a section of the researcher's current doctoral thesis that discusses government initiatives and the legitimisation of new-tutoring-markets after the policy changes during the pandemic. It explores the debate around the welfare-state's responsibility to ensure the education as right and the public-private partnerships adopted by the state to enhance equitable-access to post secondary education during desperate times. A comparative case-study design examines the role of this public-private partnership, ensuring that 'cases' are not measured against a universal-yardstick or pitted against-one-other, rather appreciated for their variations and contributions across Indian states. The study draws from neo-liberal policy framework and organisational change theories to unwrap the increasing privatisation and private players; its vision and viability for safeguarding sustainability of quality-education agenda. This paper in particular touches upon all these concepts while focussing majorly on the sustainability of access parameters for admission to post-secondary or higher education in India. It informs policy practices from an equity and justice lens in pursuit of the National Education Policy vision for massification of higher education.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Post-secondary, Privatization, Partnerships, Sustainability, Access, Equity

REWRITING THE RULES OF RESEARCH AND SCHOLARSHIP FOR OUR TIMES

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

As humanity stares down a cascade of environmental crises, alongside collapses of international order and peace around the world, academe continues to move in the wrong direction, instead of seeking to help address these challenges. Driven by bizarre new practices of numerically scoring scholarship and globally ranking institutions, academic disciplines and universities reward individual scholars for being selfish, greedy, and competitive—rather than for taking social and environmental responsibility. Over the past few decades, research has become more self-serving for individual scholars and their disciplines – with interdisciplinarity being a mission that universities try and keep failing to promote. Scholars who pursue high scores and institutions that pursue high ranks keep justifying the “universal” value of contributing knowledge for greater human good: the reality, however, is the opposite, because greater human good could be achieved far better by first grounding research and scholarship in the communities and countries in which scholars and institutions are located, where they know the context and needs and priorities best, where they can translate and apply knowledge most impactfully. If scholars and institutions are honest, it is evident that knowledge has many purposes, from the advancement of disciplines (of course) to the support for professions and communities to the input for policy and culture and the redirection of public discourse within and across borders. But scholars who are selfish and institutions that are irresponsible to society keep using the first, epistemic purpose alone, as the sole purpose of universities/higher learning—all while the alarming challenges of human societies and a planet in peril keep exacerbating every day. These trends, driven by powerful global neoliberal and neocolonial forces, also mask or reproduce local dynamics of inequality, irresponsibility, and injustice. And they deserved to be called what they are: radical challenges warrant radically honest descriptions, if we are to address them to any effect. My proposed presentation will share lessons drawn

from a scholar training model, the STAR Scholars Training Program, that sought to address the above challenges of academia. Facilitated on behalf of STAR Scholars Network for the last two years, the training has involved nearly a hundred scholars from nearly forty countries. Building on the vision with which I initially developed the framework for this training, and as one of the six facilitators of the last two training sessions, I will share and discuss how scholar leaders and academic institutions can counter some of the above trends and the neoliberal and neocolonial forces behind them. For instance, countering the trend of doing research to acquire grants (rather than the other way around), scholars and institutions can put the horse of social purpose in front of the cart of research, with the necessary resources provided by grants serving as wheels or lubricant for the cart. To counter the practice of measuring the “impact” of research/publication by counting the number of citations, scholars and institutions can instead seek and show the actual social and professional impact of their knowledge contributing, integrating knowledge impact in the very process of research where possible. I will structure the presentation as discussion and problem-solving activities (splitting the time equally between me and the audience), as we do the following together: 1) explore the harms that our intellectual and material contributions are making in society (from toxic chemicals to harmful ideologies to self-serving ideals) and seek greater social good through our scholarship; 2) identify how to break down barriers against the normal working of knowledge in society (of academia is a bubble of well-connected minorities, a space behind walls of financial and social barriers); 3) rethink teaching/learning by putting students and an inquiry-driven mode of education at the center; and 4) develop practical ways for countering our privilege toward taking responsibility and countering the status quo within and beyond academe. These activities are built on the four modules of the STAR Scholars Training program: developing socially driven research agenda, sharing and applying knowledge beyond academe, integrating research into teaching, and seeking multiplier effects of a knowledge economy designed to advance higher education’s social mission. I acknowledge my fellow facilitators who have collaborated with me to give life and meaning to these ideas, impacting the careers of dozens of scholars around the world.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Research, Scholarship, Social and Environmental Responsibility, Knowledge Economy, Socially-driven Research

CAPACITY DEVELOPMENT NEEDS FOR COLLEGE PRINCIPALS: CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS IN CURRENT POLICY DISCOURSE IN INDIA

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The National Education Policy envisages Higher Education to reach greater heights in the post- pandemic era. With a goal of almost doubling the current Higher Education Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) by 2035, the long-term aim of increasing public investment in education by 6% GDP share instead of the current 4.43% has been emphasized in the policy. The massification of education has been promoted through greater use of technology and by promoting online and distance learning, while at the university level funding has become necessarily performance based. The performance criteria are indicators mentioned in the policy guidelines as quality measures like holistic multidisciplinary, research intensiveness, continuous professional development of faculty etc. All these constitute the educational input, process, outcome and context indicators (Florida & Quinto, 2015). The quality assurance approach of the NEP, 2020 ensures to serve students and other stakeholders' quality higher education through all combined processes taking place in each HEI. The quality assurance is majorly dependent on the management (Kahveci et al., 2012) responsible for curating the higher education experiences. The dynamics of higher education in the country are driving the demand for a new set of skills and capabilities for tomorrow's leaders. This imperative promotes the professional development of college management, wherein the academic head is the College Principal. College Principals today face challenges alongside all the opportunities and prospects the NEP, 2020 envisages. Often while there is a focus on opportunities, the challenges get sidelined in the policy implementation

discussions resulting in unachieved goals. Accountability without autonomy can often lead to discontentment and inefficient resource utilization. Academic capitalism and resource development focus attention on the relationship of funding to purpose. Emphasis on outcomes without optimal mapping of ground realities and challenges often leads to unmet aspirations. The current study thus attempts to understand the quality higher education agenda through the lens of college principals' view, wherein it aims to map out the opportunities and challenges that these principals deal within their institutions. This initiative is much needed as we begin to chalk-out a road-map for implementation of the current policy. This independent study attempts to understand the experiences of Higher Education Leadership particularly the Principals of Colleges in reference to the implementation of the key elements of the National Policy on Education, NPE, 2020. It is an enquiry to gauge how the HEIs have been envisaged to implement Combined University entrance test (CUET), multidisciplinary, Multiple entry and exit options, internationalisation, accreditation, research and innovation etc. In order to gain an in-depth understanding of the phenomena experienced by specific individuals, phenomenological inquiry has been conducted using a qualitative approach while engaging with the Leadership Development Theory and Organisational Management theory. This interpretivist design helps inform the perspective and attitudes of the Principals towards the current policy discourse and its sustainability in future. The study envisages that leadership has to go much beyond effectively managing the status quo. The context of the Higher Education mantle is dynamic, multidimensional and complex. It requires effective leadership that could aid in improving the changing landscape of knowledge and in increasing the potential for interdisciplinarity. The study helps analyse the requirements of the Principals who move from purely academic duties as faculty to addressing leadership and administrative duties as Principals. It addresses the pertinent question on how Principals should be facilitated and supported for implementation of recent initiatives for policy as well as overall management of the institution.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Leadership, Sustainability, Higher Education Policy, Quality Assurance, Internationalization

CONTRIBUTION OF HIGHLY EDUCATED EXPERTS IN SUSTAINABLE RENEWABLE ENERGY AND CLIMATE CHANGE REDUCTION PROJECTS

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

In-depth knowledge attained through higher-level education enables individuals to become professionals and experts in their respective fields. These professionals include researchers, teachers, economists, environmentalists, sociologists, engineers, and others. Based on their expertise, these professionals can engage in the planning, design, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of development activities. Sustainable development is defined as "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs." For any project to be considered feasible and sustainable, it must be technically sound, environmentally friendly, economically viable, and socially acceptable. Therefore, experts from various relevant disciplines play a crucial role in ensuring the sustainability of a project from all four perspectives.

The United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) aim to achieve decent lives for all on a healthy planet by 2030. As of 2078 BS, the literacy rate in Nepal is 76.3%, showing a significant improvement from 65.9% in 2068 BS. However, disparities in school attendance still exist based on gender, class, and other social factors. Out of the 17 SDGs, SDG4 focuses on ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all. SDG13 emphasizes the urgent need to combat climate change and its impacts. Well-educated experts can actively participate in sustainable development activities to minimize the adverse effects of climate change in the current context.

This study aims to assess the sustainable aspects of a Renewable Energy Development Project focused on biogas. The involvement of several experts, including civil engineers, environmentalists, sociologists, and economists, will be crucial. The study will utilize a mixed-method approach, incorporating both qualitative and quantitative methods. Primary data will be collected through

field observations, key informant interviews, and formal and informal discussions with community members. Secondary data will be gathered through literature reviews. Data analysis will involve the use of various models, such as the Long Range Energy Alternative Planning System (LEAP) for energy and environment assessment, the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for social analysis, and an Economic Analysis model for economic evaluation. The project's outcome, once implemented, will contribute to combating climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Higher Education, Sustainable Development, Long Range Energy Alternative Planning System (LEAP), Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), Climate Change

HUMAN-CENTERED DESIGN METHOD TO ACHIEVE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The needs of students and the shifting demands of society are driving ongoing change and adaptation in higher education. Within this framework, academic learning and social action are linked through the transformative technique of Service-Learning (SL), an educational approach. By encouraging a link between theory and practice, where hard and soft skills are worked on, SL goes beyond the conventional constraints of university teaching and inspires students to become proactive agents of social change.

Furthermore, the goal of the Human-Centered Design (HDC) technique is to provide an inventive design that is grounded in user demands (user experience). The aim of this project was to create an experience using the HCD technique in the context of Engineering Drawing, with a specific focus on the Sustainable Development Goals. The experience includes working with people, applying information, developing hard and soft skills, integrating theory and practice, and empowering students to conduct research. Participating in this event were sixty-three first-year University of A Coruña (Spain) students from three STEAM

degrees. The projects used a Service-Learning (SL) method and concentrated on finding a real-world problem's solution. In particular, resource prototypes were created in response to requests from organizations that have a contract with the UDC Office of Cooperation and Volunteering. CAD software was used to create the projects' three-dimensional designs. Twenty projects in all were developed. A survey was sent out once it was finished to gauge how satisfied the students were. The survey's findings were quite encouraging. An interactive learning environment has been facilitated by the HCD approach.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

STEAM, Human-Centered Design, Service-Learning, Sustainable Development Goals

EL DEBATE UNIVERSITARIO COMO HERRAMIENTA DE INNOVACIÓN DOCENTE

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Los debates sobre un tema científico de relevancia internacional son una herramienta didáctica que beneficia la reflexión, las habilidades comunicativas, de trabajo en equipo o la toma de decisiones. Es por ello que el objetivo del presente estudio fue analizar el uso de esta herramienta didáctica en un grupo de alumnado universitario del Grado de Dirección y Gestión Pública, concretamente el alumnado de tercer curso tanto en su modalidad virtual como presencial (n = 29, muestra invitada= 42) en el tema: La nueva regulación de la dirección pública profesional en España, ¿debate nuevo o viejo?, vinculado a la discusión actual sobre el reciente Anteproyecto de Ley de Función Pública del Ministerio de Hacienda y Función Pública del Gobierno de España. La metodología empleada consistió en un debate profesional que se practicó en tres sesiones previas al mismo en la materia de Habilidades en las Administraciones Públicas, pero contando con el apoyo y participación del profesorado de las materias de Dirección Pública Profesional y Dirección Pública en los Gobiernos Locales. Se ha seguido el protocolo estipulado para los debates universitarios en la Facultad de Dirección y Gestión Pública, concretándolo a las características de los grupos participantes. Las sesiones de práctica del debate tuvieron una duración de 2 horas por sesión, un total de 6 horas. La evaluación realizada consistió en una autoevaluación a través de una reflexión grupal de los participantes y una heteroevaluación de un tribunal compuesto por dos docentes del Grado a través de la rúbrica ad hoc. Los resultados obtenidos mediante la evaluación indicada previamente confirman que este tipo de propuestas metodológicas son eficaces para el desarrollo de habilidades de reflexión, de trabajo en equipo, comunicación verbal y no verbal, toma de decisiones y adquisición de contenidos y competencias de las tres materias. Los resultados obtenidos concuerdan con los hallados por experiencias pasadas en Universidades como la de Granada o la

Universidad Loyola, quienes indicaban que los debates permiten el desarrollo de dichas habilidades comentadas anteriormente. En definitiva, los debates universitarios permiten el desarrollo de las competencias recogidas en los planes de estudios del Grado de Dirección y Gestión Pública a través de una metodología activa, participativa, reflexiva y crítica por lo que pueden ser tenidos en consideración para otras propuestas de naturaleza similar.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Debate, Trabajo en equipo, Habilidades Comunicativas, Toma de decisiones

DEVELOPING THINKING SKILLS IN A GLOBAL CLASSROOM

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The webinar will take the format of a workshop with participation from the audience. There will be an introduction to Global Citizenship Education and its importance in today's classrooms. I will continue with an explanation of what thinking skills are and will make emphasis on the different kinds of thinking skills needed in a global classroom. Working through PBL (Project Based Learning), students will acquire Critical Thinking Skills, Systems Thinking, Strategic Thinking and Creative Thinking. There will be time for debate in the audience to see how they believe these types of thinking can be integrated in the classroom before being provided with the tools to do so. Last but not least, there will be reflection on the benefits of teaching this way. The objectives are (1) to raise teachers' awareness on the importance of global citizenship for today's students; (2) to introduce teachers to thinking skills; (3) to show why thinking skills are essential in a global classroom; and (4) to reflect on what kind of thinking we need to train our students. The main expected result is that teachers leave the webinar with a clear idea of how to take this new way of teaching to their own lessons.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Global Citizenship, Thinking Skills, Systems Thinking

EDUCACIÓN Y PATRIMONIO: LA EXPERIENCIA DE LA RED PEA ARGENTINA

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La educación en patrimonio adquiere importancia en una época en la que conviven una sociedad marcada por lo inmediato, lo presente, lo efímero, que gira en torno al espacio y la dimensión individual insertos en una dinámica global, así como la reivindicación de lo local con una reafirmación de las identidades. Mediante la educación en patrimonio, el bien patrimonial se convierte en un recurso para el aprendizaje, capaz de conectar al ciudadano con su diversidad cultural y su desarrollo social. En este sentido, el trabajo en torno a la educación y el patrimonio realizado desde la Red de Escuelas Asociadas a la UNESCO (Red PEA) en Argentina, buscan constituirse como un proceso permanente centrado en el patrimonio como fuente primaria de conocimiento y enriquecimiento individual y colectivo, a la vez que actúa como un instrumento de “alfabetización cultural” que permite a la persona interpretar el mundo que lo rodea y guiar sus intervenciones. De esta manera, el patrimonio puede considerarse la expresión más genuina de la identidad, porque su apropiación por parte de las personas puede favorecer la construcción de una identidad ciudadana responsable; el desarrollo de un pensamiento social crítico, para ser capaz de situar históricamente las evidencias del pasado y darles significado social, político y cultural; la capacidad de implicarse y actuar de manera responsable en la conservación, la preservación y la divulgación local y global; así como la construcción de un conocimiento histórico y social a partir de la construcción de la conciencia histórica y la indagación histórica con fuentes primarias.

Preservar el Patrimonio Cultural y Natural es una tarea que trasciende la simple conservación de paisajes y monumentos, encontrando en la educación una herramienta fundamental para difundir, sensibilizar y concientizar a la población respecto de problemáticas de interés común. La Convención sobre la Protección del Patrimonio Mundial Cultural y Natural, aprobada por la Conferencia General de la UNESCO en 1972, establece en su artículo 27 que todos los estados firmantes

deben procurar “por todos los medios apropiados, y en particular, a través de programas de educación e información, estimular en sus pueblos el respeto y aprecio por el patrimonio cultural y natural”. Con este mismo espíritu, la Ley de Educación vigente en la República Argentina desde 2006 fija como objetivo prioritario para el sistema educativo nacional “la promoción del conocimiento y los valores que permitan el desarrollo de protección y cuidado del patrimonio cultural y el medio ambiente”. La CONAPLU, a través de la Red PEA, entiende la importancia de colaborar con esta tarea en una estrategia integrada donde la educación es fundamental para garantizar la preservación de nuestros sitios de Patrimonio. Desde la coordinación nacional de la Red PEA, la CONAPLU ha propiciado el trabajo articulado de sus establecimientos educativos, promoviendo los ideales de la UNESCO y alentando el trabajo innovador en el aula.

Objetivos:

- 1) Reflexionar sobre la educación patrimonial como componente fundamental para la educación para el desarrollo sostenible
- 2) Identificar buenas prácticas de educación transformadora llevadas adelante por la Red PEA Argentina en torno al patrimonio cultural y natural

Metodología: exposición, desarrollo de debates a través de preguntas y espacios de compartir reflexiones por parte de los participantes.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Educación, Patrimonio Mundial, Patrimonio Cultural, Patrimonio Natural

IV

ONE HEALTH

NIVEL DE ALFABETIZACIÓN SANITARIA DEL PROFESORADO: INFLUENCIA DE VARIABLES DE SALUD

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

La relevancia de la figura docente como factor de salud ha cobrado gran importancia en los últimos años, de ahí que se preste especial atención al estudio de sus niveles de alfabetización en salud. Una inadecuada preparación docente en este sentido podría suponer un obstáculo sustancial si tenemos en cuenta la influencia que puede tener en los hábitos, creencias y actitudes de sus estudiantes. La alfabetización sanitaria del profesorado se puede definir como la capacidad de este personal para obtener, interpretar y comprender la información y los servicios sanitarios básicos, tomando decisiones adecuadas. A ello se le puede añadir la competencia para utilizar dichos conocimientos de forma que se mejore el aprendizaje de conceptos y habilidades de salud por parte del alumnado. Por ello, el objetivo de esta propuesta consiste en analizar los niveles de alfabetización en salud de docentes españoles, observando, además, la influencia de ciertas variables de salud. La muestra se compone de 450 profesionales de enseñanza obligatoria y el instrumento utilizado es el Cuestionario Europeo de Alfabetización en Salud (HLS-EU-Q47). A partir del análisis estadístico de los datos registrados los resultados más relevantes indican:

que los niveles son buenos, siendo la capacidad de entender la más alta y obteniendo la dimensión de atención y cuidado de la enfermedad la media más elevada; que es mayor el nivel de alfabetización en el profesorado que no ha sufrido ningún proceso patológico, en el que dispone de acompañamiento médico; también es mayor en quien nunca ha tenido un ingreso hospitalario y en quien nunca ha realizado una visita a urgencias; asimismo, los valores son superiores en el personal que realiza con frecuencia ejercicio físico, siendo la alfabetización mayor cuanto mejor autopercepción de la salud se tiene. Se hace necesario afianzar la formación en temáticas de salud en el personal docente, proporcionando programas multidisciplinares y activos para mejorar la alfabetización en aquellas personas que tienen niveles más bajos. También es imprescindible evaluar la eficacia de dichos programas y su posible repercusión en el estudiantado.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Alfabetización en salud, Docentes, Enseñanza Obligatoria

FROM HERMENEUTIC CRITIQUE OF EDUCATION TO THE CONSTRUCTION OF A SOLIDARITY DIVERSITY

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to seek, on the basis of a hermeneutic critique of the epistemological assumptions of educational research and of the pedagogical referents of educational practices, to legitimize the status and purposes of education understood as an anthropological practice.

With this status and by adopting the distinction between "meaning" and "truth" as conceived by Paul Ricoeur, education can truly assume and foster a diversity of solidarity. The ethical distinction between truth and meaning will allow each person to be able to recognize meanings in adverse positions, despite the fact that truth presupposes a conviction that the person him/herself recognizes and leads.

To this end, it is important to first confront the autocracy of epistemological vigilance of scientific research in education with the conflictual and normative dynamics of educational practices.

Thus, a demarcation occurs both from objectivism, without falling into perspectivism, and from dogmatism without opening the door to nihilism, gaining importance as central dimensions of education, personal intersubjectivation and contextualization of practices.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Hermeneutics, Meaning, Truth, Diversity; Solidarity

A HEALTH EDUCATION PERSPECTIVE IN EXPLORING THE EMOTIONAL DISTRESS OF SHELLFISH WORKERS IN THEIR SOCIO-OCCUPATIONAL CONTEXT

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Gender, as a social determinant of health, interacts with other social determinants in a complex and patriarchal social structure. It is therefore also a social determinant of mental health. The aim was to identify emotional distress related to the socio-cultural and working conditions of women shellfish gatherers. An exploratory and descriptive qualitative and quantitative methodology was used on the emotional discomfort of shellfish gatherers on foot. The main findings revealed that shellfish gatherers experience negative emotional states that they identify in everyday situations. This everyday discomfort could become chronic and affect mental health. At the same time, they experience positive emotions and satisfaction with their work in similar contexts. It is essential to consider gender conditions when addressing the emotional distress of women shellfish workers, as these complex circumstances interact and affect health and well-being. Focusing on the emotional health of these women will move towards a care approach that is more sensitive to their needs. Health education is the essential tool to empower shellfish gatherers, providing them with the skills and necessary knowledge to manage their emotional well-being in a specific context such as shellfish gathering.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Shellfish Gatherers, Health, Emotional Distress, Well-being, Health Education

EVIDENCIAS DE VALIDEZ Y FIABILIDAD DEL CUESTIONARIO DE BIENESTAR EUDAIMÓNICO EN ADOLESCENTES

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

El objetivo principal fue identificar las evidencias de validez y fiabilidad del cuestionario de bienestar eudaimónico (QEWB; Waterman et al., 2010) en una muestra de adolescentes en la Comunidad Autónoma de Galicia, así como comprobar su asociación con la práctica del ejercicio físico. Se trata de un estudio instrumental y psicométrico mediante el análisis de la estructura del cuestionario, fiabilidad de consistencia interna e inferencias estadísticas. Participaron 869 adolescentes con edades entre los 12 y 18 años (46.1% chicas; $M_{\text{edad}} = 14.44$). El análisis preliminar de los ítems aconseja reducción del cuestionario a 17 reactivos. Los resultados revelaron la existencia de tres factores (crecimiento, propósito y sentimiento personal) con cargas fuertes en el análisis factorial exploratorio, corroborados mediante el análisis factorial confirmatorio con índices de bondad de ajuste aceptables. La confiabilidad alcanzada fue adecuada para los tres factores del cuestionario. Además, los datos confirman diferencias significativas en los tres factores del bienestar eudaimónico, con puntuaciones superiores en los adolescentes que practican ejercicio físico de manera frecuente. En conclusión, este estudio sostiene el carácter multidimensional del bienestar eudaimónico, con unas propiedades psicométricas del cuestionario QEWB internamente consistentes y confiables. También se confirma una elevada relación entre la práctica de ejercicio físico y el bienestar eudaimónico.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Bienestar Eudaimónico, Ejercicio Físico, Adolescencia, Fiabilidad, Validez, Estructura Factorial

SPORT EDUCATION ROLES AND HEALTH-RELATED FITNESS MARKERS THROUGH AN EDU-CROSSFIT SEASON

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The Sport Education have been recognized as a pedagogical model that contribute with the promotion of physical activity and fitness in children's (Hastie, 2020). Hastie and his colleagues urge to continue validate the reliability of the SEM through other countries, settings, and focus. Yet to date, there none studies that examine the impact of Siedentop model on health-related fitness markers among the season roles. The aim of this study was to examine the impact of an Edu-CrossFit season on SE roles (captain, trainer, manager equipment, judge, and journalist) health-related fitness markers. A total of 70 elementary (5th) school students (36 boys and 34 girls) between 9 to 11 years old ($M=10.7$, $SD=.671$) from Puerto Rico participated on 16th lessons of (60 minutes) two times per week on an Edu CrossFit season. An experimental design was used for this study. SE roles were divided in two groups active (captain, trainer) and passive (judge, manager equipment, and journalist). Fitnessgram test (pacer, push-up, pull-up, and body mass index (BMI) were used as data collection method. Pre and posttest, means, standard deviations (SD), paired samples t-test were conducted to examine differences through the SE roles (active and passive). Overall results, indicate significant differences (improvements) between pretest and posttest (PACER, Push-ups, Sit-ups, and BMI), $p < .001$. In terms of the analysis of variance differences in means among the different SEM active and passive roles (e.g. Captain, trainer, manager equipment, judge, journalist) a slightly better performing were identified for active roles (e.g. captain, trainer) with higher PACER ($M = 5.533$, $SD = 3.277$), push-up ($M=2.233$ $SD = 1.524$) and sit-up scores ($M=3.067$, $SD=2.348$) than passive roles with PACER ($M=4.975$, $SD=4.079$), push-up ($M=2.100$, $SD =1.336$), and sit-ups scores ($M=3.025$, $SD = 2.259$), but not statistics significant. The Sport Education model demonstrates its

reliability to improve health-related fitness markers (PACER, push-ups, and sit-ups) and BMI for active and passive roles with fitness contents in elementary schools. The selection or assignation of SE (active or passive) roles during the affiliation phase will not negatively impact fitness tests results. Despite students BMI classifications or gender physical educators should consider switching roles during the season to provide SE extended benefits.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Sport Education Roles, Health-related Fitness Markers, Edu-CrossFit

THE URGENCY OF NOW: INCLUSION OF HEALTH LITERACY INTO COLLEGE CURRICULUM

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Preparing learners for the industry is of the utmost importance in colleges and universities. While it is essential to provide administrative and clinical education/training within health programs, it is vital to ensure that learners know the health literacy levels of the population they serve and that they work to improve the population's health literacy levels. Older adults, people with limited education, and people from disadvantaged backgrounds have higher rates of low health literacy. These adults need help understanding and using health information containing jargon and technical words. People with low and limited levels of health literacy globally have a harder time understanding health information delivered in English. It is important to note that while much health literacy research is occurring in developed countries, more research still needs to be done in developing countries. Populations in developing countries tend to be low-income, primarily leading to lower reading skills and, thus, low health literacy equating to poorer health outcomes. Research shows that improvements in health literacy result in decreased emergency room visits, increased patient satisfaction, and better health outcomes. Properly training undergraduate students about the importance of health literacy is vital. This training should also incorporate the importance of local cultural beliefs and customs. Institutions that commit to training on health literacy, implicit bias, and health equity will better prepare students for social impact. This session highlights the importance and benefits of incorporating health literacy training into an undergraduate program. Improving health literacy can decrease health inequities and improve health disparities throughout the globe.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Health Literacy, Undergraduate Education, Equity

DISEÑO Y EVALUACIÓN DE UN PLAN DE EDUCACIÓN PARA LA SALUD SOBRE EL CONOCIMIENTO DEL VIRUS DEL PAPILOMA HUMANO (HPV)

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Según estimaciones de la OMS, más de un millón de personas contraen una ETS cada día. La OMS estima que en 2016 hubo alrededor de 376 millones de nuevas infecciones por una de estas cuatro ETS: Clamidia (127 millones), gonorrea (87 millones), sífilis (6,3 millones) y tricomoniasis (156 millones). El número de personas con infección genital por el virus HSV (herpes) supera los 500 millones y hay más de 300 millones de mujeres infectadas por el VPH, principal causante del cáncer de cuello uterino. Alrededor de 240 millones de personas padecen hepatitis B crónica. Tanto el herpes genital como la hepatitis B pueden prevenirse mediante la vacunación. (OMS 2019). La situación epidemiológica mundial en Europa es muy difícil por varios aspectos: la forma asintomática de muchas de estas patologías, el estigma social asociado a las mismas que hace que en muchos casos las personas no busquen atención sanitaria, las dificultades especialmente en los países en desarrollo, la mala implementación de los sistemas de vigilancia en los países más afectados y la falta de homogeneidad de los sistemas de vigilancia (OMC 2011). Por tanto, las infecciones de transmisión sexual constituyen un grupo de enfermedades de gran importancia por su impacto en la calidad de vida de los ciudadanos. Por ello, el objetivo de esta propuesta es el diseño de un programa de salud para dar conocimientos a la población sobre las enfermedades de transmisión sexual y principalmente sobre el Virus del

papiloma humano (HPV) y permitir una adecuada toma de decisiones. El objetivo específico del programa es crear hábitos de auto cuidado y auto responsabilidad en las personas mediante un programa de educación para la salud (Eps) basándose en el conocimiento de las enfermedades de transmisión sexual y, principalmente, en las conductas de riesgo vinculadas al virus del papiloma humano (HPV). Concretamente se pretende formar a la población en el uso adecuado de métodos para la contención de una pandemia imparable que se está viviendo actualmente y considerada ya endémica. El programa va dirigido a mujeres de un centro de salud de hasta 65 años, aunque podrán acudir todas las que estén interesadas, independientemente de si tienen pareja o no, mediante un tratamiento multidisciplinar donde participan diferentes agentes de formación: médicos, psicólogos, farmacéuticos, matronas, enfermeras etc. Por tanto, la metodología será colaborativa y activa mediante dinámicas de grupo que permitan la concienciación de las situaciones de riesgo y la asunción de nuevos hábitos. Para la consolidación de conocimientos, habilidades y actitudes se utilizarán herramientas como el ChatGPT3 o la realización de videos en TIK TOK, entre otros, con el fin de que las propias participantes en el programa se conviertan en generadoras de contenido y trasladen la información dentro de su ámbito comunitario. Por tanto, la tarea educativa consistirá en la realización de un programa de difusión comunitario para informar a la sociedad sobre conductas de riesgo en relación a las enfermedades de transmisión sexual. Para la evaluación del impacto del programa se utilizará una metodología mixta mediante procedimientos cualitativos y cuantitativos y un diseño pretest-postest. Se hará especial hincapié en la evaluación formativa para evitar la consolidación de conocimientos erróneos y aumentar el nivel de motivación de las participantes. Se pondrá particular atención en el seguimiento individualizado de las participantes para conocer las dificultades y su nivel de satisfacción con el programa. Se pretende con ello evitar la pérdida de asistentes que habitualmente se produce en este tipo de programas y aumentar la adherencia al mismo.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Enfermedades de transmisión sexual (ETS), Prevención, Educación para la salud (Eps), Virus del papiloma humano (HPV)

EFICACIA DE PROGRAMAS DE EDUCACIÓN POSTURAL EN EL ÁMBITO EDUCATIVO: UNA REVISIÓN SISTEMÁTICA

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

El objetivo principal de esta revisión sistemática es establecer el estado de la cuestión de las intervenciones sobre educación postural en el ámbito educativo. A lo largo de este proceso, se ha consultado la literatura más reciente relativa a programas de educación postural en la educación formal y sobre la incidencia del mal endémico que estas intervenciones de alfabetización en salud tratan de paliar: las dolencias de espalda relacionadas con la postura. El dolor de espalda y, concretamente, el dolor lumbar está considerado como un importante problema de salud pública en España, que afecta considerablemente a la calidad de vida de las personas e incrementa el gasto en servicios sanitarios. El sistema educativo es uno de los principales motores de promoción de la salud. La inclusión de la educación postural, como contenido de la educación para la Salud, está plenamente justificada en el proceso de formación del alumnado. Esta revisión sistemática responde a un diseño descriptivo retrospectivo, para el cual se utilizó el método PRISMA para la búsqueda en las bases de datos Scopus y Web Of Science. Se han revisado un total de 61 artículos originales relacionados con programas de educación postural en el ámbito educativo, estudios de diseño y validación de cuestionarios de salud, aplicabilidad de dispositivos electrónicos en el análisis de la postura y estudios de prevalencia y factores de riesgo de

dolencias de espalda vinculadas a la postura. Los resultados de dichas intervenciones demuestran la eficacia y los beneficios obtenidos a través de la implementación de programas de educación para la salud de la espalda en el ámbito de la educación formal. Se hace necesaria la realización de más estudios relacionados con intervenciones didácticas de promoción de la salud de la espalda en el ámbito educativo y que incluyan muestras de alumnos suficientemente amplias.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Educación postural, Alfabetización en salud, Espalda

DOMESTIC VIOLENCE ON WOMEN IN NEPALESE FAMILIES

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Purpose: The purpose of this study is to present domestic violence existing on women in Nepalese families and societies. Although people are educated, domestic violence on women is not minimized and appears in many families as before. So, this study aims to show social inequality in terms of gender. Taking these points into consideration, the purpose of this study is to present the existing discrimination and domestic violence on women in Nepalese families and societies. This research study also shows that patriarchal families and societies are extremely dominating women.

Design/ Methodology/ Approach: Furthermore, regarding methodology, this is a qualitative study and data are collected through interview and document analysis. This is an ethnographic design under qualitative study. The study maintains convenience sampling under purposive sampling related to qualitative study. A woman fallen victim of domestic violence will be identified and interviewed and through her another woman of similar category is identified to interview and collect data. The data analysis process is interpretive. The data are collected and interpreted by using language but no other statistical tools are used.

Findings: Nepal is a small country situated between two large countries, China and India. Nepal is surrounded by China in the northern part and by India in the eastern, southern and western parts. So, the lifestyle of the people in the northern part of Nepal is like that of the Tibetan tribes; and similarly, the lifestyle of the people in eastern, southern and western part is similar to that of Indian people. It is also found that there is less domestic violence on women among northern communities; and there is a high level of domestic violence of women in many other parts of the country. The findings of this study show that society has not taken responsibility to control discrimination and domestic violence taken place on women. This is an unsolved social responsibility.

Research Limitations: This research study is ethnography in research design so that it does not cover more aspects of male population. And also it is a qualitative study and does not point out any statistical tools and numerical data.

Managerial Implications: The implications of this research are that women need equality in family and society, maintaining a humanistic view for women and implications for further research.

Originality/ Value: This research study has maintained its originality and it has also got great value. The delimitation of this study is that it concerns within discrimination and domestic violence of women in families and societies. The findings of this study show that women are highly/ mercilessly discriminated against and have been victim to death through domestic violence; this situation has been an unsolved challenge in Nepalese families and societies.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Patriarchal Society, Discrimination, Domestic Violence, Oppression of Women, Social Practices

ANALYSIS OF THE FUNCTIONS OF THE SCHOOL NURSE THROUGH INTERNATIONAL LEGISLATION

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

In recent years, the concept of health literacy has gained great importance in Europe, due to the implications it has in the acquisition of healthy habits, with the consequent benefit for society. Various definitions of the concept of health literacy have been used, the most widely used definition currently being that offered by the HLS-EU consortium, indicating that HL "is linked to literacy and entails people's knowledge, motivation and competences to access, understand, appraise, and apply health information in order to make judgments and take decisions in everyday life concerning healthcare, disease prevention and health promotion to maintain or improve quality of life during the life course". The school, being the place where children and adolescents spend more time (after their home), is the ideal place for this acquisition of healthy habits, as has been demonstrated through the projects of schools that promote health. Therefore, the involvement of health agents in the school is necessary: the teacher and the school nurse. Through various studies, the low level of health literacy among teachers has been verified, despite the fact that knowledge of health promotion and acquisition of healthy habits is presented in the curriculum of various subjects. These training deficiencies mean that some teachers consider the incorporation of the figure of the school nurse to be a priority for the SA of the entire educational community. The state of the question lies in the fact that despite the

importance given to this health agent by groups and associations, currently in our country we do not have our own state legislation that regulates and indicates the functions of the school nurse, being her figure relegated to private, concerted and special education centers, only having legislation on her figure in the Community of Madrid and in the Valencian Community. The main objective of this work is to analyze and compare the existing legislation in Spain and abroad on the functions of the school nurse. The secondary objective is the realization of a proposal on the competences of the school nurse in Galicia. In order to achieve this objective, a content analysis of the legislative documents of the main countries in our environment at an international level (France, Poland, England, Scotland, USA, Australia, Japan, Argentina, among others) will be carried out. a comparison between the competencies assigned by each of them to the school nurse and the competencies defined by the general nursing council of our country. The main conclusions of this work focus on the need to design legislation at the state and regional level that determines the importance and competencies related to the school nurse. At the same time, we advocate the need for continuous training of teachers in health literacy that allows both coping with different health situations that occur in educational centres, as well as designing the training processes of their students in order for them to make appropriate decisions. in health based on empirical evidence.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

School Nurse, Health Literacy, School Health, Teachers, Competences

SOCIAL SUPPORT AND SELF-ESTEEM IN WOMEN ATHLETES

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Female athletes are under a lot of pressure and stress. The purpose of this study was to determine whether perceived social support is related to self-esteem and the type of sport performed by elite female athletes. A cross-sectional observational study was conducted. A sample of 243 Spanish elite female athletes in different individual and group sports with a mean age of 23.89 years. They completed the questionnaire for the evaluation of perceived social support (Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support). The results show that the greatest social support for high-performance sportswomen is family. The social support of the family and the group of friends has an impact on their self-esteem. In addition, it is highlighted that high-performance female athletes who practice team sports versus those who practice individual sports have higher self-esteem and perceive friends as their main social support.

Family social support is a predictor of self-esteem in Spanish elite athletes.

Given the importance of self-perceived social support for physical and mental health and stress management in athletes, it would be important to establish prevention programs that include psychological and social resources so that athletes perceive the necessary social support to avoid stress and anxiety situations.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Sport, Woman, Performance, Self-esteem, Social Support

DEPORTE COMO VEHÍCULO DE DESARROLLO E INCLUSIÓN SOCIAL DESDE LA PERSPECTIVA DE LOS GESTORES

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

En la última década un gran número de académicos y profesionales han dedicado importantes esfuerzos para contribuir al desarrollo de teoría y práctica alrededor del uso del deporte para la promoción de los Objetivos de Desarrollo Sostenible (ODS). La literatura sostiene que es necesario identificar y constatar de forma empírica la contribución única del deporte para lograr un impacto hacia el desarrollo humano de colectivo en riesgo social. En este sentido, el deporte es una herramienta educativa con un gran potencial, especialmente en colectivos desfavorecidos en los que también resulta tener un fuerte carácter integrador. Uno de los principales motivos es que la mayoría de la población mundial está dispuesta a realizar deporte, entendido este como juegos, de forma que resulta fácil estimular la participación de un gran número de personas de forma sencilla. Además, el deporte o la práctica de actividad física o el juego, si se organiza de forma correcta y se orientada adecuadamente, facilita la transmisión de valores adecuados y deseados, aunque es necesario trabajar de forma intencionada este aspecto para que la relación sea positiva. Para su estimulación se deben diseñar planes de investigación sistematizados que proporcionen las condiciones en las cuales una programación eficaz y medición del impacto del uso del deporte como herramienta educativa en comunidades vulnerables. Se ha resaltado la importancia de escuchar y empoderar a colegas de países de ingresos bajos y medios para que sus voces contribuyan a la construcción de teoría, práctica sólida y contextualizada. La mayoría de los trabajos se han centrado en regiones

geográficas particulares -África, Asia, Oceanía- aunque en América Latina, el Caribe y España se ha utilizado como catalizador aún hay limitada comprensión entre la comunidad general sobre cómo el deporte puede ser una plataforma viable para alcanzar objetivos sociales más amplios. Esto resalta la oportunidad e interés de impulsar estudios que contribuyan significativamente al cuerpo del conocimiento respecto a su uso como base de programas de intervención comunitaria -construcción de paz, resolución de conflictos, educación de calidad, igualdad de género, acción por el clima, bienestar y salud- que utilicen estándares científicos para medir su contribución en los participantes en tiempo y espacio. En este estudio se han analizado, desde un enfoque etnográfico mediante entrevistas semiestructuradas en profundidad, dos experiencias (Fundación Colombianitos y Fundación Tiempo de Juego) que permiten determinar las razones que tienen los gestores de estas para intervenir en poblaciones en riesgo social utilizando el deporte como vehículo de transformación e inclusión social. Entre las principales conclusiones podemos señalar que los jóvenes en riesgo que están familiarizados con el ámbito deportivo promueven la integración social entre los participantes de una forma lúdica y minimiza diferenciadores como la cultura, raza, credo o nivel socioeconómico. Además, los implicados mejoran su capacidad de trabajar en equipo y forman un sentido de pertenencia.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Desarrollo, Deporte, Intervención Comunitaria, Inclusión, Derechos Humanos

Lenguaje Emocional sobre Situaciones Vividas Intensamente: Conflicto y Perdón

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Uno de los procesos fundamentales en la comunicación con otros seres humanos es la selección de las palabras para transmitir el significado adecuado a aquello que queremos comunicar (Vogt et al., 2022). Este proceso no solo se realiza de manera planificada, sino que las palabras también muestran vínculos directos con la actitud del hablante ante la situación (Braun et al., 2019). El perdón desempeña un papel clave en esta actitud ante las relaciones interpersonales (Klimecki, 2019). Sin embargo, aunque los aspectos emocionales de la comprensión del lenguaje han sido profundamente estudiados, se sabe muy poco sobre su expresión (Hinojosa et al., 2010; Rohr & Rahman, 2018) y sobre su relación con otros procesos cognitivos.

Para desentrañar el papel del perdón sobre el lenguaje utilizado para relatar situaciones de mayor y menor conflicto, el presente trabajo analiza 83 relatos libres producidos por 45 estudiantes de la Universidade de Vigo. Se analizó la gravedad de la situación y la medida en la que habían perdonado a aquella persona mediante el Cuestionario EPEC (Rosales, 2021) y el Inventario EFI-30 (versión en castellano). Además, se tomaron los verbos principales de los relatos para obtener la medida del lenguaje utilizado y se codificaron sus características emocionales a partir de Stadthagen-Gonzalez et al. (2017).

Las situaciones de conflicto y no conflicto se diferenciaron tanto en la emocionalidad de los verbos escogidos para relatarlas ($F_{1,76} = 39.85$; $p < .001$ para la valencia; y $F_{1,76} = 8.38$; $p = .005$ para la intensidad) como en el nivel de perdón de la otra persona ($F_{1,76} = 44.59$; $p < .001$). Además, los resultados mostraron una relación negativa y significativa entre el perdón y la gravedad percibida de la situación ($r = -0.53$; $p < .001$), sugiriendo importantes implicaciones del impulso del perdón para el desescalamiento del conflicto interpersonal.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Lenguaje, Conflicto, Perdón, Valencia, Intensidad

INTERCONNECTING TEACHING SPACES WITH COMPASSION THROUGH MINDFUL INNOVATIVE PRACTICES

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Knowledge is conceived to be an empowering experience, which helps the person as well as society to realize their goals. In order to overcome suffering there have been deep meditative practices and spiritual teachers (Gurus) in the Indian tradition. The vast expanse of India has experienced spiritual Masters' of the like of Buddha, Ramana Maharishi, Paramhansa Yogananda, Aadi Shankaracharya, Swami Vivekananda, Swami Sivananda, Jiddu Krishnamurti, Sri Aurobindo, Mata Amritananda Mayi and many more.

Today, there are deliberations to offer happiness, joy, mindfulness as practices integrated in the pedagogical discourse. His Holiness, the Dalai Lama has spread the message of compassion and joy amongst the world. The Zen Master- Thich Nhat Hanh's Philosophy & Practice has a clear focus on mindfulness. Eckhart Tolle has given the mantra of 'Be Present'. All of these Masters are today leading the world towards liberation and realization of our true self. This realization is an end to all worldly suffering.

Yet, our educators are stressed. The stressors that the teachers carry with them to the schools permeates through the classroom exchange to the students, which doubles the stress. Today, there is an urgent need to work in the direction of mental well being especially for school teachers and students. Mindfulness training (MT) has emerged as a useful and tested means to support educators in terms of their emotional coping skills, mental health status, stress reduction and working motivation. There is ample evidence that substantiates the effectiveness of Mindfulness-based intervention (MBI) in alleviating stress, promoting well-being, resiliency and building social-emotional competence, which in turn contributes to higher efficacy in teaching processes.

Collective Teacher Efficiency (CTE), as part of the general teacher efficacy, has recently risen to eminence as it is reported as the second most influential variable associated with student achievement. In the context of professional training (PT), numerous studies have also shown a positive relationship between teacher's professional learning (TPL) and CTE. The teachers' participation in MT is posited to have a positive effect on teachers' well-being and social emotional competence. In turn, teachers' wellbeing is related to effective classroom management, positive interpersonal climate and positive teacher-student relationship. The effects will eventually trickle down to students' social, emotional and academic performance.

Statistics have shown over time that teaching is one of the most stressful occupations. Approximately 40% of the teachers left their position for the first five years of their career in the United States as per some statistics . Challenges for teachers include administrative burdens, lack of emotional support, long working hours, class management difficulties, teacher-student relationship, to name a few. Also, the lack of time for teachers to collaborate with their co-workers to solve students' problems together has posed more stress on their job. The poor well-being of teachers can in turn have negative effects on students in classroom engagement, reduce student self-efficacy and diminish teaching effectiveness

The anecdotes and narratives of teachers who participated in a drama and mindfulness module will be shared as part of this paper. The findings compel the teacher training programs to integrate Drama Mindfulness Training (DMT) programs for the mental wellbeing of teachers and students. The DMT programs will ensure high quality classroom interactions, social emotional competence of students and high performance in an enriched classroom climate.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Mindfulness, Mental Wellbeing, Teaching Efficacy, Creative Drama, Compassion

ESTRATEGIAS Y POLÍTICAS PARA CONTRARRESTAR EL DISCURSO DEL ODIIO EN LA EDUCACIÓN

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

La Educación formal juega un papel fundamental en edades tempranas como vía para el entendimiento y el respeto para una convivencia pacífica. Aunque existen desafíos y obstáculos, el ecosistema escolar se presenta como un territorio propicio para gestionar el respeto a la diferencia, fomentar el intercambio cultural y el conocimiento mutuo. La heterogeneidad del alumnado no debe ser vista como una debilidad, sino como una fortaleza del Sistema Educativo. Sin embargo, es necesario superar creencias peyorativas, mejorar los planes de estudio, la financiación y la formación del profesorado para afrontar la diversidad en el aula y los conflictos que puedan surgir. Aunque queda mucho por hacer, la educación se erige como el motor principal para abordar estos desafíos. Se trata de un modelo pedagógico basado en el respeto a la diversidad, que reconoce las necesidades y potencialidades de cada estudiante y se esfuerza por proporcionar un entorno de aprendizaje que promueva su pleno desarrollo académico, social y emocional. Ello implica la eliminación de barreras y la adopción de prácticas pedagógicas flexibles y adaptativas, así como la promoción de una cultura de respeto, tolerancia y aceptación de la diferencia en toda la comunidad educativa para construir un futuro común en el que se respeten los derechos humanos, se promueva la igualdad y se fomente la convivencia pacífica en la sociedad. Por ello, es crucial que desde el Sistema Educativo se aborden los desafíos y retos que las dinámicas sociales imponen. En un mundo globalizado como en el que vivimos, las migraciones hacia territorios occidentales suponen nuevos desafíos para los países de acogida. La búsqueda de mejores oportunidades de vida y factores como la falta de perspectivas laborales en los países de origen, las situaciones de guerra y la persecución, son, entre otras, las principales causas de estos flujos migratorios los cuales han transformado la sociedad española y plantean la necesidad de afrontar con medidas educativas la

diversidad cultural y lingüística que traen consigo los migrantes. Los nuevos escenarios sociales suponen nuevos retos educativos debido, entre otras causas, a los discursos de odio que proliferan de una manera incontrolada desde las redes sociales a los medios de comunicación e Internet en general y que se materializan en el día a día del centro escolar. Los estudios académicos realizados sobre el discurso del odio se centran sobre todo en el Derecho, la Psicología, la Comunicación, etc. pero no tanto en el mundo educativo. Nuestro objetivo principal es realizar una revisión del desarrollo y estado actual de la investigación sobre el Discurso del Odio y proponer posibles prácticas y estrategias para contrarrestar la proliferación de esta nueva pandemia.

En este sentido, la educación inclusiva se vuelve esencial para atender las necesidades del alumnado y evitar situaciones de discriminación reforzando el sentido de la convivencia pacífica en los centros educativos. La igualdad de oportunidades, basada en la solidaridad y la participación escolar, debe ser promovida y reforzada para garantizar una vida plena a todos los estudiantes. Para ello, utilizaremos una metodología cualitativa para analizar los documentos académicos publicados hasta el momento actual incidiendo en la necesidad de garantizar el acceso a una enseñanza gratuita y de calidad, eliminar las desigualdades en el ámbito educativo y luchar contra el racismo y la discriminación en las escuelas.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Educación Formal, Inclusión, Comunidad Educativa, Racismo, Convivencia Pacífica

WHAT ADOLESCENTS EAT AND ITS RELATIONSHIP WITH A SUSTAINABLE FOOD PATTERN, THE MEDITERRANEAN DIET

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The aim of this research is to understand how adolescents eat nowadays, to analyze the nutritional adequacy of their eating habits and establish a comparison with a sustainable food pattern like the Mediterranean Diet. The methodology is based on (1) the review of publications on adolescents eating habits published in the last years, studies made with adolescents aged between 10 and 19 years old will be included; (2) the comparison of the eating habits with the nutritional guidelines available for adolescents. Finally, (3) a comparison with the adolescent's food habits and the Mediterranean Diet guidelines, regarding sustainability, will be made. The main expected results include how adolescents consume insufficient amounts of fruit, vegetables, pulses and whole grains, while they have an excessive intake of animal products (such as meat and dairy products) and processed foods rich in sugar such as cakes, biscuits and soft drinks. This food pattern has led to the increase in the prevalence of obesity observed in most developed countries. At the same time, the adolescent's food habits observed aren't sustainable due to the amount of animal products and processed products consumed. In conclusion, the nutritional adequacy of current adolescents' eating habits must be improved to preserve their present and future health, as well as reduce the impact on the environment.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Nutrition, Adolescents, Sustainable Eating, Mediterranean Diet

THE PERCEPTIONS OF HEALTH PROFESSIONALS REGARDING THE PARTICIPATION OF MEN IN ANTENATAL CARE: A DELPHI STUDY WITH NURSES IN MOZAMBIQUE

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Antenatal care is the medical monitoring of pregnant women during pregnancy and it plays a key role in the prevention and early detection of maternal and fetal pathologies. The participation of men in antenatal care is extremely important because it improves maternal and newborn health outcomes as men provide their partners emotional and financial support. In addition, men are considered as “decision makers”, being so, their involvement in antenatal care can reduce the maternal mortality. Despite the importance of the participation of men in antenatal care, many studies show that men experience many barriers to accessing antenatal care, including less access to HIV testing and family planning services. The aim of this research is to assess the perceptions of the maternal and child health professionals regarding the participation of men in antenatal care at Nhaconjo Health Center in Beira City, Mozambique. This will be a cross-sectional study with a qualitative approach using a Delphi study consisting of three (3) rounds of questionnaires. In the first round, information will be collected from the maternal and child health professionals through an open-ended questionnaire in order to obtain a list of different perspectives regarding the participation of men in antenatal care at Nhaconjo Health Center. The second and third rounds will be used to reach consensus among the participants through a closed-ended questionnaire. There will be 21 maternal and child health professionals involved in the study. The results of this research will contribute to the production of knowledge for the scientific community, intervention developers and the health professionals with special reference to nurses who deal with the maternal and child health programs. Based on the results of this study, interventions can be developed that aim to increase men’s participation in antenatal care and in other services such as family planning and HIV testing. The

participation of men in antenatal care can substantially improve men's adherence to family planning programs and reduce the risk of HIV transmission incidences. Therefore, health care providers, specifically maternal and child health nurses, in antenatal care play an important role in counseling men and their partners about the importance of antenatal care.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Antenatal Care, Men, Maternal and Child Health Nurses

USO DE LOS MEDIOS DE COMUNICACIÓN PARA PROMOVER EL ENVEJECIMIENTO ACTIVO

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

El objetivo de esta investigación es el de impactar positivamente la calidad de vida de las personas mayores y promover el envejecimiento activo. Para ello, se generó un programa de radio para interconectar a la población mayor diseminada en una autonomía principalmente rural. El objetivo fue llegar precozmente a los domicilios de las personas mayores a través de un programa aparentemente de compañía que se diseñó para instalar conceptos claves en el envejecimiento activo y promover el desarrollo de conductas saludables. El programa estaba apoyado por una serie de interacciones con los auditores a través de WhatsApp, Instagram y YouTube. De forma tal de estimular el uso de estas tecnologías en el repertorio conductual de nuestros mayores. Se diseñó una estructura sencilla basada en el recordatorio de músicas emblemáticas de la época juvenil de quienes estaban sobre los 60 años de edad, todas en inglés italiano o francés para instalar el uso de un segundo lenguaje en forma lúdica, sustentado en las emociones de placer y alegría al recordar temas emblemáticos de los años 50/60. Además, el programa permitía que las personas mayores pudieran participar llamando directamente o enviando audios vía WhatsApp, comentando el desarrollo del programa y actividades propias de su devenir. Luego se desarrollaron concursos de memoria para recordar eventos específicos en la historia de la televisión, el cine o la literatura., dando la oportunidad para que hicieran presente sus recuerdos más importantes y su historiografía en torno a esta temática. Luego en cada programa se terminaba con una entrevista a un especialista de la Universidad Pontificia de Salamanca, Universidad Miguel Hernández, Universidad pública de Navarra y otras de Chile en envejecimiento activo y vida saludable, generando preguntas de interés previamente socializadas con el público y cuidadosamente elegidas conforme a una estrategia intencionada por el equipo de producción para estimular desafíos personales

asociados al autocuidado, el desarrollo de conductas saludables y la estimulación temprana de funciones superiores como la memoria y la asociación de ideas. El programa duró 4 meses y luego se realizó una encuesta telefónica para establecer evidencia respecto de la mejoría de la calidad de vida como consecuencia de confirmaron el propósito de esta estrategia comunicacional en orden a promover el envejecimiento activo en la población. Se evidenció la conveniencia de usar estrategias amigables y lúdicas para llegar a la población de personas a mayores e impactar positivamente en el desarrollo de conductas responsables de autocuidado asociadas al envejecimiento activo y el uso de las TIC como puede de comunicación y soporte de información.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Envejecimiento activo, Reminiscencias, TIC, Intervención Social

PROGRAMA DE SALUD MATERNAL PARA GESTANTES DE RIESGO DURANTE SU INGRESO HOSPITALARIO

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Las gestantes de alto y muy alto riesgo suelen tener episodios de hospitalización durante la gestación de mayor o menor duración dependiendo de la gravedad. Estos episodios hacen que, en la mayoría de los casos, no se pueda llevar a cabo el seguimiento habitual de la gestación recogido en la “Consulta preconcepcional e de atención ao embarazo normal. Proceso asistencial” del Servicio Gallego de Salud. Además, las mujeres implicadas no pueden realizar ningún tipo de educación prenatal. La educación maternal (EM) incluye una serie de medidas educativas y de apoyo que ayudan a la gestante y su pareja a comprender sus propias necesidades sociales, emocionales, psicológicas y físicas durante el embarazo, el trabajo del parto y los cuidados relativos al puerperio. Teniendo en cuenta que estas mujeres se van a enfrentar a un embarazo, parto y posparto con unas connotaciones especiales, dada su patología gestacional, se debe tener en cuenta esta situación y tratar de subsanarla desarrollando programas específicos para las gestantes de alto/muy alto riesgo durante su ingreso hospitalario. Por ello, el objetivo de esta propuesta consiste en el diseño de un programa de salud para este colectivo, que facilite el acceso y comprensión a conocimientos específicos y facilite la toma de decisiones adecuadas, proporcionando un mayor grado de satisfacción en todo el proceso y previniendo situaciones no deseadas. Se llevará a cabo el diseño de un programa específico para mujeres ingresadas con estas circunstancias, adaptado a las necesidades de las gestantes. La metodología utilizada será activa y se utilizarán medios educativos directos como la charla, la discusión en grupo y clases prácticas de resolución de problemas, e indirectos como medios visuales o sonoros. Los principales

resultados esperados se relacionan con la obtención de una mayor satisfacción en el proceso de embarazo, parto y puerperio de las gestantes de alto/muy alto riesgo. Asimismo, se espera un aumento en los conocimientos y habilidades relacionadas con la salud materna, de forma que el programa haya proporcionado herramientas para poder afrontar con éxito las posibles variaciones de la normalidad en su proceso gestacional. El campo de acción de la educación para la salud es toda la colectividad, independientemente de las circunstancias personales que puedan afectar en un momento determinado a la población. Por tanto, desde las instituciones se debe hacer un esfuerzo por poner el foco de atención también en este colectivo, atendiendo a la diversidad y favoreciendo el mejor estado de salud posible tanto en ellas como en sus bebés.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Diseño de programas, Educación maternal, Alfabetización en salud

V

INTERNATIONALIZATION AND COMMUNICATION

EDUCATION AS DISCOVERY: FOSTERING AGENCY THROUGH NARRATIVE EXPLORATIONS

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

As higher education demands students to become more advanced in reading, writing and research, educators can foster students' social voice and intellectual agency by letting them connect the personal with the social. When students encounter new genres and disciplines, they are not only intimidated by complex conventions and expectations; developing agency also requires them to "perform" new roles as writers and researchers, in the sense of role playing. To facilitate this process of meeting new challenges and assuming new roles with agency, as a teacher, I help my students take ownership of their ideas and find agency and voice in their own stories/experiences. In my presentation, I use what I call "discovery narratives" in order to illustrate how sharing personal stories while also exploring social issues in them can help achieve the above learning/teaching objectives in my classroom with a diverse student population with different socio-economic and linguistic backgrounds. Discovery narratives are personal stories whose social themes or implications students explore through research and reading, discussion and critique. I use discovery narratives as a launching-pad assignment in my first-year writing and undergraduate seminar courses. I usually begin the process by assigning "Family Narratives in Multiple Literacies," by Concha Delgado-Gaitan, which highlights how sharing narratives help families across borders to connect, communicate, share, and act as they strive for social justice and mobility. Because many of my students come from challenging and diverse social backgrounds, they relate well to narratives exploring social issues, thereby realizing how education can help "disenfranchised people exercis[e] their voice--[appreciating] actions that contribute to a larger picture of what democracy and social justice are about" (271). The assignment validates and taps into students' knowledge and interests,

inspiring them to discuss, research, read, and write about issues they care about while also helping them develop themes and arguments in their own voices as they develop confidence and critical academic skills. I will share cases of students exploring broader socio-cultural, political, economic, and educational issues by studying and writing about their own experiences at home and in the community or school. I will also share a list of annotated bibliographies of the readings to show how these readings (which are more interdisciplinary or transnational) encourage my students to view the issues from different angles. I will conclude by highlighting the significance of agency in performance especially in the difficult political times that we inhabit, prompting the audience to share their strategies toward achieving the goals of writing education that I share.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Education, Narrative Exploration, Discovery Narratives, Agency

IMBEDDING MYSTERY, GROWING CURIOSITY: ACTION RESEARCH IN AN ARABIC FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSROOM

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The internationalization of higher education will undoubtedly encompass an array of activities, pedagogies, and strategies. One well-established area of international education is world language education, or the promotion of bilingualism among students. This will be particularly important among predominantly English-speaking countries whose citizens, by virtue of the global dominance of English, remain internationally isolated and interculturally less aware, like the U.S. Arabic foreign language pedagogy remains relatively new to the educational landscape of North America. As such, its methods and materials will continue to develop. This was the aim of one instructor's action research project within his Beginning Arabic (MSA) course within a U.S. university. Learners were predominantly African-American undergraduates with no prior experience of Arabic learning. Drawing from *Learning that Sticks: A brain-based model for K-12 instructional design and delivery* by Goodwin, Gibson, and Rouleau, the project aimed to, "tap into (learners) natural sense of curiosity" (p. 26). To improve learners' cognition of Arabic vocab, the project experimented with four strategies to pique curiosity: to involve either mystery, cognitive conflict, suspense, or guessing-and-receiving-feedback (p. 27-28). Using materials adapted to embed these strategies, this project implemented the lessons. These lessons were intermixed with standard, unmodified lessons (control). To explore students' perceptions of their cognition and curiosity, a simple post-intervention questionnaire was administered after each lesson (of both modified and unmodified materials). Results will be determined and shared within this presentation, as will the full set of materials utilized. Ultimately, scholarship on Arabic language pedagogy, second language acquisition will most directly benefit. For attendees uninterested in language acquisition, this

presentation offers four strategies to enhance any type of learning by maximizing learners' curiosity. Application within any learning context -beyond language acquisition- is possible. It is this type of action research, of thoughtful creativity, that will help transform our teaching, making the education we provide more engaging, and thus produce more engaged, effective students. On the micro-level, in the minutiae of the classroom, is where focused attention can produce the greatest impact. Action research aligns well with incremental, classroom-tested pedagogies rather than educational revolutions. Moreover, it is led by instructors. Further action research, in wider contexts, should be encouraged and shared! This project was developed as a capstone for the professional development training for instructors of critical language entitled "Engaging All Learners Through Brain-Based Strategies". The program ran from March through October 2023, operated through the Concordia Language Villages in Minnesota and was made possible by a StarTalk grant, funded by the U.S. government.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Arabic, Action Research, Curiosity, Cognitive Conflict, Mystery

HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHERS' AWARENESS TOWARDS DIVERSITY AND INCLUSION COMPETENCIES: AN EXPLORATORY SURVEY

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Diversity management education and inclusive learning environments became subjects of research interest more than 20 years ago. However, the focus was largely on pre-university students or on general guidance in education, higher university field being somehow neglected. Competencies related to diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI) are needed especially in teaching multicultural groups in international degree programs in higher education. The current paper aims to identify the level of awareness of higher education teachers from GLOBDIVES partner universities regarding the importance of introducing DEI topics into the curriculum, and their corresponding perceived level of knowledge and skills. A survey on university teachers was conducted, using scales developed according to different frameworks found into literature review. Preliminary results of the quantitative research showing the differences and similarities among respondents are presented, together with some recommendations regarding the development of higher education teachers' diversity and inclusion competencies.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Higher Education, Diversity, Equity, Inclusion, DEI, Teachers' Awareness

RELIGIÓN Y GUERRA EN LA GRECIA ANTIGUA: RITUALES EN LA BATALLA. UNA PERSPECTIVA INTERCULTURAL

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

En la Grecia Antigua, las divinidades estaban por encima de lo puramente humano y ejercían su dominio, prácticamente ilimitado, sobre los mortales. La vida de los humanos estaba marcada por su relación con las divinidades, tanto en el plano público, como privado. En este artículo se analiza la imbricación de las divinidades en la vida de los individuos a través del caso concreto de la guerra, aportando ejemplos que ponen de manifiesto que los guerreros no siempre eran responsables de su desenlace, ni de lo que ocurría en su transcurso. No cumplir con los rituales y las normas de la guerra, no solo suponía la reprobación de la sociedad, sino también la de las divinidades, que no dudaban en castigar severamente las transgresiones. Veremos cómo las fuentes literarias evidencian la estricta y constante ritualización de todas y cada una de las pautas de la guerra y que la conexión con los dioses, a diferencia de la táctica y del armamento, permaneció invariable desde el siglo VIII a. C., momento que se considera que los poemas homéricos adquirieron su forma definitiva, hasta el siglo II d. C., época que refleja la obra de Pausanias.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Divinidades, Sacrificios, Oráculos, Santuarios, Sacerdotes, Trofeo

UNA EXPERIENCIA DE DEMOCRATIZACIÓN DE LA ENSEÑANZA DEL FRANCÉS, INGLÉS Y PORTUGUÉS EN ENTORNOS VIRTUALES: EL CASO DE IDIOMAS EN ELE

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

La siguiente presentación expone los resultados del primer año de implementación del programa virtual 'Idiomas en ELE' para la enseñanza de francés, inglés y portugués, impulsado por Subsecretaría de Planificación Del Sistema Educativo, Ciencia y Tecnología, a través del Ministerio de Educación, Cultura, Ciencia y Tecnología de la Provincia del Chaco. Este programa se desarrolla de manera remota, con modalidad sincrónica y asincrónica utilizando aulas virtuales Moodle en la Plataforma Educativa Chaqueña ELE' y encuentros por videoconferencia. El proyecto posibilita que niños y niñas de 5to a 7mo grado del nivel primario, como también jóvenes de 12 a 18 años del nivel secundario accedan a cursos vocacionales gratuitos de idiomas y, al aprobarlos, reciban una certificación ministerial. Esta experiencia evalúa el impacto del aprendizaje virtual según la perspectiva de los 366 estudiantes que finalizaron el curso durante el ciclo 2022. Tres aspectos resultaron fundamentales para obtener resultados cuantitativos y cualitativos: el uso de la tecnología, los materiales didácticos y el entorno social y afectivo de las clases virtuales. El análisis cuantitativo de las opiniones de los estudiantes reveló que mientras un 24% de los estudiantes de nivel primario manifestó que el uso de la plataforma Moodle les resultó accesible, ese porcentaje asciende a un 81% en el nivel secundario. La brecha entre niveles se torna inexistente cuanto se analiza la percepción de los estudiantes en cuanto a los materiales de estudio, alcanzando, en ambos casos, una apreciación positiva del 48%. Los análisis cualitativos de las encuestas de satisfacción revelan que, los estudiantes de ambos niveles valoran de manera primordial la posibilidad de aprender idiomas a través de recursos interactivos,

como por ejemplo gamificación, videos y cuestionarios. Los datos obtenidos de las encuestas realizadas a los cursantes señalan la importancia de los tutores en el acompañamiento y destacan el rol de los compañeros/amigos en el aprendizaje. Consideran que compartir entornos virtuales de manera interactiva, fomenta un clima de respeto y participación constantes. Es sumamente importante mencionar que los estudiantes reconocen la magnitud en términos socioeducativos que significa la oportunidad de tener acceso a cursos de idiomas gratuitos en localidades remotas de la provincia.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Idiomas, Entornos Virtuales, Gamificación, Comunicativo, Moodle

DIVERSITY AND GLOBAL CITIZENSHIP IN HIGHER EDUCATION: IS UNIVERSITY TRAINING CONTRIBUTING TO THEIR MASTERY?

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The study aims to describe the perception that students have about whether their university is raising awareness about the importance of training on diversity and global citizenship. It will also address its association with certain socio-demographic and academic variables in order to be able to introduce changes in university training programmes that respond to current demands on this subject.

A questionnaire was distributed to the students of five European universities and sent through their respective platforms.

The main features of the data were described using descriptive statistics, and the relationship between the variables was ascertained using Pearson's chi-square test. The findings enable us to confirm that a significant portion of students believe their university is promoting D&GC awareness, particularly in Romania. The university students who most frequently carry out D&GC training activities

are between 24 and 30 years old and live in Spain. In addition, a high percentage of students consider it important or very important for universities to conduct D&GC courses. Except for Finnish students who prefer an online format and German students who prefer a face-to-face style, residents of Romania, Lithuania, and Spain prefer these courses to have a hybrid structure.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Higher Education, Training, Diversity, Global Citizenship

MERITOCRACY: A REMEDY TO ADDRESSING SOCIAL INJUSTICES IN SELECTING STUDENTS TO PUBLIC HIGHER EDUCATION IN MALAWI?

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

This essay analyzes whether an ostensibly merit-based policy of selecting students to public higher education can act as a remedy to ameliorate social injustices in Malawi's education system. We address this question through the lens of equity based on a broader discussion of ethnicity in Malawi. The paper is organized in the following sections. First, we provide an overview of the geography of Malawi. This is followed by a detailed review of the literature on the education system focusing on access and equity between the predecessor quota system and the current merit-based policy. The article concludes by arguing that merit-based policy is very likely to perpetuate rather than ameliorate social injustices in education, as the future of students attending under-resourced schools is in jeopardy to access public higher education. Therefore, we strongly recommend that the Malawi government consider re-adopting the quota system, which if designed carefully could serve to address social injustices in access to higher education.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Meritocracy, Public Higher Education, Malawi, Quota System, Social Injustice

GESTIÓN PARA LA INTERNACIONALIZACIÓN DE LOS POSGRADOS/PROGRAMAS EN LA UNIVERSIDAD ESTATAL A DISTANCIA DE COSTA RICA: UN ENFOQUE BASADO EN EL DESARROLLO DE COMPETENCIAS INTERCULTURALES PARA LA MOVILIDAD ESTUDIANTIL

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Para la Universidad Estatal a Distancia (UNED), después de una educación postpandemia el desarrollo de un modelo de movilidad estudiantil bajo un modelo de internacionalización comprensiva ha sido un proceso de análisis e investigación que construya la conexión cultural significativa basada en valores interculturales, colaboración y que no refuerce los estereotipos sociales entre países. es el modelo que en esta ponencia los autores tenemos como propósito desarrollar. El objetivo de esta ponencia es dar a conocer el modelo y estrategias de Gestión para la Internacionalización Comprensiva de los programas y posgrados en la Universidad Estatal a Distancia, bajo un enfoque basado en el desarrollo de las competencias interculturales para la movilidad estudiantil. El modelo de movilidad estudiantil se desarrolla bajo la teoría de la pedagogía crítica, y un enfoque sociocultural que construya andamiajes de agencia comunal, el desarrollo de las voces individuales de los estudiantes desde un modelo de base de los estudiantes participantes y la escritura de una investigación acción política participativa. Luego de 45 años de demostrar la calidad y excelencia académica de la UNED, democratizando la educación superior, se hace necesario agregar una mirada más allá de las fronteras locales y buscar la visibilización global, que sea de conocimiento internacional la existencia de programas y posgrados de calidad de esta casa de estudios. La ponencia desarrolla un modelo de movilidad híbrida a distancia mediante un sistema de gestión de aprendizaje

en línea, aprovechando el uso y desarrollo de las tecnologías educativas basadas en la implementación de multimedios y la virtualidad como herramientas que se utilizan en el modelo de educación a distancia del cual, en Costa Rica, es pionera esta Universidad. El modelo presenta las estrategias para el desarrollo de una conexión intercultural con estudiantes costarricenses y de otros continentes mediante plataformas interactivas y herramientas 2.0 -4.0 para el desarrollo de interacción estudiantil especialmente postpandemia. El modelo presenta el procedimiento de gestión para todos aquellos interesados en desarrollar propuestas de movilidad estudiantil y conexión internacional con Costa Rica y Latinoamérica. Los presentadores concluyen con un conjunto de procedimientos para la audiencia interesados en el desarrollo de una propuesta de gestión para la internacionalización de programas y posgrados para la internacionalización con un enfoque en el desarrollo de competencias interculturales, no solo con Costa Rica, sino con Latinoamérica en una educación postpandemia.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Posgrados, Internacionalización Comprehensiva, Prospección, Cooperación

INCORPORATING IMPLICIT BIAS TRAINING INTO UNDERGRADUATE COURSES: STUDENT PERSPECTIVES

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Colleges and universities are encouraged to promote diversity and ensure intercultural awareness. Undergraduate years are an excellent time for self-reflection and critically analyzing how our experiences and upbringing may lead to unconscious bias. Implicit bias, also known as unconscious bias, is a form of bias that occurs automatically and unintentionally. Implicit bias can impact judgments and decisions and create barriers in careers, education, and life. This presentation will highlight the need for incorporating implicit bias training into undergraduate degree programs. A commitment to self-awareness enhances the capacity and competency of students and can address concerns that can fuel social inequities, prejudices, and hate. The presentation will provide insight from undergraduates regarding how their Implicit Bias training has equipped them to recognize their own biases and engage with diverse communities. Colleges and universities that offer training on implicit bias will better prepare students for industry, social impact, intercultural collaboration, and to fight social inequities. This panel discussion will provide insight directly from faculty and undergraduate students. The objectives are (1) to demonstrate the importance of incorporating implicit bias training into undergraduate health programs; (2) to examine barriers to incorporating implicit bias into the undergraduate

curriculum; and (3) to explain the ways implicit bias training can positively impact students from a global perspective.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Implicit Bias, Undergraduate Education, Cultural Sensitivity

REFORMULACIÓN LINGÜÍSTICA Y CONVIVENCIA ESCOLAR

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

El objetivo principal La violencia entre escolares y el acoso escolar son problemas crecientes y ciertas formas de discurso, una de las principales fuentes de generación de violencia y de acoso. Las palabras insultantes resultan comunes en la escuela y contribuyen a la creación de un clima hostil; son la antesala del acoso escolar. Urge que los centros escolares prioricen la erradicación del uso del lenguaje como herramienta victimizante, generadora de discriminación y de odio. Para eliminar los comportamientos verbales discriminatorios y promover un lenguaje amigable y respetuoso que facilite la convivencia y la resolución de controversias y conflictos se han de llevar a cabo intervenciones específicas con el alumnado.

El programa Reformulando ha sido diseñado para promover la convivencia pacífica en la escuela a través de la instrucción directa de habilidades comunicativas mediante sesiones estructuradas y manualizadas. Para estudiar su eficacia e incidencia, se analizaron las diferencias en los estilos y tácticas de resolución de conflictos de los escolares, indagando en las diferencias de género, así como en el acoso escolar sufrido antes y después de su aplicación. Participaron un total de 89 escolares (49 niños) de la provincia de Pontevedra (España).

Los resultados mostraron diferencias significativas en los estilos y tácticas de resolución de conflictos, así como con relación al acoso escolar sufrido. Se encontró un efecto de interacción entre la aplicación del programa y el género [$F(3, 167) = 23.071, p < .05, \eta_p^2 = .293$], así como un efecto principal del programa de intervención [$F(3, 167) = 6.642, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = .107$] y del género [$F(3, 167) = 4.033, p < .001, \eta_p^2 = .068$]. Estos resultados sugieren un funcionamiento diferencial según el género y apoyan la necesidad de la reformulación lingüística para lograr una convivencia pacífica y la igualdad efectiva entre mujeres y hombres.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

language, Reformulation, School Coexistence, Gender

VIOLENCIA DE GÉNERO. OTRA PERSPECTIVA

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

La violencia de género es una lacra social que siempre se trata, a mi modo de ver, desde una perspectiva unidireccional, donde los papeles de cada una de las partes están prácticamente establecidos de antemano. Está claro que la víctima lo es a lo largo de los tiempos de la misma forma y siempre se le dan las mismas soluciones. El agresor o delincuente igualmente es tratado de la misma forma. La innovación en el ámbito de la violencia de género radica en plantearse de un modo directo qué busca la víctima y, por qué no, qué busca el agresor o delincuente. Mirar a la cara la violencia de género significa hacerse un planteamiento distinto, abierto, que resuelva el problema con valentía. Lo que subyace en las víctimas es el deseo de situarse en una posición de igualdad o superioridad frente a su agresor y, en el agresor, el dominio o la no pérdida del estatus de “macho” alfa. Una faceta no explorada y precisamente no permitida es la de la mediación. Mediación después del procedimiento judicial, al margen de las consecuencias estimatorias o desestimatorias. Decimos esto porque, en materia de violencia de género, una condena con una orden de alejamiento resuelve una parte muy importante del problema, pero deja otro importante conflicto sin resolver que se lograría con la mediación. Por supuesto que considero imprescindible la mediación en aquellos supuestos de archivo, dado que aquí el conflicto continúa y se agrava. A través de una mediación con ciertas variantes y todas las garantías se lograría resolver aspectos que no se tocan en ningún caso y rompería la estadística de reincidencia como agresores y como víctimas.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Violencia de género, Mediación judicial

IMPLEMENTING CLIMATE ACTION AND GENDER EQUALITY IN BUSINESS COURSES

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Higher education is a key instrument for initiating social change. Universities and universities of applied sciences can play an important role in promoting human rights, peace education, and gender equality (Rosa and Clavero, 2021). Nevertheless, a systematic integration of SDGs into curricula development of business administration is missing.

To fight against discrimination and inequality, the European commission has always been committed to promoting diversity and inclusion. This commitment was materialised by the creation in 2004 of the European Diversity Charters. Nowadays, 26 Diversity Charters (DC) are established in Europe including the German DC, the Spanish DC, the Finnish DC, the Romanian DC, and the Lithuanian DC launched in 2006, 2009, 2012, March 2018, and October 2018 respectively. The main issue addressed in the DCs is discrimination based on gender, race, nationality, ethnic origin, religion, physical ability, age, sexual orientation and identity. All of the above-mentioned DCs aim at supporting and promoting best practices in diversity management and global citizenship in public and private organisations, including educational institutions. In 2019, 1.3 million international students were enrolled in tertiary education across the EU-27 including 44% from within Europe, 25% from Asia, and 15% from Africa. Additionally, programmes like Mobility for individuals of the Erasmus+ and other similar European programmes have contributed to creating diverse learning environments. The above has also largely contributed to immigration as a constantly growing phenomenon in Europe, which has led to demographic changes. Whereas, Europe has recently witnessed a rise of nationalist organisations such as Finns Party, Alternative for Germany, or the Alliance for

the Union of Romanians. There is an urgent need for tolerance, development of global mind-sets, and skills in inclusion and diversity management.

Global citizenship (as an attitude) and diversity management (as a process) are concepts for creating awareness and developing skills, attitudes, and values needed in a heterogeneous world (UNESCO, 2015).

A comparative analysis of five countries showed that neither global citizenship nor diversity management is systematically integrated in business courses. This paper exemplifies how Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) can serve as a thematic frame for addressing knowledge, skills, attitudes and values.

The paper finally concludes that there is still much to discuss at the integration of global citizenship and diversity management into higher education. There is a need for continued debate on how curricula development is further progressed and enhanced.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Global Citizenship, Diversity Management, Higher Education, Global Sustainable Development Goals, Human Rights, Gender Equity and Equality

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HACIA UN SERVICIO DE ATENCIÓN A LA MIGRACIÓN JUVENIL

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Se analizará el modelo de consejos municipales (y en algunos casos regionales) de participación de la población extranjera creados en Alemania desde 1973 en comparación con los modelos existentes en España. Otra cuestión a tener en cuenta es como se puede trabajar y planificar de manera orientada a objetivos. Un ejemplo de atención especial a la población juvenil migratoria es la figura del tutor de integración y el tutor de nacionalización existente en varias ciudades alemanas. Ante el aumento de la población juvenil de origen migratorio entre 12-27 años es necesario contar un servicio de atención a la migración juvenil en España similar al que tienen en Alemania, los llamados *Jugendmigrationsdienste*. Esta institución fue creada por Ministerio Federal de Familia, Mayores, Mujeres y Juventud. Cuenta con una red de 500 puntos de atención que presta asesoramiento, actividades educativas y de ocio. El enfoque de su labor es el apoyo individual a largo plazo de los jóvenes en su camino educativo y profesional. El objetivo es promover la participación social de los jóvenes y mejorar sus perspectivas. También es vital desde un punto de vista democrático: el principio de igualdad y de libertad para que todos participen en la vida social de un país. La proporción de personas con antecedentes migratorios está aumentando significativamente. Los hijos de estas personas se quedarán en este país y representan el futuro. Por lo tanto, un país no puede descuidar tanto a esta parte de la población en términos de educación y oportunidades. Además, se puede observar que los hogares urbanos están siendo agobiados por un número cada vez mayor de beneficiarios de ayudas sociales y que los hogares de altos ingresos están migrando al área periférica. Las ciudades se convierten en el crisol de todos los trastornos sociales. Hay que prestar la atención sobre las

consecuencias del cambio en el desarrollo de la población. Se pretende demostrar la situación actual de la prestación de servicios para un determinado sector de la población inmigrante que es manifiestamente mejorable a nivel público y que recae principalmente en ONGs.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Consejos de inmigración, Tutores de integración, Tutores de nacionalización

INTERCULTURAL AWARENESS, DIVERSITY, AND GLOBAL CITIZENSHIP – CONCEPTUAL CLARIFICATIONS AND SUGGESTED APPROACHES FOR HIGHER EDUCATION

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

There are big differences within European countries in how or if at all interculturality, diversity and global citizenship are taught in higher education. This roundtable discussion presents key findings of Erasmus+ funded cross-cultural research conducted in Finland, Lithuania, Germany, Romania, and Spain on understanding global citizenship and diversity concepts as well as developing study materials and a toolkit for teachers on teaching and integrating global citizenship and diversity management topics in higher education. It will introduce cross-cultural differences in understanding the concepts based on national literature reviews and theme interviews conducted among HEI teachers

as well as company and NGO representatives. In addition, students' and teachers' concepts, preferences for Sustainable Development Goals as well as topics taught as part of courses vary within Europe and these differences will be introduced supported by data collected with quantitative and qualitative methods. Global challenges, European and national politics in project countries, the impact of covid-19 and due to it a shift in preferred study methods in some project countries as well as differences in national curricula and general competences for HEI students will be discussed supported by research findings.

In conclusion, the roundtable discussion will share experiences in the preparation of the study materials for the pilot course including a handbook for activities related to diversity, inclusion, and global citizenship training, present the toolkit used in training HEI teachers in diversity and inclusion topics as well as give best practices for how to integrate global education topics into students' professional courses to increase awareness for the topics. With these different findings and outputs project partners aim to educate global citizens that are ready to fight global challenges, pay attention to sustainability in their everyday lives and have also better competences and a global mindset needed in a more diverse European or global workplace.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Intercultural Awareness, Diversity, Global Citizenship, Cross-cultural Differences

FINNISH AND ROMANIAN STUDENTS' UNDERSTANDING OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Educating students of all levels from kindergarten to higher education in Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is of high importance due to global goals for education as well as the life-long process of a single individual to become a better global citizen. Academic research and educational policies in recent years have focused a lot on pre-university levels and less emphasis was put onto higher education students' perspective. Thus, the paper aims at analysing the students' reasons for choosing the most important SDGs to learn about and describing students' understanding of how much these SDGs are being integrated into their studies. Results coming from a quantitative survey for students will be presented. Context analyses in which certain SDGs were selected by students from Finland and Romania will be conducted and variables such as the socio-demographic profile of the respondents, degree-specific differences, country cultural specificity, along with the influence of other institutional actors (university strategy, educational policies, governmental policies, countries' 2030 Agenda, etc.) will be considered. Differences and communalities will be presented.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Higher Education, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Global Citizenship, Educational Policies

INTERNATIONAL OR INTERNATIONAL(-ISED) STUDENTS? HOW STUDYING CRITICAL REPRESENTATIONS OF STUDENTS CAN ENHANCE OUR UNDERSTANDING OF EQUITABLE EDUCATION

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

In this proposal, we draw on research by colleagues from across East and South-East Asia whose scholarly work forms individual chapters in a book due to be published by STAR Scholars, titled: *International(-ised) students in East and South East Asia: critical perspectives*. We are very pleased to edit this book on constructions of international students across the region. We called for papers focusing on East and SouthEast Asia, as whilst there now exists quite a large body of literature on representations of international students in countries such as the US, the UK and Australia (e.g. Walker, 2014; Lee and Rice, 2007; Zhang and Tu, 2019), we wanted to expand this literature by focusing on international students in the region with the biggest diversity of TNE (Transnational Education) partnerships and where new forms of regionalism in internationalisation are emerging. We considered this important, as an attempt to destabilise the dominance of English-majority speaking destinations in shaping thinking and scholarship about international students. In the book, we feature submissions from Japan, Laos, China, Vietnam and the Philippines. The submissions have prompted a critical reflection around conceptualising internationalisation within education and required an examination of the term 'international student' – we would like to argue that the term 'international(-ised) student, rather than international, could more accurately capture the processes that shape student experiences of education abroad and understandings of internationalisation. The submissions from the authors in the book show this by drawing attention to the fact that it is not purely the international students' status (i.e. paying differing

fees, arriving in a foreign country for educational purposes, often associated with visa regimes, etc.) which creates differing student experiences, identity formations, and different 'takes' on internationalisation (all of which have implications for equity in international education). Rather, it is how the international students' status is 'patterned' into the social, political and institutional systems that structure and maintain their experiences of mobility and the outcomes that are produced (this is particularly highlighted in the chapter by Anh Ngoc Quynh Phan and Ha Ngan Ngo). This 'patterning', reflected in representations of international students which the authors in the book explore, gives their 'international student' status meaning(s). These meanings then position them as inclusive or 'greener' (chapter by Enkhtur Ariunaa and Li Ming), as agents of human capital development (chapters by Soubin Sisavath and Arlyne C. Marasigan, Mark Ponce C. San Juan & Nathaniel S. Dalida) and as people with dynamic identities (chapters by Mei Lai and Jasmine Ryu). The contributions in this book, therefore, demonstrate that how international students are represented is ascribed with positions of privilege or disadvantage – they are therefore international(-ised) into these positions, with implications for equity. Thus, in this context, engaging with the concept of an 'international(-ised) student' may offer a more nuanced understanding of the processes and factors that shape (in-) equitable international education.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

International Students, Transnational Education, East and South-east Asia, Equity

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING (ELT) POLICY IN MULTILINGUAL SCHOOLS IN NEPAL

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

In Nepal, English language teaching (ELT) is a widespread debate which has fascinated the attention of scholars because it has been practiced diversely in multilingual schools and classrooms. With this backdrop, this study explores the practices of ELT policy in two community schools situated in the rural part of Tanahun, Nepal.

The presentation intends to reveal the enduring practices of ELT and its policy in basic level community schools located in multilingual settings; especially, how the language policy arbiters (teachers and students) create, interpret, and appropriate ELT policy in their classes.

I adopted the 'critical ethnography' fieldwork for 3 months to reveal the ideologies of teachers and students for the 'creation, interpretation, and appropriation' of ELT policy in multilingual classrooms settings, and the 'ideological and implementational spaces' for other languages. The information was collected through observations of four ELT classes and two focus group discussions (FGD) with teachers and students from rural schools in Nepal, particularly, Tanahun district.

The presentations critically reveals the findings of the study in three major segments: tensions among English as a medium of instruction (EMI), Nepali as a medium of instruction (NMI), and mother-tongue based multilingual education (MTB-MLE); mismatches on policies and practices; and conflict amid monolingual, bilingual, and multilingual policies. Besides, I attempt to retell the opportunities and challenges, tensions and conflicts to adopt ELT policy in multilingual classroom situations. Finally, I manage question-answer and discussion with the participants, and get feedback for the effective implementation of appropriate language policy in the basic level ELT classroom in the multilingual context of Nepal, and some pedagogical insights on the issue.

The study globally informs the students and teachers on ELT policy and the processes for creation, interpretation, and appropriation of educational language policy in a multilingual school context in rural Nepal.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

ELT Policy, Rural Schools in Nepal, Critical Ethnography

CROSSING BORDERS: AN ANALYSIS OF STUDENT DEVELOPMENT OF GLOBAL CULTURAL AWARENESS IN AN ONLINE INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATIVE MODULE

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Internationalisation is core to the principles of higher education; it provides the opportunity for mobility of staff, students, and research, to enhance the reputation of the university (de Witt, 2013). Knight (2008), defines internationalisation in higher education as a 'Process of integrating an internal, intercultural or global dimension into the purpose, functions and delivery of post-secondary education'. Globalisation, the needs of the economy and society are all key drivers of the need to internationalise in Higher Education while the role of internationalisation for the university has become an industry and source of revenue for the university (de Wit, 2020). Internationalisation is a core element of a university therefore needs to be considered in a more comprehensive manner rather than from a mobility perspective. This research is based on the premise that not all staff or students may be in a position to engage in international mobility, therefore internationalisation engagement becomes an elite activity. The process of internationalisation needs to be thought of not as solely an outbound/inbound mobility activity but rather as core to the curriculum. The Crossing Borders project developed at Georgia Southern University (GSU). The objective is to engage students in structured online cross-cultural conversations with students from different universities, cultures and countries in order to increase cultural awareness and cultural competency (Wickline, 2012; Wickline et al. 2021). This project has the potential to increase the engagement of at home students and to benefit from the goals of internationalisation. The Crossing Borders project has used the increased capacity and awareness of online tools and skills to introduce students from different countries, ethnic groups and culture to each other. Students engage in a series of guided online conversations/structured social interactions with students in universities in other countries. The

aim of this research is to gather data from students who have engaged in The Crossing Borders Project through a pre-and post-test questionnaire (Appendix 1). Students are based in Ireland, United Kingdom, Belgium and the United States. This data will be used to highlight and explore the challenges experienced and the opportunities of online internationalisation at home teaching for students who have participated. The questionnaires will explore intercultural awareness and intercultural competency and have been developed from the work of Deardoff on assessment of intercultural competence (Deardoff 2006). It is anticipated that the outcomes of this study can contribute to a developing body of work on Internationalisation at Home and to developing curriculum strategies to influence intercultural understanding and global awareness.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Internationalisation at Home, Curriculum Strategies, Intercultural Understanding, Global Awareness

OVERVIEW AND TRENDS IN EASY READ IN SPAIN TODAY

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The easy-to-read writing method is unknown nowadays, as it tends to be confused with plain language i.e. simplifying the language. On the contrary, easy read is an elaborate writing method, with precise guidelines that need to be met in order to obtain the logo that certifies the material as a publication written in easy-to-read method.

Such a system was born in Sweden in 1968. From Sweden, this work spread to neighbouring countries, and gradually, an European inclusion network called Inclusion Europe was created.

Until the early 2000s such initiatives were rare and unpopular. It is essential to highlight two aspects that completely revolutionised the easy-to-read landscape in Spain.

Firstly, the Associació Lectura Fàcil, a Catalan non-profit organisation that has been adapting and compiling easy-to-read materials since 2003. This association has joined the Inclusion Europe network.

Secondly, it is also worth mentioning the UNE 153101: 2018 regulation. This is the first technical standard on Easy Read in Spain whose content specifies the guidelines and recommendations for the adaptation, creation and validation of documents in easy read, and seeks to facilitate the understanding of written information to ensure equal opportunities.

In order to know the current panorama of materials published in easy read in Spain, we have carried out a study.

We have identified all the materials published in easy-to-read format in Spain up to September 2022. To do this, we first consulted the Catalogue of the Associació Lectura Fàcil and, due to the lack of data, we turned to the BNE (Spanish National

Library). Then, we were able to create a list with all relevant data that we analysed later on.

We expected to have little creation and a huge lack of genres as well as a lack of works in other languages besides Spanish.

Evidently, after this analysis, the current trends become clear and match our expectations: contemporary literature is scarce; big name publishers are not interested in this method of writing, poetry and theatre are not explored in depth; instead, there is a tendency to adapt classics whose copy-rights have already expired, or to opt for children's and young people's literature due to its apparent simplicity as a genre. Finally, publications in other languages such as Galician are increasing but are still really scarce.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Easy-to-read, Easy Read, Associació Lectura Fàcil, Adaptation, Creation

RECOGNIZING THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE 'INSIGNIFICANT': FROM LATIN AMERICA AND THE CARIBBEAN TO TAIWAN

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Around the world, initiatives at the institutional, national, and regional levels aiming to augment international student enrollment targets are contributing to increased cross-border mobility and have also led to shifts in the flow patterns of international students (Mok, 2012; OECD, 2018). For instance, new flows of international students (IS) to non-traditional study destinations have emerged (Aydin, 2021; Bista & Glass, 2020; Li & Bray, 2007; Lipura & Collins, 2020) as well as atypical 'South-South' (Phan, 2016), 'East-East' (Lee, 2017) and 'intra-periphery' (Shields & Edwards, 2010) mobility patterns. Moreover, due to COVID-19, many countries around the world closed their national borders and increased restrictions on international travel. Even though the long-term impact of this catalyzing factor is yet to be understood, researchers have widely documented the immediate and short-term impacts of this phenomenon to the international student mobility (ISM) landscape (Buckner et al., 2002; Cao & Chieu, 2021; Lau, 2020). Despite these changes, the existing literature on the experience of IS remains overwhelmingly concentrated on students from the Global South going to the 'traditional' English-speaking destination countries, namely, the US, the UK, Canada, and Australia (S. W. Lee, 2017), thus continuing to ignore 'non-traditional' destinations and non-traditional students. My thesis research responds to calls from critical scholars to move beyond the constraints of the current research and draw new approaches that reflect the state of the field more accurately and more equitably (Lipura & Collins, 2020; Madge et al., 2015; Stein, 2017). I argue that the lack of research outside Western settings might not only solidify the hegemony of Western thought and practices, but also attach a

meaning of 'insignificance' to research in non-traditional settings, and of non-traditional students, by denying their importance and power within the field.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Higher Education, Student Mobility, Decentering, Taiwan, Latin America and the Caribbean

DIFFERENCES IN PROFESSIONAL IDENTITY OF MALE AND FEMALE EXPATRIATE TEACHERS IN INTERNATIONAL SCHOOLS IN THE MIDDLE EAST

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

While previous research focused on the professional identity of teachers, no research has compared the professional identity development of male and female teachers, particularly with a large set of data which covers various international schools. The purpose of this research is to gain insight into the professional identity development of male and female expatriate teachers in international schools in the Middle East. Therefore, the following hypotheses were proposed: (1) The alternative hypothesis (H_a): there are significant differences in identity development of male and female expatriate teachers. (2) The null hypothesis (H_o): there are no significant differences in identity development of male and female expatriate teachers. Tajfel and Turner's (2004) model of identity allows for operationalization of identity into five factors: self-presentation, self-image, self-esteem, self-categorization, and self-concept. The independent variables constitute of sex (e.g., female, male). The dependent variable represents the scores on professional identity operationalized as mentioned above (self-presentation, self-image, self-esteem, self-categorization, and self-concept). The design of the study was comparative, comparing both males and females in the development of various attributes of teacher professional identity. The instrument for data collection in this study consisted of a two-part online survey. The population sample originally included 136 participants who took the survey; however only 127 of those participants (38 males and 89 females) were included in the study as some of them did not complete the survey. A paired t-test was conducted to determine whether there were significant differences in each of the categories of professional identity (self-presentation, self-image, self-esteem, self-

categorization, and self-concept) for both male and female expatriate teachers. All the t-test results were based on an alpha value of 0.05. Firstly, out of the four constructs, participants scored the highest on self-esteem. Females scored higher than males in self-esteem, which confirms Cramer's (2000) earlier study which indicated that males scored lower in this construct. The results indicate significant differences between males and females in all constructs of professional identity used in this study. This finding further emphasizes Cramer's (2000) discovery emphasizing the existence of gender differences concerning identity development. Particularly focused on professional identity development, these results also confirm Naukkarinen and Bairoh's (2021) outcomes that males and females differ in the construction of professional identity. This study has been one of the first attempts to thoroughly investigate the differences between male and female teachers' professional identity development. The findings reported here shed new light on understanding the complex process of professional identity development of both male and female teachers in international schools in relation to induction. The analysis of professional identity undertaken in this study, has extended our knowledge of the differences between professional identity development of males and females. Based on the findings, there are significant differences in professional identity development between the two sexes. In the light of the lack of current knowledge of how male and female teachers develop their professional identity, this study represents a first step in expanding this knowledge. The results have significant implications for the understanding of the differences between male and female teachers in the development of their professional identity.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Expatriate Teachers, Professional Identity, International Schools, Teacher Identity

PROMOTING INTERCULTURAL AWARENESS IN A JAPANESE UNIVERSITY ENGLISH READING CLASS

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Intercultural awareness is an essential aspect of language teaching and learning in today's globalization era. The promotion of the ability to understand and appreciate different cultures is especially important in English classes in Japanese universities, where students have relatively limited access to various intercultural experiences outside classrooms. This paper will discuss the importance of promoting intercultural awareness in an English reading class based on my recent study in a Japanese university and the strategies that lecturers can use to promote it. While there is abundant literature on intercultural awareness, little exists for how this is promoted in English reading classes embedded in disciplinary departments in a particular national context. Studies of this nature are important since students' preferred teaching style impacts on students' learning, every discipline has a unique character, and each national culture is different. For instance, some students prefer an interactive teaching style while the others, a lecture style. Moreover, though a disciplinary language may, at large, be universal, intercultural awareness is necessary to ensure full understanding of the different contexts in which it is used. For instance, a legal phrase may have nuanced meanings in a different cultural context. Meanwhile, in countries like Japan, despite the promotion of internationalization of higher education, many classes are still composed of all Japanese students. To investigate the current situation in which intercultural awareness could be promoted, a qualitative study was conducted to 28 students at a compulsory English reading class in a law department composed of all Japanese students at the beginning of the school year, using a survey that focused on what style of teaching students preferred and why. Despite interactive teaching style to be the world norm nowadays, many students expressed that they preferred the lecture

style due to anxiety involved in expressing one's ideas or communicating with classmates. As in any other discipline, law students need to be able to appreciate different cultural perspectives which in turn would enable them to understand and interpret their disciplinary legal language broadly and deeply as fit for each case. Implications from this study point to the importance of creating a safe learning environment and exposing a wide range of texts, including literature, news articles, and academic papers written by authors from different cultural backgrounds. In this way, students are guided to be aware of the cultural context in which the texts were written and the values and beliefs that underpin them. By promoting intercultural awareness in a stress-free environment, lecturers can support students to develop critical thinking skills, empathy, and effective communication skills. They can do this by encouraging students to discuss the cultural context of the texts they read, incorporating group activities made up of a small number of students, and including intercultural awareness into their assessment criteria. With these strategies, lecturers can prepare students to communicate and interact without anxiety with people from different cultural backgrounds in their personal and professional lives.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Intercultural Awareness, Globalization, English Reading Class.

OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES OF INTERNATIONALIZING HIGHER EDUCATION IN POST- COLONIAL INDIA

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The Indian subcontinent has a long tradition of higher learning. The ancient Buddhist centres for higher learning dated back to ancient times with Takshashila University (600-500 BC) in modern Pakistan, Nalanda University (425 AD -1205 AD), Vikramshila University (800 AD – 1203 AD), Vallabhi University (600 AD – 1200 AD), Nagarjuna Vidyapeeth (600 AD), Kanthalloor University (1000 AD – 1300 AD) in modern India and Jagaddala University (1084 AD – 1207 AD) in modern Bangladesh. These Universities attracted scholars from across Asia and the middle-eastern region. However, these universities declined over the years with external invasions and loss of patronage of local kings and dynasties. Even in the modern times, Asia's first Nobel Laureate in Literature, Rabindranath Tagore built Viswa Bharati (literally meaning World-minded Indian) University with an international vision in the year 1921. Viswa Bharati did not just attract scholars from around the world, the University also established an international curriculum with the study of multiple Indian and international languages, alongside the study of arts and sciences. However, this tradition declined in the postcolonial era and Indian higher education became increasingly inward-looking, as it is evident from research (Altbach 2012, Belousova 2018). In recent years, especially with the new National Education Policy 2020 there is a renewed interest for internationalising Indian higher education. This paper discusses the specific opportunities and challenges of internationalizing higher education in the postcolonial Indian context. The paper also discusses how the international dimension of higher education evolved in the western context over the past half century. From a focus on international development projects and student scholarships to promote peace and understanding following the two World wars, international higher education in the West has been facing a stage of crisis following neoliberal disinvestment in

public higher education and the recent global pandemic (Kinght & DeWit 2018, Lau 2020. Marmolejo 2021). Hence, this paper concludes by arguing that aligning the internationalisation agenda with the sustainable development goals could be a way forward to make higher education equitable for the marginalized and to make it relevant for both the Indian and Western contexts as our planet Earth is facing a serious sustainability challenge.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Internationalisation, Indian Higher Education, Post-colonial Indian Context

INTERCULTURAL AWARENESS IN HIGHER EDUCATION: INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS' PERSPECTIVE

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The internationalization of higher education globally and educational initiatives are continuously increasing in numbers to enrich the learning environment through intercultural awareness, diversity, values, and understanding. The foremost focus of globalization of higher education is focusing on developing students' intercultural communication skills, critical thinking, and overall bringing awareness to prepare them for local and global markets (Deardorff, 2015). Increasing students' intercultural awareness would also help shape their identities and they will be exposed to different cultures, values, and experiences (Ayber & Hojeij, 2021). One of the major reasons why there is an influx of international students in North America is because they contribute towards economic growth at a local and federal level. Meanwhile these students are also bringing diverse experiences and cultural values to the host institutions. However, these students face various challenges as they arrive in a new country where there is pretty much everything new for them. Some major challenges that they face include language barriers which restrict their ability to socialize and communicate effectively, loneliness, culture shock, and academic learning difficulties due to different teaching pedagogies. While these students navigate different challenges it is important that they have a sense of belonging, a place to call home while being away from home. These students need support inside and outside the classroom, need space and opportunities to socialize, connect with peers, participate in various activities on- and off-campus, and most importantly be able to achieve their desired grades, personal and professional goals. The purpose of this study is to investigate international students' experiences at a Canadian post-secondary institution to determine the need for intercultural

awareness using semi-structured interviews. The main research question consists of: (1) How is their experience in terms of social life and academic learning as an international student? (2) What are the participants' attitudes towards creating intercultural awareness in higher education? Semi-structured interviews were conducted using qualitative methodology. Data was collected and transcribed. Thematic analysis was performed to identify codes and themes to make sense of shared meaning and experiences (Braun & Clarke, 2012, p.57). Participants expressed various challenges as they were trying to adjust to the Canadian environment and university culture. It is very hard to socialize and make friends because of language barriers and lack of opportunities to network and make friends. While it was hard to socialize, there were also academic difficulties because of different expectations. Participants showed frustration that there was minimal to no intercultural awareness such as recognizing major cultural events from their home country or organizing events to celebrate festivals. Overall, participants wanted to represent their culture by wearing ethnic dresses, introducing authentic and popular food items, music, and language because it brings joy, satisfaction and a sense of belonging while representing their country. Even though Canada is considered one of the diverse countries in the world, yet, in higher education, international students are feeling left out and alone. Several implications are suggested in this study to provide support to these students and bring intercultural awareness on-campus through various means such as training faculty members, meaningful mentoring programs, increase peer interactions, initiatives of social cultural activities, institution wide strategic planning and initiatives to increase intercultural awareness on-campus and surrounding communities.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Intercultural Awareness, Diversity, Higher Education, Understanding, Challenges

TRANSLANGUAGING FOR EQUALITY AND INCLUSION IN SECOND LANGUAGE EDUCATION: A PEER REVIEW

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Translanguaging is a pedagogical approach that recognizes the multilingual nature of many language learners and encourages them to use all their linguistic resources to facilitate learning. This approach promotes equality and inclusion in the second language classroom by valuing and utilizing the diverse linguistic backgrounds and experiences of learners. Translanguaging allows students to make connections between their languages and cultures, to express their thoughts and ideas more effectively, and to develop a deeper understanding of the second language. In a study conducted by Creese and Blackledge (2010), translanguaging was found to be an effective strategy for promoting equity in multilingual classrooms, as it allowed all students to participate actively and engage in learning. Similarly, García and Wei (2014) argue that translanguaging can lead to a more democratic and inclusive classroom environment by giving all students equal opportunities to use their full linguistic repertoires. The objective of this peer review proposal is to explore the effectiveness of translanguaging in promoting equality and inclusion in second language education. Specifically, this review aims to examine the literature on translanguaging and its impact on language learning outcomes, cultural identity, and social inclusion in diverse educational settings.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Translanguaging, Second Language Education, Equality, Inclusion

COMMUNICATION: AN AVENUE FOR THE PROFESSIONAL LIFE

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Language is a tool to express human feelings and thoughts, and competencies in communication determine success on the job market. In Nepal, both the English and Nepali languages are considered essential skills for finding lucrative jobs. Besides, newly established companies are focusing on the politeness and attitude of their employees when hiring. This research paper deals with the necessity of communication skills that outweigh the content for getting entry in the job. In Nepal, thousands of graduates from different communities go to the job market every year after completing their formal education, so among them non-Nepali speakers have less chance to be hired in these vacant places despite they are quite qualified in concerned subject matter. This paper tries to figure out how non-Nepali speakers struggle to get entry in the professional career due to their insufficient language skills, and how the so-called mainstream languages create problems in their career growth. This study adopts qualitative methods for data collection from ten employees from five different communities: Maithili, Newari, Tamang, Magar, and Tharu, who will be asked from five different business houses, including a media house. The employees will be asked several questions about how they got enrolled in the job and how the process was. Moreover, the method of setting up the questionnaire was by sharing Google Forms and in-person interviews. The employees have to struggle to get enrolled in the job due to the lack of command of the so-called standard language. Although they have a good command of their subject matter, there is less chance of being selected from the selection process. Therefore, language creates social class and economic hierarchy. Employees from non-Nepali mother tongues face a variety of problems from the very beginning of their careers. Difficulties in communication create differences. If employees are competent in communication, they can take

their career to the next level. Therefore, communication skills play a vital role in shaping and growing a career, which is why communication skills are one of the inevitable skills.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Business Houses, Social Class, Economic Hierarchy, Media Houses, Mainstream Language

FORMACIÓN EN INTERCULTURALIDAD A TRAVÉS DEL MANGA: EL CASO DE *DETECTIVE CONAN*

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Por su marcado carácter transcultural y sus orígenes, donde amalgama influencias de todo el mundo junto a particularidades niponas, el manga —un medio de origen japonés similar al cómic— se erige como uno de los instrumentos más versátiles para la formación en interculturalidad de los individuos en general y, más concretamente, del alumnado universitario. Con el fin de detectar cómo se representa la interculturalidad —tanto de forma consciente como inconsciente por parte del autor— en un manga cuya temática no está relacionada con el didactismo (es decir, una obra no planificada para ser trabajada en un aula destinada a la interculturalidad), en esta investigación realizaremos un análisis cualitativo de la presencia de elementos interculturales en la narrativa de algunos de los casos más relevantes del manga *Detective Conan*, de Gōshō Aoyama. A partir de este estudio, basado en los estudios de Katan (2004) y Hofstede (1980), se prevé la posibilidad de entender cómo funcionan los mecanismos por los que se generan situaciones interculturales (planificadas o espontáneas) en el manga y la de establecer una serie de criterios que permitan trasladar los resultados obtenidos al aula universitaria con el fin de aumentar la etnorrelatividad del alumnado.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Formación en interculturalidad, Manga, Detective Conan, etnorrelatividad

UNINTENDED CONSEQUENCES OF INTERNATIONALIZATION: IMPLICATIONS FOR PRACTICE

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The conference theme examines ways to improve education for a more equitable world. This requires new ways of looking at internationalization within new frames. The focus of this presentation is to identify and expand on an overlooked part of internationalization, the Unintended Consequences of Internationalization (UCI). Internationalization of higher education goals are constantly evolving. Research on UCI, while referred to as something that exists (Knight, 2009), is limited which can result in missteps in evaluation, underestimation of outcomes, and inaccurate projection of goals and outcomes. Kamyab and Raby (2023) offer an expanded definition of UCI: “what occurs when a single or set of actions (theoretical or practical) influence new perceptions, trajectories of action, or byproducts in unexpected ways” (p. 1). The panel presenters explain UCI in a binary construct, as a positive (e.g., being transformative) or as negative (e.g., fostering marginalization, systemic inequities, or shifting rationales from a socio-cultural to a neo-liberal focus (Brandenburg et al., 2019; de Wit, 2020; Stein, 2019; Van Gaalen, 2020). The presenters will also provide examples in a non-binary construct, where UCI is both negative and positive depending on context. For example, unintended actions can reduce marginalization in one group while accentuating it in another. Theoretically, UCI frames goals, vision, and processes, while practically, it is the outcome of policies and products. Two constructs inform the UCI Framework. First, is the concept of shifting internationalization discourses, including shifts in definitions of concepts (Leask & de Gayardon, 2021), shifts in rationales (de Wit & Altbach, 2021), shifts in global imaginaries (Buckner & Stein, 2019), and shifts

resulting from UCI (Kamyab & Raby, 2023). Second, is critical internationalization that challenges traditional rationales for being grounded in Western neo-colonial foundations (Buckner & Stein, 2020) that perpetuate inequality (Suspitsyna & Shalka, 2019) and that deny local imaginaries that exist in each country (Yang, 2021). The panelists will share how UCI can innovate and which can disrupt cycles of disadvantage and marginalization. The case study approach will target UCI in different countries (Creswell, 2022). Other methods include discourse analysis of literature, historical documents, and policy analysis. When examining UCI across different case studies, four themes emerge. 1) Historical, Political, Socio-economic, and Geographic context of IHE in their country; 2) UCI: Binary and/or Non-Binary construct; 3) Importance of the UCI for Comparative and International Higher Education; and 4) Scholarly Significance to the Field of Higher Education.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

International Higher Education, Equity, Unintended Consequences of Internationalization (UCI)

AMERICAN PRESIDENT JOE BIDEN'S VICTORY SPEECH: A RHETORICAL ANALYSIS

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

In triangular argumentations such as ethos, logos, and pathos are analyzed rhetorically when President Joe Biden delivers his victory speech on November 7, 2020, as the 46th President of the United States. It is a video speech that has been subjected to ten different videos doing oratorical analyses in order to collect qualitative data. This essay's main objective is to use a theoretical lens to assess Biden's victory speech to the American folks. This study aims to pinpoint the rhetorical points presented in President Biden's victory speech. The data is analysed from his speech under the Aristotelian qualitative technique for this investigation, which is the foundation of the research. For data analysis, it used a descriptive qualitative approach. According to the research, Joe Biden uses ethos 37%, pathos 55%, and followed by logos 8% in his winning speeches. The paper includes various primary resources of videos as well as secondary materials like books, media, film, newspapers, magazines, and journal archives as well as primary resources like various video speeches to establish the context and support the rhetorical interpretation. In his victory speech, Biden vows to promote unity rather than division especially to America. Additionally, Biden pledges that their efforts will start with containing the COVID-19 outbreak. His analysis demonstrates that plain language is more approachable than complex one since speaking clearly and persuasively is essential to creating comfort and trust with the audience.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Ethos, Folks, Lens, logos, Oratorical, Pathos

HOW TO EDUCATE IN THE VALUES OF DIVERSITY AND TOLERANCE: TEACHING POLITICAL IDEOLOGIES FROM A PLURALIST PERSPECTIVE

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Most introductory courses on Political Science at Universities include in their contents the study of modern political ideologies. The point is that the most widespread way of teaching each of these political ideologies is based on understanding them as a set of political concepts with exclusive meanings, and as separate ideational structures, conceptually disconnected and in contradiction with each other. Although it could be argued that this way of teaching political ideologies is the most accessible, in our view it would prevent students from reaching a satisfactory understanding of the complexities of political reality. The reason is that this approach does not take into account how most political ideologies arrogate to themselves the true definition of conceptual meanings and believe themselves to be in possession of political truth. Thus, it forgets how political ideologies want to prevent any healthy discussion of the meanings they attribute to political concepts, ultimately, blocking the development of political debate. And, inasmuch as political ideologies renege from the virtues of democratic deliberation, if we teach them as they present themselves, we would prevent the possibility of developing, in the classroom, a normative discussion based on the premises of tolerance and respect for diversity and pluralism. In this paper we aim, first, to assess how the way we conceive of the nature and structure of political ideologies conditions the possibilities for critical reflection and debate. Specifically, we argue that the most appropriate way to analyze and teach political ideologies is the "morphological approach". This approach allows us to achieve an understanding of each political ideology as a flexible network of interrelated political concepts and, more importantly, allows us to discover how

the political and ethical concepts on which those ideologies are based have a fundamentally contested nature, despite ideologies thinking otherwise. Moreover, this approach allows us to apprehend the complexity involved in the processes of political cognition, conditioned to a large extent, and unfortunately, by the anti-pluralistic character that characterizes most political ideologies, with their capacity to create cognitive barriers and promote conflict between individuals and groups. On the other hand, once we have provided students with a useful framework of ideological analysis, we want to find out what tools could be used to develop, within the classroom, a peaceful and tolerant discussion on ethical and ideological issues, thus potentially contributing to forge a citizenry less prone to assume conflictive and polarizing attitudes. In short, if we really want to appreciate the richness of the existing diversity of values, cultures, identities and worldviews that permeate our societies, while, simultaneously, aspiring to the achievement of common political and moral principles both nationally and globally, we should deepen the study of political cognitive processes in order to achieve better ways of developing a public debate free of intolerant and anti-democratic attitudes.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Democracy, Diversity, Ideologies, Pluralism, Tolerance

PLURILINGUALISM AS AN APPROACH TO TEACHING SUSTAINABILITY IN MEXICAN PUBLIC HIGHER EDUCATION

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

My experience with internationalization started when I coordinated the language department of a public technological university in Mexico (2012-2018). Internationalization was quickly integrated into my Institution's strategic plan, and paradoxically it opened spaces and resources for language programs in public universities, yet it also brought a myriad of challenges to language departments. Language programs in Mexican public higher education face two challenges: English hegemony and additional languages being taught as separate subjects and disconnected from mainstream curricula. The scarce content-based approaches in Mexican education, such as Content and Language Integrated Learning/CLIL, usually have an English proficiency requirement. This marginalizes most students from opportunities to learn mainstream content through their full language repertoires and constitutes a gatekeeper for access to bilingual programs (Spolsky, 2009). English hegemony in Mexican higher education not only brings myriad consequences for learners and the ecology of languages of universities but also contradicts the national discourse that recognizes Mexico as a pluricultural and multilingual. There have been calls to integrate an intercultural framework and respect for Indigenous cultures and languages into mainstream education, yet this ideal has not materialized in classrooms (Dietz & Mateos Cortés, 2011). A new bill, Ley General de Educación Superior, now states interculturalism as a mandate that requires all universities across Mexico to integrate interculturality and contribute to revitalizing Indigenous languages (Diario Oficial de la Federación, 2021). I situate my Ph.D. research in this framework which fosters a plurilingual approach to teaching a course in sustainability that draws on the ecology of languages in Mexican universities, including Indigenous Languages. There is scarce research on

linguistic diversity and the environment, yet evidence has correlated the death of linguistic and cultural diversity with the disappearance of biological species (e.g. Skutnabb-Kangas, 2002). In the field of sustainability, there have been calls for integrating Indigenous knowledge with Western traditions of sustainable development (Binagwaho et al., 2022). I argue that plurilingualism can foster connections between socio-ecological sustainability and the ecology of languages in their educational contexts. Yet, critical scholars caution that initiatives that promote plurality in education must address unresolved historical hierarchies among languages and cultures in education, especially in contexts with colonial legacies (Rosa & Flores, 2017). In this paper, I explore how plurilingualism may be an entry point for critical dialogue and actions in mainstream curricula when it goes beyond pedagogy, and it impacts the social and political arenas (Rincón-Gallardo 2015). The paper investigates the affordances of critical and participatory action research as a starting point to support critical communities of practice that embark on implementing plurilingualism into sustainability courses in Mexican Higher education through collaboration between language and content teachers. I propose a processual approach to comparative case study (Bartlett & Vavrus, 2017) to foster critical reflection and exchange among communities of educators and students across three sites of Mexican higher education. I hope to engage researchers and educators in critical reflections and critical action research to support plurilingual education in mainstream curricula to foster social justice agendas and linguistic diversity in Mexican higher education.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Plurilingualism, Intercultural Education, Sustainability, Internationalization

THE MODERATING ROLE OF HUMAN CAPITAL IN THE FDI-ECONOMIC GROWTH LINK

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) has become an important driver of economic growth and development for countries around the world, including African nations. FDI refers to the investment made by foreign entities in the domestic economy of a host country, typically in the form of capital, technology, and expertise. It plays a crucial role in stimulating economic activity, enhancing productivity, promoting trade integration, and transferring knowledge and skills. African countries have increasingly sought to attract FDI to leverage its potential benefits for their economies. These nations often possess abundant natural resources, untapped markets, and growing consumer bases, making them attractive investment destinations. FDI inflows to Africa have increased over the past few decades, but the effectiveness of these investments in fostering sustainable economic growth has been a subject of debate.

The main aim of this paper is to examine the impact of FDI on economic growth in African countries mainly in 4 regions which are Sub-Saharan Africa, Africa Western and Central, Africa Eastern and Southern and Middle east and North Africa specifically focusing on the period from 1990 to 2019. The inclusion of the moderating variable, human capital is crucial to understand the nuanced relationship between FDI and economic growth. Human capital represents the skills, knowledge, and capabilities of a country's workforce, which is essential for driving innovation, productivity, and overall economic performance. By incorporating human capital as a moderating variable, the study acknowledges that FDI may have varying effects on economic growth depending on the level of human capital development in African countries. It recognizes that the effectiveness of FDI in promoting growth could be influenced by the quality of education, training programs, and skill levels of the local workforce.

The research employs a quantitative approach which is of secondary data kind, using econometric techniques and panel data analysis to assess the relationship between FDI and economic growth. A sample of 20 countries have been chosen and the data have all been collected on the database of the World development indicators. At first a panel unit root test was conducted and it has been found that the components are of mixed variables, that is, there are both stationary and non-stationary variables with mixed order of integration. In this case, it is more useful to use the ARDL model. The findings of this research dissertation is that FDI has indeed had a large impact on economic growth of these 4 regions of Africa and it can be seen that FDI and human capital work very well together in those regions to promote economic growth. Yet, it can be noted that while analysing those 4 regions individually, it is clearly visible that middle east and north Africa are much more advanced than the other 3 regions. The research outcomes can inform policymakers, investors, and international organizations on strategies to maximize the benefits of FDI while addressing the challenges associated with human capital development in African economies.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), Economic Growth, African Countries, Human Capital

Y DESPUÉS DE LA PANTALLA... ¿QUÉ? EL CINE PARA EL APRENDIZAJE LIBRE E INTERCULTURAL DESDE LA COLABORACIÓN CON ESTUDIANTES

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

El cine tiene una mística propia, seduce. Es un medio poderoso para la comunicación y efectivo para retratar la conducta humana. Si bien por ello se ha convertido en una herramienta útil para la educación, es común relegarlo a la malentendida innovación del uso del audiovisual por sí mismo y que se deja aislado de una efectiva y significativa experiencia de aprendizaje. Bajo esta premisa, esta investigación explorará al llamado séptimo arte como medio educativo durante un verano de investigación en el que estudiantes provenientes de distintos contextos colaborarán en una experiencia de sensibilización intercultural a través de dicho medio. La metodología de estudio de caso dará cuenta del proceso y teorías producto del trabajo democrático, creativo y crítico que estos llevarán a cabo durante su estancia en la Universidad de Guadalajara (México), institución de educación media superior y superior participante en el XXVIII Verano de la Investigación Científica y Tecnológica del Pacífico en el mismo país durante junio y julio de 2023. Los resultados permitirán aportes de relevancia para: (1) los campos de estudio de la educación, la internacionalización del currículum, la interculturalidad, el análisis de la imagen y el análisis cinematográfico; (2) dotar de una mirada sensible a las metodologías y estrategias enfocadas en el estudio de las competencias interculturales; (3) ampliar las posibilidades de referencias audiovisuales a múltiples contextos socioculturales; (4) impulsar y documentar prácticas de aprendizaje libre, aquel basado en la disrupción del núcleo pedagógico y que permite encontrar sentido a preguntas y problemáticas sociales que sean de interés de los estudiantes.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Cine Intercultural, Aprendizaje libre, Internacionalización del currículum, Competencias interculturales, Investigación con estudiantes.

BOUNDARIES, POWER DYNAMICS AND RESISTANCE: SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL STUDY OF TRANSFORMING PLAYGROUND INTO MEANINGFUL AND INCLUSIVE SPACE

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The systems of playing and the power of playground design affect the social, emotional, cognitive, and physical development of children. Some playgrounds are systematically designed and some are explored and created by the children. In the first case, playgrounds are imposed by the parents, school authorities and urban localities with instructions and boundaries. In the second case, children, esp from marginalized groups and segregated areas, try to explore their playgrounds and develop a sense of achievement. So, children create their own space despite daily exclusions. Their imagination and free will to explore their social world become the symbol of their resistance. Construction of their play is a kind of collective activity which creates hope for a meaningful group process. This research is a qualitative program to venture into the marginalized children's understanding of play, how they meaningfully construct their play and their collective sense of resistance to the dominant playgrounds exclusively occupied by the dominant groups.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Power Dynamics, Resistance, Playground, Social Psychology, Diversity, Transformative Education

EDUCAR PARA LA CONVIVENCIA PACÍFICA. NUEVAS NECESIDADES EN LA EDUCACIÓN FORMAL

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

La Educación formal juega un papel fundamental en edades tempranas como vía para el entendimiento y el respeto para una convivencia pacífica. Aunque existen desafíos y obstáculos, el ecosistema escolar se presenta como un territorio propicio para gestionar el respeto a la diferencia, fomentar el intercambio cultural y el conocimiento mutuo. La heterogeneidad del alumnado no debe ser vista como una debilidad, sino como una fortaleza del Sistema Educativo. Sin embargo, es necesario superar creencias peyorativas, mejorar los planes de estudio, la financiación y la formación del profesorado para afrontar la diversidad en el aula y los conflictos que puedan surgir.

Por ello, es crucial que desde el Sistema Educativo se aborden los desafíos y retos que las dinámicas sociales imponen. En un mundo globalizado como en el que vivimos, las migraciones hacia países occidentales suponen nuevos desafíos para los países de acogida. La búsqueda de mejores oportunidades de vida y factores como la falta de perspectivas laborales en los países de origen, las situaciones de guerra y la persecución, son, entre otras, las principales causas de estos flujos migratorios los cuales han transformado la sociedad española y plantean la necesidad de afrontar con medidas educativas la diversidad cultural y lingüística que traen consigo los migrantes. Estos nuevos escenarios suponen nuevos retos educativos debido, entre otras causas, a los discursos de odio que proliferan de una manera incontrolada desde las redes sociales a los medios de comunicación e Internet en general y que se materializan en muchos casos en el día a día del centro escolar. Prueba de lo anteriormente dicho es la creciente tendencia a priorizar los estudios sobre el Discurso del Odio en el mundo del Derecho, de la Psicología, en Comunicación, etc. pero no tanto en el mundo educativo. Nuestro objetivo principal es realizar una revisión del desarrollo y estado actual de la

investigación sobre el Discurso del Odio y las posibles prácticas y estrategias para contrarrestar la proliferación de esta nueva pandemia.

La educación inclusiva se vuelve esencial para atender las necesidades del alumnado migrante y evitar situaciones de discriminación reforzando el sentido de la convivencia pacífica en los centros educativos. La igualdad de oportunidades, basada en la solidaridad y la participación escolar, debe ser promovida para garantizar una vida plena a todos los estudiantes. Para ello, utilizaremos una metodología cualitativa para analizar e interpretar a través de documentos académicos porque es necesario garantizar el acceso a una enseñanza gratuita y de calidad, eliminar las desigualdades en el ámbito educativo y luchar contra el racismo y la discriminación en las escuelas.

Desafortunadamente, el aumento del racismo y la xenofobia en la sociedad civil se refleja también en el entorno educativo, lo cual demanda una respuesta efectiva. Es importante abordar el discurso de odio y promover la convivencia en los espacios educativos, mediante intervenciones que contrarresten y prevengan estos problemas. La multiculturalidad y el respeto a la dignidad de los migrantes deben ser prioritarios en la agenda educativa, implementando políticas y acciones correctivas.

Aunque aún queda mucho por hacer, la educación se erige como el motor principal para abordar estos desafíos. Solo a través de un enfoque educativo que busque garantizar la equidad y la participación del estudiantado, sin importar sus características individuales, diferencias culturales, sociales o de habilidades, se podrá avanzar. Se trata de un modelo pedagógico basado en el respeto a la diversidad, que reconoce las necesidades y potencialidades de cada estudiante y se esfuerza por proporcionar un entorno de aprendizaje que promueva su pleno desarrollo académico, social y emocional. Ello implica la eliminación de barreras y la adopción de prácticas pedagógicas flexibles y adaptativas, así como la promoción de una cultura de respeto, tolerancia y aceptación de la diferencia en toda la comunidad educativa para construir un futuro común en el que se respeten los derechos humanos, se promueva la igualdad y se fomente la convivencia pacífica en la sociedad.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Migración, Educación, Convivencia, Discurso del odio, Libertad de expresión

EDUCATIONAL COLLABORATION AND INTERNATIONALIZATION IN CHINA: A CASE OF SINO- FOREIGN COOPERATIVE INSTITUTIONS

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Chinese students are one of the major groups to pursue higher education abroad, particularly in the United States (Henze & Zhu, 2012; Gong & Huybers, 2015; Chao et al., 2017). There is an increasing demand among Chinese students to obtain a more diverse educational experience (Zhang, 2019). Many higher education institutions worldwide seek pathways to construct a presence to fulfill this demand. The session aims to contribute to the discussion of the various factors in the newly internationalization reform plans in higher education in China, focusing on the emergence and formation process of the new model of collaboration in higher education between Chinese and universities in other countries. This session will use a case study approach to focus on the Sino-foreign joint universities as one of the models to illustrate how this type of collaboration functions. The inception of this type of partnership began with the Hopkins Nanjing Center in 1986. Since then, more than 2000 new collaborations have been established to encompass various levels of cooperation (Lin, 2016). These types of ventures in higher education are a depiction of transnational higher education. The session will offer a descriptive scholarly analysis of the overview and background of this form of collaboration based on the existing literature. The study will utilize the essential connection of scale, quality, and benefits as a theoretical framework to analyze this type of institutions (Lin, 2016). By adequately exploring the three factors, the study will facilitate the understanding of the fundamental relationships in Sino-foreign cooperative education. Current literature indicates that this type of venture contributes to the facilitation of further development and reform in China's education system (Ergenc, 2020). However, the model is highly individualized, and these institutions require tremendous support from the Chinese government for their operations (Ennew

& Yang, 2009). In addition, these sites are situated in the most developed cities in China and require high tuition, thereby limiting access and therefore feeding inequality in education. It is essential to understand the benefits and challenges of this emergent collaboration model as well as China's plans to become a global force in higher education to better inform other countries' future partnerships with China.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Internationalization, China, Sino-foreign Cooperative Institutions

ENRICHING PERSPECTIVES VIA CROSS-CULTURAL STUDENT FILMS

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The objective of this research presentation is to showcase how collaboration in the field of arts, within universities from different parts of the world, helps in expanding the global understanding and appreciation of other cultures, among students. I am a film faculty member teaching for the last thirteen years. My teaching philosophy relies heavily on internationalization. In my ten-minute research presentation, I will be highlighting three bi-lingual film projects I led, as cross-cultural collaboration, between Denver film students and their cohorts in India. I will show highlights from the film, talk about the research and learning experience across continents, and highlight the process of leading such a program, as a faculty member. In these thirteen years, I have had the opportunity of leading two study abroad programs, to Mumbai and Delhi, in India. Both times I flew film students to these places for two to three weeks, and we shot and produced two films on location. The first project was funded by a UROP full grant. I led a team of another faculty member and one student, to shoot a feature documentary in New Delhi, on road fatalities in India. The documentary titled, *The Golden Hour*, was completed in 2012. We followed a social entrepreneur named Piyush Tewari, who had lost his sixteen-year-old cousin to a road accident. Following that incident, he founded a road safety non-profit organization called SaveLIFE Foundation. We collaborated with students from New Delhi film institute to create a 60-minute documentary, which won at many global film festivals and is still streaming today on NDTV, India. The research methodology included data on road fatalities in India, and the work of SaveLIFE as well as detailed off- and on-camera interviews with Delhi government officials and police force. Please see the twenty-minute version here: <https://www.surcreations.com/thegoldenhour>. My presentation will highlight

this three-week production and show a short clip from the film. My second example is the study abroad two-week immersion program I led in 2019 to Whistling Woods International, Mumbai. I flew eleven film students and one music major to Mumbai and we shot a fifteen-minute film titled *Not Pictured* (<https://www.surcreations.com/not-pictured>). Research methodology included exploring the laws and policies of producing a bi-lingual film in a different cultural landscape. Crewing actors, getting permits and learning the norms and parameters of filming in a foreign land. Finally, I completed a documentary film, as a cross-cultural collaboration between students in Denver, and Seniors of Satyajit Ray Film Institute in Kolkata, India, during COVID and beyond. It was a two-year project. The film titled *MAA* (<https://www.surcreations.com/maadoc>) has screened at multiple global film festivals. Every department was a cross-collaboration between Denver and film students in India. This will be a ten-minute PowerPoint presentation with clips from the three films. Expected results will be to show the growth among students, and pedagogical approaches to creating works of art across cultures, in higher ed. Conclusion will focus on the accolades the films received and how that impacted the career charts of these students.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Cross-cultural Collaboration, Film Pedagogy, Diversity

THE NEXUS OF ACCULTURATION, FACEBOOK USE, AND HOMESICKNESS OF INTERNATIONAL STUDENTS IN AMERICAN COLLEGES

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

The current study analyzes the intersection of Acculturation, Facebook use, and Homesickness among college students while studying abroad in the US. Omori and Schwartz (2022) found in their study of international students' use of Facebook and Acculturation that international students frequently use Facebook as a way to affirm their cultural identity during the first and second semesters in the US. Building on this finding, the current study investigates the relationship between homesickness and cultural value orientation (Poyrazli & Devonish 2020), and use of Facebook using Berry's Acculturation Model (1990) and Communication Act Theory (Gallois, Ogay, & Giles 2005) as theoretical frameworks. Specifically, the study asks two research questions. "What is the relationship between SNS, acculturation, and homesickness and how does this relationship change over time? This longitudinal study seeks to understand how Facebook use facilitates or hinders international students' acculturation to American culture and homesickness. The researchers will gather data through in-depth interviews. Additionally, the researchers will observe and document international students' posts on a Facebook page setup especially for this study." The opportunity to participate in the study will be announced in university classes for international students studying in American colleges. Findings from the current study will extend our understanding as educators of what international students experience emotionally as they adjust to living in a new culture several thousand miles away from home and may help universities in providing support services for international students as they experience the ups and downs of cultural adjustment and homesickness.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Acculturation, Intercultural Communication, Study Abroad, Social Media, Homesickness

INTERNATIONAL AND DOMESTIC STUDENT EXPERIENCE IN AUSTRALIAN HIGHER EDUCATION: INSIGHTS FOR TRANSFORMATIVE AND EQUITABLE EDUCATION

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Universities have been increasingly paying attention to the student experience, which is seen as an important factor in improving the institution's quality and performance. While the topic has been taken up by previous studies, the multidimensionality of the student experience has yet not been fully considered. Furthermore, the increasing internationalization of higher education (HE) is resulting in a more diverse student body, reinforcing that the concept of a unidimensional student experience is no longer valid. Based on analysis of the Student Experience Survey (SES) data (n=208,734 undergraduate and postgraduate students from 39 HE institutions), this article provides empirical insights on how educational experience in Australian higher education differs for international and domestic students. Key results indicate that a range of factors impact on the different aspects of the student experience, and that the experiences of international students vary depending on the country or region of origin. The findings further indicate that being an international student moderates the effects of each aspect of the student experience on the overall educational experience. Specifically, the effects of teaching quality, followed by student support and skills development, on overall satisfaction are weaker among international students than among domestic students, while the effects of learner engagement and learning resources are stronger among international students than among domestic students. This research offers valuable insights for theory, policy, and practice in higher education, contributing to the goal of transformative education for an interconnected and equitable world. The results suggest that policy initiatives aimed at improving international student experience across multiple

dimensions can enhance overall educational experience, emphasizing the importance of investing in the international student experience as it is linked to university performance.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

International Students, Higher Education, Student Experience, Australia

INTERNATIONALIZATION OF HIGHER EDUCATION AND INTERNATIONAL STUDENT MOBILITY TO INDIA: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Internationalization of higher education (IoHE) as a strategic policy is a relatively new phenomenon in India. It is only very recently that the Government of India (GOI) has introduced a planned policy initiative with a vision to 'internationalize at home' and enhance the inward mobility of international students. Before this step, the recently introduced Education Policy (NEP 2020) also mentioned the intent for the same.

The present study reviews the literature on policies and practices relating to IoHE in India and the issue of inward mobility of international students. It uses the PRISMA model and VosViewer software to perform a systematic literature review (SLR) on peer-reviewed articles extracted from the Scopus and Google Scholar databases, coupled with the extraction of relevant documents from the Ministry of Education, GOI, and University Grants Commission (UGC) between 2000-2022. The key words "internationalization," "higher education," "university/ies", "international student mobility" and "international students in India" were used to extract articles and relevant documents.

The paper further attempts to analyze the relationship between IoHE and international student mobility based on this review of existing research/theoretical perspectives on IoHE, primarily through identifying dominant approaches and models of IoHE.

Preliminary findings suggest that India's policy agenda on IoHE is guided by the motive of making India an educational hub in Asia. In practice, however, it appears that myths about IoHE play out as dynamically as evidence-based approaches emanating from certain economic models of IoHE. Almost every second university in India, especially in and around metropolitan centres, is attempting to acquire recognition in the domain of being visible with the foreign students. However, we must engage in a constructive yet critical dialogue with the dominant models of IoHE and allied processes to debate sustainable pathways and models for destination India.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

Internationalization, Higher Education, India, Internationalization at Home, Inward Mobility, Economic Models

EXPLORING THE CULTURALLY RESPONSIVE EXPERIENCES OF INTERNATIONAL DOCTORAL STUDENTS IN CAREER DEVELOPMENT AND COUNSELING ON THE U.S. CAMPUSES

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RESUMO | RESUMEN | ABSTRACT

Many international students pursue doctoral education in the U.S. with the aim of seeking employment opportunities and achieving long-term permanent residency status in the country. The aim of this exploratory qualitative inquiry is to examine the experiences of international doctoral students as they seek career-related counseling and services for career development and success during their doctoral programs in U.S. higher education institutions. Given the increasing enrollment of international graduate students at the doctoral and master's levels in the U.S. in 2022 and its growing trend, it is important to understand and enhance their career outcomes. The purpose of this proposed study is to examine the experiences of international doctoral students' experiences during their career development and counseling process and how institutions respond to them culturally to support them for career success. Exploring the career needs and outcomes of international doctoral students is crucial for creating an inclusive, connected, and diverse campus in the U.S. This study will contribute to the literature regarding the career-related challenges and supports of international doctoral students in the U.S., which is particularly important given that they have oftentimes been described as "cash cow" and a minority in the past decades. This research will provide an avenue for institutions to subsequently address the career needs of international doctoral students with responsive approaches and equitable strategies.

PALABRAS CLAVE | KEYWORDS

International Doctoral Students, Graduate Students, Career Development, Career Counseling, Cultural Responsiveness

